

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D4.4 Training Report including Training Materials

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITE D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACION ESPANOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUCILISTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE DE L'UNIVERSITE	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSOE - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT

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UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
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UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAN LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

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Version	Created/Modified	Comments
0.1	Authors	Final draft for review
0.2	Reviewers	Review copy with comments
1.0	Authors	Final version

Acronyms

CAP	Common Access Point
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DNS	Domain Name System
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EDIB	Equity, Diversity, Including, and Belonging
EQSIP	Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing
ERA	European Research Area
HTP	HTML5 Package
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EDIB	Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Providers
OA	Open Access
SCORM	Sharable Content Object Reference Model
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
xAPI	eXperience API

Executive Summary

The report is a deliverable of the DIAMAS Task 4.4. It outlines the development of the training programme and training platform of the DIAMAS project. The programme comprises 34 training materials, including recordings of two webinars to onboard users on the platform. The training materials are organised into 14 courses - an introductory course that introduces the training pathway, and 13 courses focusing on the elements of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS). The programme is hosted on a Moodle installation accessible at <https://training.diamas.org/>. It is primarily intended for learners at an elementary level, with an aim to provide a comprehensive introduction to the principles and practices of Diamond Open Access publishing.

The report includes a description of the conceptual framework, writing process, and instructional design. It also presents the architecture of the training platform, its content structure, and learning pathways.

The report and the training materials can be accessed at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1543320>

Note on terminology

To ensure clarity and consistency throughout the document, the following terms are used to describe the elements developed by T4.4:

- **Training programme:** the complete, structured set of learning resources. It is designed to help learners achieve specific objectives and impart skills and knowledge to a defined audience.
- **Training pathway:** the various ways learners can navigate and engage with the training programme. Learners create their own pathway by choosing the courses that best suit their needs and completing them in their preferred order.
- **Course:** a structured learning unit, as a component of the overall training programme, designed to cover specific and coherent learning objectives. The term "course" is used in alignment with the terminology of the Moodle platform.
- **Moodle Section:** a structured presentation of the course elements: introduction, glossary, training materials, feedback questionnaire, etc.
- **Training Materials:** the individual learning resources provided within each Moodle Course. There are 34 training materials, including H5P elements and PDFs.
- **Chapters:** the training materials are organised into chapters and subchapters.

Introduction

Task 4.4 of the DIAMAS project focused on developing a comprehensive training programme for journal editors and Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSP) across the European Research Area (ERA).

The training programme addresses skill gaps identified in earlier project phases, with an aim to support IPSPs in adopting the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS, Consortium of the DIAMAS project 2024) and strengthen institutional Diamond OA publishing practices. The design of the programme began in June 2023 (month 10 of the project) and was led by OpenEdition. The task drew upon prior DIAMAS outputs – specifically the Toolsuite (Armengou et al., 2024i) and Guidelines (Armengou et al., 2024ii) – repackaging them into a modular, self-paced online training workflow.

The programme comprises 34 training materials, including recordings of two webinars (see chapter 4) to onboard users on the platform. The training materials are organised into 14 courses – a course that introduces the training pathway, and 13 courses focusing on the elements of DOAS. The programme is hosted on a Moodle installation which is part of the DIAMAS Common Access Point (CAP), and can be accessed at <https://training.diamas.org/>. It is primarily intended for learners at an elementary level, aiming to provide a comprehensive introduction to the principles and practices of Diamond OA publishing. Diverse learning approaches have been used, including interactive courses, infographics, simulated conversations and self-reflection tools, delivered mainly in H5P (an open-source tool for creating interactive HTML5 content) and PDF formats.

The materials have been designed for easy adaptation, which is anticipated as part of the ongoing enhancement and expansion of the training programme. The programme is currently available in English, with translations into other European languages planned to reach a wider audience and ensure broader accessibility.

The sections of this report provide a detailed account of the methodology and task outcomes. The report outlines the conceptual framework that guided the implementation, its relevance to prior DIAMAS deliverables, the writing process, and the instructional design methodology employed in developing the training programme. It also focuses on the platform's architecture and content, and describes the deployment process – including technical specifications, design choices, and user pathways. Additionally, it addresses the challenges encountered and the solutions implemented to mitigate them, and discusses the next steps and sustainability considerations for the content and technical infrastructure.

The report and the training materials can be accessed at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1543320>

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1. Methodology and development outcomes

This section outlines the methodological approach used to develop the training programme, and presents the key outcomes of its implementation, including the course structure, training materials, visual identity, and evaluation mechanisms.

1.1 Framework

1.1.1 Relevance to other DIAMAS deliverables

Task 4.4 builds directly on earlier work within the DIAMAS project, and the training programme was informed by the following key project outputs:

- "Institutional Publishing in the ERA" (Armengou et al, 2023): a landscape analysis based on the DIAMAS survey results. The report maps publishing practices across Europe, identifying common challenges and needs within the institutional and Diamond OA publishing ecosystem.
- Diamond Open Access Standard (Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024): findings from the landscape survey informed the development of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS), initially called the European Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) [Rico-Castro et al. 2024]. This framework provides comprehensive recommendations across seven core components essential for high-quality Diamond OA publishing.
- Report on the gap analysis results (Brun et al. 2023): the report examined the gaps between the EQSIP recommendations and actual institutional publishing practices. The analysis revealed four types of gaps: social (resource-related constraints), moral (differing value orientations), interpretative (linguistic or pragmatic differences), and practical (implementation hurdles). These insights helped identify the conceptual framework of the training, highlighting areas where publishers needed the most support.
- Dissemination and engagement plan (Blake et al., 2023). This document provided a detailed analysis of key actors within the IPSP landscape, which was essential to ensure the training programme addressed the diverse needs of the target audience.
- DOAS self-assessment tool, and Diamond Open Access sustainability check: these online tools (accessible at <https://diamas.fecyt.es/>) enable IPSPs to

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evaluate their current practices against the DOAS framework and identify improvement priorities.

- IPSP Toolsuite (Armengou et al, 2024): a collection of 15 high-level articles (accessible at <https://Toolsuite.diamas.org/Toolsuite-articles>) providing a comprehensive understanding of the seven core components of DOAS through detailed background information. The Toolsuite is complemented by a glossary of terms, keywords, and frequently asked questions (FAQs).
- IPSP Guidelines (Armengou et al, 2024): the Guidelines comprise 18 articles (accessible at <https://Toolsuite.diamas.org/Guidelines>) focusing on specific aspects of DOAS to provide actionable instructions and recommendations to IPSPs.

1.1.2 Writing Process

To ensure both pedagogical soundness and content accuracy, the development of the training programme was supported both by instructional designers and subject matter experts from the DIAMAS consortium. Co-authors and/or reviewers were assigned to each topic, and were encouraged to contribute throughout the development process. This collaborative approach facilitated a comprehensive review of the material at different stages of development.

OpenEdition - Instructional designers

The role of the team of instructional designers involved the overall coordination of material development, in alignment with specific learner needs. This included conducting content analysis to adapt existing materials, defining learning objectives, selecting appropriate instructional strategies, and developing the core learning content such as course scripts, training activities, and supplementary tools. An instructional designer was the lead author for course topics, ensuring consistency and coherence across the programme.

DIAMAS Consortium - Subject matter experts

The subject matter experts were selected from among the authors of the Toolsuite articles and the guidelines. Thus, they were already aware of the context and helped translate the findings and content of these resources into comprehensive courses, to ensure the accuracy and relevance of the training content. They also offered insights into the practical application of the training materials in varied contexts.

Review and feedback

Feedback was provided by project partners and experts from other projects and initiatives, such as the LIBER Working Groups.¹ The reviewers were asked to evaluate the overall structure of the programme, and assess the contents of its elements. Feedback was generally incorporated iteratively as the materials were developed, with some suggestions noted for consideration in subsequent versions. The review process identified gaps and areas for improvement. During the review phase, the Open Edition Moodle sandbox provided reviewers with access to the training materials in a learning environment, allowing them to evaluate the content from a learner's perspective.

1.2 Instructional design methodology

The training programme followed the ADDIE instructional design model, a widely adopted framework for creating effective training materials. ADDIE is an acronym for:

- Analysis: defining learning environments and target audience needs.
- Design: defining learning objectives, strategies, assessment methods, and course structure
- Development: creating and assembling learning materials and media.
- Implementation: delivering the training to learners.
- Evaluation: assessing the effectiveness of the training and making revisions.

The ADDIE model provides a logical sequence of steps for instructional design. In this project, it was implemented with a strong emphasis on iteration, particularly within the design and development phases. For example, initial design drafts were often revisited and revised as development progressed and subject matter experts provided further input, ensuring technical accuracy and offering valuable insights. This flexibility allowed for continuous refinement of the training materials, informed by feedback from the subject matter experts. The following sections provide a detailed account of the implementation of the ADDIE model during the preparation of the training programme.

1.3 Analysis

This foundational phase focused on a thorough review of project deliverables and resources, in order to understand the elements of the publishing ecosystem, and the specific needs of IPSPs within the ERA. This phase was designed to align the training as closely as possible with the specific and diverse needs and priorities of journal editors and IPSP managers. Key activities are described in the following subsections.

¹ <https://libereurope.eu/working-groups/>

1.3.1 Target audience analysis

A target audience analysis was conducted to define and understand potential learners – their professional contexts, motivations, and training needs.

The primary target audience includes journal editors and IPSP managers within the ERA, particularly those practicing Diamond Open Access or considering transition. At earlier stages the project has identified a wide range of IPSPs, including university presses, editorial service providers, educational publishers, international and local publishing platforms, scholarly societies, and libraries. Secondary audiences include trainers working with publishers, as well as stakeholders such as institutional leaders, policymakers, funders, and researchers engaged in scholarly communication.

The DIAMAS evidence-based resources provided useful insights into the key audience characteristics, and showcased that IPSPs constitute a heterogeneous community with diverse operational models, structures, resources, and variable levels of expertise. Many organisations function as publishers and service providers, simultaneously, creating complex organisational structures with varying levels of formalisation and professionalisation.

The target audience analysis resulted in identifying four key stakeholder groups who would benefit from structured training materials:

- Directors and managers of publishing services: university presses, Open Access journal publishers, and editorial boards who need guidance on flipping journals to Diamond OA, setting up new journals, and implementing best practices.
- Publishing professionals: copy editors, proofreaders, and other implementors who require practical training on editorial workflows and technical processes.
- Regional, national, or international publishing infrastructure providers: Journal hosting services and data centres seeking to support institutional publishers with documentation and training content.
- Standard & best practice providers: organisations like DOAJ, Sherpa Romeo, and Crossref who both inform and implement quality standards, and seek to provide practical guidance on how institutional publishers can meet current standards and best practices.

1.3.2 Contextual analysis

The analysis focused on the DIAMAS deliverable "Institutional Publishing in the ERA: Results from the DIAMAS survey" (Armengou et al., 2024i), which provides a comprehensive overview of open access publishing practices and challenges in the ERA. Another internal DIAMAS document focusing on IPSP use cases documented specific

challenges faced by these groups. The aim of the analysis was to identify key challenges to be addressed by the training programme. These include:

- **Fragmentation:** a lack of standardised practices across IPSPs leads to inefficiencies and inconsistencies in service quality.
- **Sustainability:** many publishers and service providers struggle to secure long-term funding and resources to maintain their operations in the long term. This is compounded by limited financial and human resources, as well as a dependency on external commercial services.
- **Quality Assurance:** challenges in introducing high editorial standards, evaluating research integrity, and ensuring technical reliability.
- **Adoption of Open Science Practices:** IPSPs face barriers in embedding Open Science principles into their workflows.
- **Equity and Inclusivity:** underfunded scientific communities often lack access to high-quality Open Access publishing services, exacerbating inequalities in scholarly communication.
- **Information overload:** IPSPs often face difficulty navigating the wealth of standards and recommendations, and struggle to find adequate training and education opportunities to address variable expertise levels within their teams.

These challenges highlighted the need for coordinated efforts to professionalise IPSPs, standardise practices, and strengthen long-term sustainability within the Diamond Open Access ecosystem.

Training approach development

Based on this analysis, the overall conceptual approach was formulated in accordance with the following basic principles:

- **Foundational level of instruction:** while some resources explore certain topics in depth, the overall focus is on facilitating a solid understanding of the fundamental concepts and practices. This foundational approach ensures that all participants, regardless of their background and level of expertise, can engage with the materials. The training programme provides a comprehensive introduction to Diamond Open Access publishing, with additional resources available for learners who wish to go further.
- **Practical guidance:** combined, the training materials directly address frequently requested information, such as how to successfully run an Open Access journal, understanding of common quality standards, and the development of Open Access policies.

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- **Resource diversity:** various content types (e.g. case studies, guidelines, actionable recommendations) and formats (e.g. infographics, interactive course, use cases) are provided to accommodate different learning preferences and contexts.
- **Self-directed learning pathways:** the modular structure enables users to select content most relevant to their specific profile, activities, and immediate needs, rather than requiring sequential completion. Guidance is provided in an introductory module to help users navigate through the training programme and select their own pathway.

1.3.3 Content analysis

An analysis of the IPSP Toolsuite and Guidelines was conducted to understand the distribution of articles and their relationships within the DOAS framework. The analysis revealed a variation in the distribution of articles across the DOAS framework components, resulting in varied density and sub-topics. These relationships are further illustrated in the following table.

DOAS	Toolsuite article	Guideline
1. Funding	1.0 Funding	Revenue streams
		Diamond OA policies
2. Ownership and governance	2.0 Ownership and governance	Implementing community-led governance in publishing services
		Copyright, authors' rights policy
3. Open science practices	3.0 Open science practices	Use of open licenses in open access publishing
		Research data sharing policy
		Preprints
		Self-archiving policy
4. Editorial quality, editorial management and research integrity	4.1 Editorial Quality	Handling negative research results
		Availability of research protocols, methods and software
		Basic editorial information that should be displayed
		4.2 Editorial management
5. Technical service efficiency	4.3 Research integrity	
	5.0 Technical service efficiency	Choosing a platform
	5.1 Software and interoperability	

	5.2 Metadata	Metadata formats and export, identifiers, CRediT tags, bibliographic references, JATS XML or equivalent
	5.3 Preservation and content formats	
6. Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact	6.0 Visibility, indexation, communication, marketing and impact	Marketing, communication and visibility
		Usage and metrics
7. Equity, Diversity and Inclusion	7.0 Equity, Diversity and Inclusion	
	7.1 Gender diversity	Gender diversity
	7.2 Accessible/inclusive website, content and metadata	Accessible/ inclusive website, content and metadata
	7.3 Multilingualism	Multilingualism

Table 1: Mapping of the training resources to the Toolsuite articles and the guidelines

The relationship between the resources in the table is characterised by hierarchy, complementarity, and varied scope: the 15 Toolsuite articles provide a conceptual interpretation of DOAS, introducing core principles and publisher considerations. The 18 Guidelines, on the other hand, offer guidance on practical implementation and actionable recommendations, by elaborating on the Toolsuite topics with a more granular approach.

Finally, while the Toolsuite and Guidelines collectively address a broad audience, our training courses are specifically targeted towards journal editors and IPSP managers. Therefore, a careful selection and rephrasing of the content was necessary to ensure relevance and effective knowledge transfer to this specific audience.

The content analysis informed the instructional design strategy. The varied distribution and nature of content within the Toolsuite and Guidelines indicate that a flexible training approach might be necessary. Whereas the structure of the training programme corresponds to DOAS and the Toolsuite, individual resources may not map directly to their elements, as they incorporate a range of learning strategies, formats, and module sizes to adapt to the different topics, content nature and levels of detail.

1.4 Design

This phase focused on developing the training materials, drawing upon the insights gained during the analysis phase. The following steps were taken:

1.4.1 Defining learning expectations

Defining learning expectations was a key activity, involving clarifying the skills, knowledge, and outcomes expected for the target audience. Learning outcomes are a cornerstone of effective instructional design, providing a clear roadmap for both the development and evaluation of training. They ensure that the training is focused, relevant, and measurable.

A syllabus detailing learner expectations, learning objectives, and learning outcomes for each course was created:

- **Learner expectations** describe the broader needs and aspirations of the learners entering the training programme. They articulate what learners hope to gain from the training in terms of their professional practice. Example: "Learners seek actionable strategies to ensure the financial sustainability of Diamond Open Access journals while adhering to DOAS core principles such as transparency and independence" (Funding course).
- **Learning objectives** are specific statements of what the learner will be able to do after completing the training. They define the intended skills and knowledge acquisition. Example: "Identify sustainable and ethical funding sources for Diamond journals" (Funding course).
- **Learning outcomes** are even more granular, detailing the measurable results of learning and often tied to specific activities within the course. For instance, in the "Funding" course, the learning outcome "Identify appropriate funding sources for Diamond OA journals, while recognising those that should be avoided or handled with caution" is directly related to a drag-and-drop activity designed to evaluate that specific skill.

The identification of those three complementary concepts facilitates the foundation for course design in the following ways:

- It serves as a sense-check for the author (who may not be a subject matter expert), ensuring he/she has correctly understood the material and can translate it into actionable learning goals.

- It directly informs the learning strategies, guiding the selection of appropriate teaching methods and assessment activities. It also dictates what is evaluated and how (e.g., drag-and-drop exercises, multiple-choice questions, etc.).
- It helps adapt the course to the specific needs of the target audience, ensuring that the training goes beyond simply repackaging existing documents and instead provides targeted, practical skills.
- It provides a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of the training. Notably, one of the questions in the feedback questionnaire is: "Which learning outcomes/goals do you think you achieved?"

1.4.2 Course structuration

Some of the seven basic components of DOAS were divided into separate courses, each addressing specific learning objectives. This modular approach enables users to focus on topics that are most relevant to specific roles and responsibilities within an organisation. For example, a user might be interested in learning about copyright and licensing, but not preprints or open peer review—even though all are part of the "Open Science Practices" component of DOAS.

The training programme consists of 14 courses, with a corresponding number of 34 training materials, as presented in Annex 1 of the report:

1. **General introduction:** introduction to DOAS and the components of the training programme.
2. **Funding:** addressing financial sustainability of a Diamond OA journal while upholding the core principles of transparency and editorial independence.
3. **Ownership and Governance:** essential aspects to consider when establishing governance and ownership structures in Diamond OA publishing.
4. **Open policies:** effective sharing policies for data, protocols, software, and negative results to enhance research quality, transparency, and impact.
5. **Copyright and licenses:** copyright and licensing policies that balance author rights with open knowledge-sharing principles.
6. **Preprints and repositories:** management of preprints, repository deposits, and self-archiving practices to enhance research visibility/dissemination and preservation/long-term accessibility.
7. **Open peer review:** Exploring transparent and open review models
8. **Editorial quality and management:** measures to enhance editorial quality of a journal
9. **Research integrity:** policies, prevention and effective workflows for addressing misconduct concerns

10. **Choosing a software:** Selecting appropriate publishing platforms
11. **Metadata:** Structuring information for discovery and preservation
12. **Digital preservation:** Ensuring long-term access to content
13. **Visibility, discoverability and impact:** effective indexing strategies, targeted communication approaches, and responsible metrics.
14. **Equity, diversity, inclusion, belonging:** enhancing publishing quality, fairness and impact through EDIB strategies on gender diversity, multilingualism and accessibility.

The transcripts of the training materials can be found in Annex 2 of the report

1.4.3 Learning strategies

To facilitate learning and enhance user experience of the training platform, a variety of strategies have been selected. These were based on the nature and complexity of the topics, the most effective approaches to implementation, as well as the technical feasibility using the development tools available.

The courses of the training programme reflect variable types of logical progression. The courses on “Funding” and “Ownership and Governance” employ narrative frameworks through simulated conversations, thus making complex governance and financial concepts more accessible. Accordingly, the course on “Editorial Quality” applies comparative analysis, presenting contrasting examples of effective and ineffective practices to develop critical evaluation skills. The “EDIB” course follows a scenario-based approach, beginning with concrete examples of bias before introducing broader concepts and practices. Technical courses like the course on “Metadata” and “Software” are based on structured implementation guides that evolve from requirements to specific solutions. Courses related to Open Science effectively compare traditional and open approaches, helping publishers understand both the “why” and “how” of implementation. A “problem-centered” approach common to all courses frames content around specific challenges that publishers face rather than introducing abstract concepts, and is complemented with interactive elements that reinforce understanding through practical application.

Evaluation of acquired knowledge is another key component of the course structure: the course on “Funding” uses scenario-based challenges that require learners to apply knowledge to real-world decisions, while the course on “EDIB” employs a discrimination scenario to strengthen user’s essential skills. Other courses leverage comparative evaluation tasks, where learners are asked to analyse contrasting website elements to identify best practices. Technical courses like “Metadata” and “Software Selection” include practical checklists and self-assessment tools that guide implementation decisions. Many courses incorporate interactive elements with immediate feedback,

such as flashcards and knowledge checks. Combined, these assessment workflows introduce directly transferrable skills and emphasise problem-solving, recognition of good practices, decision-making, and practical application.

Consequently, the training programme uses a range of instructional patterns, including:

- Elements that provide structured presentation of information (for example, in modules like “Metadata” and “Copyright and Licenses”), where foundational knowledge precedes practical application. These elements incorporate interactive features such as expandable definitions and knowledge checks to maintain engagement.
- Scenario-based learning features (prominently in courses related to Funding and Ownership), where simulated conversations guide learners through realistic publishing challenges. Accordingly, the courses on “EDIB” and “Editorial Quality” present concrete situations requiring critical analysis and decision-making.
- Infographics that offer concise and visually appealing summaries of key concepts and practices. They are primarily used in the courses related to “Digital preservation”, “Open policies” and “Funding”.
- Self-reflection guides that provide structured assessment frameworks that help publishers evaluate their current practices and identify specific areas of improvement, in modules such as “Choosing a Software” Platform and “Visibility”

These differentiated approaches have been applied in a complementary manner to create a comprehensive learning experience that balances theoretical understanding with practical implementation.

1.4.4 Content adaptation

The content of the Toolsuite articles and the Guidelines was refined by prioritising elements that aligned with the learning objectives and, more broadly, with publishers’ needs. Where necessary, the resources were enriched with additional information, while maintaining non-technical language.

Adaptation also depended on the learning format. For instance, content designed for conversation-based modules, featuring a dialogue between fictional characters (an expert and a learner), was structured to facilitate this question-and-answer exchange, guiding the learner through the information. In contrast, information presented in infographics was distilled into its most concise and impactful form.

Finally, adaptation extended to the creation of interactive learning activities, such as flashcards, multiple-choice questions (MCQs), drag-and-drop exercises, and fill-in-the-

blank questions, leveraging the functionalities offered by the H5P tool to enhance engagement, knowledge retention and understanding.

1.5 Development

This phase of the ADDIE framework involved the production of the training materials (the individual learning resources provided within each Moodle course).

1.5.1 Types of training materials

During the Design phase, the team of instructional designers identified the formats that best support the training objectives, taking into account accessibility, reusability, and sustainability requirements. The training materials were developed as interactive HTML5 content, using H5P. H5P was implemented as the principal development tool for several practical reasons: as an open-source framework, it is specifically designed for the creation of interactive educational content and offers compatibility with the Moodle platform. Furthermore, it supports both reuse and translation, and provides a variety of content types. The H5P content types used include:

- **Presentations:** for delivering structured content with text, images, and interactive elements
- **Interactive books:** for multi-chapter content requiring a more comprehensive reading experience
- **Documentation tools:** for frameworks and self-assessment instruments
- **Multiple-choice questions:** for knowledge checks and self-assessment activities

Each content type was selected upon assessing the specific learning objectives and content requirements of each instance of training materials.

In addition to H5P content, PDF documents were created for infographics. These were designed using Canva to present complex information in a visual format. The PDF format was chosen for its ease of download and offline accessibility, and Canva was selected for its robust design capabilities, enabling the creation of visually engaging and informative graphics.

Ultimately, the decision was made to prioritise these text-based interactive materials over video formats due to their enhanced maintainability, ease of translation, and greater adaptability to diverse learning contexts.

1.5.2 Graphic design

The graphic design of the resources is constrained by the limited customisation options available in the H5P formats. Typography choices are fixed, and layout, composition, and

certain accessibility elements are largely predetermined by the H5P framework. This uniformity across H5P resources ensures a baseline level of consistency, but limits opportunities for extensive graphic customisation.

The infographics were developed using Canva, which offers a wider choice of design elements compared to H5P. The infographics share a consistent design structure: glacial indifference for titles and TT Fors for content, the DIAMAS logo at top right, and the Creative Commons logo at bottom right.

Both the H5P resources and infographics follow the same colour palette. The primary colours blue (#365ca9) and orange (#fcb316) are based on the DIAMAS graphic chart. To enhance accessibility and visual appeal, three complementary lighter tones were added: soft cream (#fdf7f0), light blue (#dee9ff), and pale orange (#fee9ba). These colours improve accessibility by providing better contrast options and maintaining visual harmony, while also adding warmth and facilitating a clearer visual hierarchy.

1.6 Implementation

The implementation phase focused on the parallel development of the training programme and the Training Platform, with the structure of the learner pathway and the integration of training materials informing the platform's design - and vice versa. This section details the implementation of the training programme and its elements; the platform's general setup is described in Chapter 2.

1.6.1 Training programme

The training programme was implemented on the Training Platform to guide users through the training materials. A key requirement was to ensure that materials could function both within the platform and as standalone resources. This approach led us to create self-contained core learning content with platform elements designed to enhance and support this material. The programme includes:

- An introductory onboarding course: this course introduces learners to the training programme and provides essential information such as licensing details and contact information.
- Individual course pages: these pages host the training materials and include supplementary resources to support users, such as:
 - Introduction
 - Glossary
 - Feedback questionnaire
 - List of relevant DIAMAS resources

- List of related courses

To ensure proper attribution when materials are used outside the platform, license information is embedded directly within each resource (e.g., in infographics and H5P interactive resource metadata).

1.6.2 Learning pathway

The DIAMAS training materials are integrated into a wider collection of resources to support IPSPs. It is expected that users are familiar with the DOAS framework, potentially through the DOAS self-assessment tool (available at <https://diamas.fecyt.es/>), and the Toolsuite, where links to relevant courses have been added. The references to the Toolsuite articles and the Guidelines can enrich the learning experience, by providing context and additional information.

Learners can access courses in two ways: the "General Introduction" course, featured on the platform's homepage, serves as a starting point for users. Alternatively, the "Explore" page offers a rich browsing experience, supported by filters and a search functionality to pinpoint specific courses of interest. To facilitate informed choices, each course is presented with a clear title, a concise summary outlining its scope, and relevant keywords indicating its focus.

As described above, the courses follow a common structure: a detailed introduction informs learners about the scope and contents of each course, and is complemented with a glossary of essential terms to ensure understanding of concepts. Learners can then browse through the core training materials, and complete a feedback questionnaire to reflect on their learning experience and provide feedback. To formally acknowledge completion of a course, they are asked to mark the training materials and the feedback questionnaire as "complete", as described in the section below. An option to explore additional resources that may be referenced, other DIAMAS resources, and related courses is also offered.

1.7 Evaluation

This final phase focuses on the implementation of a workflow to assess training effectiveness and foster continuous improvement. The feedback mechanism is based on a short survey (cf. Annex 2) that captures multiple dimensions of the learning experience –including content relevance, alignment with prior knowledge and learning outcomes, instructional quality, etc.

A "Mark as complete" functionality for all training materials (both H5P interactive content and PDF resources) was implemented to enhance user engagement and monitor

progress. This feature serves multiple purposes: it provides learners with a visual indicator of their progress, generates data for programme evaluation, and motivates users through achievement recognition. This functionality was replicated in the feedback questionnaire to encourage its completion and maximise response rates.

The current evaluation framework intentionally prioritises lightweight, integrated assessment methods. While more robust credentialing mechanisms like certificates and badges were considered, their implementation presents several methodological challenges within this programme context. Specifically, the training programme incorporates interactive activities but no formal assessments, and completion tracking relies on manual user action rather than automated platform monitoring. Though these factors somewhat limit the formal credibility of potential certification, the technical infrastructure could support the introduction of certificates, should future iterations require this functionality.

This evaluation framework enables platform administrators to gather valuable metrics: user engagement statistics (course starts and completions), content relevance to professional contexts, prior knowledge levels of participants, specific learning outcomes achieved, practical application insights, alignment with learner needs, and quality assessments across multiple dimensions (clarity, usefulness of examples, appropriate length, navigation ease, design effectiveness, and overall user experience).

2. Deployment of the Training Platform

This section outlines the technical structure of the Training Platform, addressing the main aspects of its development and deployment.

2.1. Financing

The Training Platform has been deployed as a standalone installation managed by OpenEdition. Its initial development and the annual subscription to the selected Moodle Partner (until March 2026), has been funded by the *Consortium for Shared Resources for Open Services and Data in the Humanities and Social Sciences* ([COMMONS](#)). COMMONS is one of the selected projects under the "Structuring Equipment for Research: EquipEx+" call, supported by France's Investments for the Future programme (PIA 3). OpenEdition is a co-recipient of the grant, alongside Métopes and Huma-Num.

2.2. Implementation timeline

2.2.1. Phase 1. Contractor selection and project initiation (January - February 2025)

OpenEdition selected E-learning Touch', a certified Moodle partner based in France (see contractor information below) to carry out the project. E-learning Touch' has been OpenEdition's partner since 2022. It has been involved in the original setup of OpenEdition's Learning Management System (<https://training.openedition.org/>), and is currently responsible for hosting and maintaining the service. Accordingly, E-Learning Touch' will provide the technical services and support for the Training Platform - including security workflows, software updates as well as planning and implementation of future developments.

Contractor Information

Website: <https://www.elearningtouch.com/>

Profile

- E-learning Touch' is a [certified Moodle Partner](#): they are officially recognised for their expertise and best practices in Moodle development, hosting, and maintenance.

- They operate under SCOP legal status in French law (worker cooperative): it is collectively owned and democratically governed by its employees.

Scope of services offered: E-learning Touch' is responsible for hosting, maintenance (updates, backups, uptime monitoring, security patches), and technical support. The contractor provides 8 hours of technical support (to OpenEdition) per year which are included in its yearly subscription fee.

Platform server location: The platform is hosted on an AWS server located in France, ensuring that all data remains under European jurisdiction and complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

2.2.2 Phase 2. Development and testing (March - May 2025)

Development and testing took place between early March and May 12th 2025 on a staging environment, which was launched for the initial setup and will be used for future developments.

OpenEdition was responsible for the general design of the platform and coordinated the technical improvements, such as: platform UX enhancements, CSS customisation, website architecture, quality insurance, course creation, course UX design, integration of training materials. E-Learning Touch' implemented OpenEdition's customisation requests that required higher permission levels (server-side).

2.2.3 Phase 3. Rollout, debugging, and official launch (May 2025)

The transition from the test environment to the production environment took place in May. The database from the staging platform was cloned to a separate Moodle installation to create the public interface of the Training Platform, which is now live and accessible at: <https://training.diamas.org>

The main tasks in this phase included:

- Final validation of functionalities and content on the staging site prior to cloning.
- Cloning of the database and necessary files to ensure consistency between the two environments.
- Post-cloning verification and debugging to ensure the platform operated as expected.
- Opening of the platform to the target audience following successful tests (May 26th, May 28th).

2.3 Technical specifications

The Training Platform is hosted on Moodle, a widely used Open-Source Management learning system.

2.3.1 Configuration, design, functional setup

The platform was developed to meet the following standards:

- High discoverability of courses and training materials
- Easy access to all learning resources
- Technical scalability
- Interoperability with other systems and platforms (e.g., potential integration of a Single Sign-On mechanism), including Drupal that has been used for the development of the Toolsuite online installation.

Technical specifications	
Technical aspect	Description
URL (Home page)	https://training.diamas.org
Moodle version	4.5
Script	PHP
Server location	France (Paris area)
Server type	Amazon Web Services (AWS)
Security	HTTPS enforcement, session timeout, password renewal
Theme	BoostUnion
Graphic charter	DIAMAS color palette and font family
Access restrictions	No geographical restrictions are applied for platform access and authentication
Authentication methods	Account creation requires ID and password creation. Authentication by name, first name, city, and country is necessary to access course content.
User interface language	English and French. Other language packages can be added.

Additional technical set-up	Bootstrap 5 (natively supported by Moodle 4.5). H5P library, a HTML 5-based authoring tool used to create interactive learning resources
Search	The platform is equipped with a search engine that supports course-level keyword search on the following elements: course titles and descriptions, section titles and descriptions, activity names and descriptions
Course categories	See “Training Platform information structure”
Course enrolment	Self-enrolment is activated by default on the platform
Filters	In addition to default configurations, search options and filters were added to the “Explore” page in order to facilitate platform navigation and course discovery.
Course indexation	Keywords are used at course level to allow indexation.
Progress monitoring (user)	Course progression indicators based on activity/achievement (self-checked) are activated by default to help users track progress.
Accessibility settings	Double navigation is supported to allow course navigation through Moodle native architecture (accessible-ready).
Analytics (course managers)	Course-level achievement reports are available to users who have teacher roles (or higher permissions).
Licensing	CC ATTRIBUTION 4.0 INTERNATIONAL LICENSE, unless otherwise indicated at course level.

2.3.2 Domain Name System (DNS) and Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) handling

In order for the platform to be available under the selected subdomain (training.diamas.org), DNS configurations were applied. As the DNS for this domain is managed by OPERAS, any changes – such as those required for both domain redirection and the configuration of the automated email delivery system via Mailjet – require coordination between E-learning Touch (the platform's technical provider) and OPERAS.

2.3.3 Security, access control, and data Integrity

Security features	Description
Sitewide URL encryption	HTTPS encryption is activated by default on all pages of the website. The platform's SSL/TLS certificate (Let's Encrypt) is regularly renewed and automatically managed.
Platform administration account restrictions	Two named administrator accounts with administrative rights on the platform are granted to the OpenEdition team. Platform administration control involves user, course and category management as well as role attribution to users with more restricted permissions.
User password encryption	Hashing (bcrypt)
User password security policy	Passwords must be 8 characters long or more and have at least <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 digit - 1 lowercase letter - 1 uppercase letter - 1 non alpha-numeric character
User password renewal	Password renewal is user-initiated. Administrators can enforce a password change for all users if needed – for example, after a security update or policy change.
User permissions	User permissions are defined by Moodle's in-build role-based system. By default, a user who creates an account and logs in to the platform is granted a student role, with permissions limited to this role.
Data retention	See GDPR compliance (2.3.9)
Platform updates (security, Moodle versioning)	Minor and major platform updates are applied to the platform according to security and performance enhancement needs. Timing is discussed with the contractor to minimise service disruptions and maintain platform availability.
Minor and major updates policy	The platform is only updated to Long Term Release (LTR) versions of Moodle, as defined by Moodle HQ. This approach ensures stability and long-term support while

	minimising the risks associated with frequent version changes.
Email and SMTP Security	Email delivery is managed via Mailjet, a GDPR-compliant provider based in France, with all data processed and stored within the European Union. Configured in transactional mode only, Mailjet ensures no user tracking or profiling. Sent emails and related logs are retained for 60 to 90 days for deliverability monitoring. E-learning Touch' has signed a Data Processing Agreement (DPA) with Mailjet, which is ISO 27001 certified. The setup is reversible, as Moodle supports flexible SMTP configuration.
Backup and recovery procedures	The Training Platform is subject to regular backup procedures managed by Elearning Touch. Backups are performed on a daily basis and are stored on servers in France. The retention period for these backups is 7 days, and recovery procedures are in place to restore the platform in case of failure or data loss.

2.3.4 Language packages

The Training Platform currently supports two language packages: English and French. These packages allow users to navigate the interface and access system messages in their preferred language. Additional European language packages can be deployed in the future to support broader multilingual access.

2.3.5 Accessibility enhancement (for users with disabilities)

To support users with disabilities, the Training Platform integrates accessibility-conscious design elements. A double navigation system has been implemented, allowing users to access both the customised 'Explore' page (course catalogue) and Moodle's native index and category pages, which are keyboard-navigable and screen-reader compatible. This approach ensures multiple pathways to course discovery. A dedicated "Course list view" button has been added to the Explore page to provide an alternative for users relying on assistive technologies.

Several improvements have been made to improve the colour contrast ratio of various UX components in various contexts.

2.3.6 Platform load capacity

Based on the current server specifications and Moodle configuration provided by E-learning Touch', the platform is technically able to support up to 80 concurrent users accessing the same training resource (e.g., PDF infographics, H5P interactive content) without degradation in performance.

2.3.7 Portability and ownership

OpenEdition retains full ownership and control over the Training Platform and is in no way contractually bound to continue using the services of E-learning Touch'. Should OpenEdition choose to migrate the platform to a different hosting environment, E-learning Touch' is contractually required to provide a full export of the platform, including all data, plugins, logs, and detailed server configuration information, ensuring the platform's complete portability and continuity.

2.3.8 Interoperability

The Training Platform was designed to ensure high levels of interoperability, enabling future integration with external systems and services. Key interoperability features include:

- Core support for standard protocols such as SCORM (1.2) and LTI (Learning Tools Interoperability). Moodle can 4.5 support xAPI through additional plugins, enabling content exchange and tool integration.
- Single Sign-On (SSO) readiness, allowing for potential future integration with external authentication systems.
- Structured course metadata (tags, filters, categories) to support data interoperability, searchability, and course discovery across platforms.
- Standardised content formats, including HTML5 and H5P, ensuring compatibility with other digital learning environments and content reuse.
- Scalable architecture designed to support technical developments and evolving interoperability requirements as the platform grows.

2.3.9 GDPR compliance, Cookies, Terms and legal notices

Personal data is collected for the purpose of managing user accounts, delivering training content, supporting learning progress, and maintaining platform security. All data is securely stored on servers located in France.

OpenEdition acts as the data controller, with E-learning Touch' as the data processor.

- The [Privacy Policy page](#) provides details and the contact information for data protection requests, which allow users to exercise their rights under the GDPR and ask questions about how their data is processed.
- The Training Platform uses only essential cookies required for secure login, session management, and basic user preferences. No analytics, advertising, or tracking cookies are used. Full details and guidance on managing cookies are available in the [Cookies Policy](#) page.
- A [Terms and Legal notices](#) page outlines the legal framework governing the use of the Training Platform. It defines the conditions of access, acceptable use, intellectual property, and data protection in accordance with French law.

2.4 Information structure

2.4.1 Design and development

The set up of the information structure of the Training Platform included two steps:

1. Design

- a. Defining course categories and their labelling, defining course keywords/tags, defining a course filtering system (search filters). The basic information structure (choice of course categories, filter types, filters, tags) was co-designed by OpenEdition in partnership with DIAMAS partners, in alignment with the structure applied to related deliverables (DOAS, Toolsuite, Guidelines).
- b. Defining page types (contact page, FAQ page, etc.) and writing content.

2. Technical tasks:

- a. Defining how to implement the choices made at design phase.
- b. Defining where to apply the choices made at design phase.
- c. Making adjustments and improvements to the platform UX to offer a coherent/cohesive user experience (ex: CSS, Javascript modifications).

The design and technical implementations were based on the condition that user experience of the platform depends on:

- Whether a user is authenticated or not on the platform
- The type of pages (dynamic or static) that a user visits
- The previous activity of logged-in users on the platform, that may influence the content a user sees (for example, whether a user needs to enrol in a course or has already enrolled).
- The roles and permissions a user has on the platform that influence what they can or cannot see, in various contexts

[D4.4 Training report]

- The tasks that course manager or an administrator perform on the platform (for example, creating a course and assigning a category to it, or designating a date of availability for a course), which have a direct impact on what a user can see.

The overall structure of the platform is influenced by the often-complex interplay between user status (logged in / logged off), page types (static, dynamic, static with dynamic components), and pages whose content is influenced by user behaviour.

The following categorisation provides an understanding of the Training Platform's structure and content interrelations:

1. Static pages (logged-in and logged-off users).
2. System-driven dynamic pages (logged-in and logged-off users).
3. User-behaviour-driven dynamic pages (logged-in users).

2.4.2 Static pages (logged-in and logged-off users)

These are informational pages whose content is manually authored and remains relatively fixed over time. They are not based on user data or user activity.

Homepage	
Title - Details	location
<p>Home page (Welcome to EDCH Training Platform)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Platform mission statement ● Featured update ● Content access instructions ● Training categories (snippet view) ● Course catalogue preview* ● Support <p>*This component of the Homepage is dynamic</p>	<p>https://training.diamas.org/</p>
<p>Sitewide footer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Links to static pages (internal) ● Links to external services ● EU Funding Disclaimer 	<p>Legal Information Privacy Policy Cookies Policy Terms and Legal Notices</p> <p>Related Services Registry & Forum Self-Assessment Tool Resources & Guidelines</p> <p>Support FAQ Contact us</p> <p><small>Unless otherwise indicated, all materials in EDCH Training are licensed under the CC Attribution 4.0 International license.</small></p> <p><small>Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed herein do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Commission. Neither the European Union nor the Commission can be held responsible for them.</small></p>

Information pages	
Title - Details	location
<p>Privacy policy Outlines how the Training Platform collects, uses, and protects user data in compliance with the GDPR. It details the types of data collected, the legal bases for processing, the parties who have access (including platform administrators and service providers), and the security measures in place. It also informs users of their data rights, storage duration, and the limited use of essential cookies. For data protection matters, users are directed to a contact address linked to the privacy policy.</p>	<p>https://training.diamas.org/privacy-policy</p>
<p>Cookies policy Describes the limited and essential use of cookies on the Training Platform. It explains the purpose and types of cookies used—mainly session and persistent cookies necessary for secure login and platform functionality. Users are informed on how to manage cookies via their browser settings, and as only essential cookies are used, no consent banner is required under GDPR. The policy also outlines future provisions should non-essential cookies be introduced.</p>	<p>https://training.diamas.org/cookies-policy</p>
<p>Terms and Legal Notices Outline the conditions for using the Training Platform. They cover user account management, acceptable behaviour, and responsibilities regarding content and data protection. The document clarifies content licensing (Creative Commons BY 4.0), intellectual property of user contributions, and legal disclaimers regarding service availability and liability. It also states the applicable legal framework (French law) and provides contact information for legal or technical inquiries.</p>	<p>https://training.diamas.org/terms-and-legal-notice</p>
<p>FAQ Provides answers to common questions for users (learners and trainers). It covers the platform's purpose, target audience, access procedures, types of available training materials, licensing information, and Guidelines for reusing and adapting content. The page also addresses course formats and language availability.</p>	<p>https://training.diamas.org/faq</p>
<p>Contact us Provides guidance for reaching the Training Platform support team. It lists the types of assistance available—technical issues, content questions, login problems, and</p>	<p>https://training.diamas.org/contact</p>

accessibility requests—and invites users to contact the team via email. Responses are typically provided within 2–3 business days. For data protection matters, users are directed to a separate contact address linked to the privacy policy.

[act](#)

2.4.3 System-driven dynamic pages (logged-in and logged-off users)

These pages are generated based on real-time system data input such as modifying the information structure (course categories, course tags), adding a course, or adding a resource within a course. Only users with specific roles and permissions – such as Administrator, Manager, or Course Creator – are granted permissions to make these changes.

Explore Page	
Title - Details	location
<p>Explore page Contains two sections: main content and a faceted filter panel (sidebar)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main content. All courses added to the platform, displayed as interactive cards. The title of the course is shown by default, and an hover action (mouse pointer on the card) unveils course summary and call-to-action button to the course • Sidebar. Sidebar contains a platform search engine and a customisable faceted filter panel. 	<p>https://training.diamas.org/explore</p>
Course index page and category pages	
Title - Details	location
<p>Courses The Course Index page provides a complete, structured list of all courses available on the platform. It serves as an alternative navigation method to the "Explore" page (which features a button linking to this page "Course list view"), particularly beneficial for accessibility purposes, screen readers, and users who prefer or require a text-based interface.</p>	<p>https://training.diamas.org/course/index.php</p>
<p>[Name of the category] Accessible from the Homepage and from the Course index page. Each course category page presents a</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding, sustainability and governance • Editorial management

<p>curated list of courses which have the related category assigned to them. These pages serve both as navigation aids and as contextual entry points into the training offer. Each category includes a brief description outlining its focus and objectives, helping users understand the scope of the content before exploring individual courses.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal and ethical issues • Technical aspects • Promotion, dissemination and indexing • General
Course description pages	
Title - Details	Location
<p>[Name of the course]</p> <p>Accessible from the Homepage, the Explore page, the course category index, the course category pages. Course description pages provide an overview of each course before or after enrolment, including a summary of the topic, key learning takeaways, estimated completion time, learning level, available formats, mode of delivery, and language(s).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOAS · General introduction • DOAS · Ownership and Governance • DOAS · Choosing a software • DOAS · Copyright and licenses • DOAS · Digital preservation • DOAS · Editorial quality and management • DOAS · Equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging • DOAS · Funding • DOAS · Metadata • DOAS · Open policies • DOAS · Preprints and repositories • DOAS · Research integrity
Tag index page	
Title - Details	Location
<p>Search tags</p> <p>The tag index page displays all the tags used on the platform to taxonomise courses. Tags are presented in a tag crowd with a larger or smaller display according to tag usage.</p>	<p>Search tags</p>
Tag index entry pages	
Title - Details	Location
<p>Tag entry page</p> <p>Accessible from the tag index page, or from clickable hashtags on each course description page, a tag entry</p>	

page displays all items (such as courses, resources, or activities) associated with a specific tag. It serves as a thematic landing page, helping users explore content linked to a particular topic or keyword.

[Example of a tag index entry page](#)

2.4.4. User-behaviour-driven dynamic pages (logged-in users)

These pages adapt their content based on the actions or status of the logged-in user. For example, they may display personalised course lists, progress tracking, or user-specific recommendations

User profile page	
Title - Details	Location
Profile Available from the user menu (top right corner). It displays personal information and activity data specific to the logged-in user. It includes details such as enrolled courses, last access, forum posts, and badges earned. This page serves as a personal snapshot, helping users monitor their engagement and contributions across the platform.	https://training.diamas.org/user/profile.php
User dashboard	
Title - Details	Location
Dashboard Reachable from the logged-in navigation menu. It offers a personalised overview of the user's learning environment. It dynamically lists enrolled courses, upcoming deadlines, recent activity, and progress tracking. This central page is designed to support self-navigation and help users stay organised in their training journey.	https://training.diamas.org/my
User preference page	
Title - Details	Location
Preferences Available from the user menu (top right corner). It allows users to manage key	https://training.diamas.org/user/preferences.php

aspects of their personal account and learning experience.	
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2.4.5 Navigation menus

Display of navigation menus depends on whether a user is logged-on or logged-off the platform.

- Menu (user logged off): Homepage link; Explore page
- Menu (user logged in): Home link; Explore page; FAQ; Dashboard

2.4.6-Footer area

The footer area is used to give users sitewide access to platform pages, contact pages and links to other services.

2.4.7 Course categories

Current platform categories are:

- Funding, sustainability and governance
- Editorial management
- Legal and ethical issues
- Technical aspects
- General
- Promotion, dissemination and indexing

2.4.8 Course filters (Explore page)

Filters are expansible and are particularly useful as the number of courses added to the platform grows. They can be modified to reach better relevance or filtering adequacy according to the evolution of the platform.

The following filters can be used on the Explore page, in the faceted filter panel:

- Learning level: foundational, advanced
- Resources: video/webinars, mixed resources
- Languages: English/French
- Learning structure: Part of a learning path, standalone course/material

Faceted filter panel also contains categories filters.

2.5 User(learner) journey map: from course discovery to course enrolment

Self-enrolment is activated by default on each course.

1. From any page of the Training Platform, a user (logged-in or logged-off) can:
 - a. go to the Explore page which displays all available courses on the platform in the form of course cards, with a sidebar containing search and filters to filter through results.
 - b. (from the Explore page), use a “Course list view” button to switch to Moodle native navigation (categories and courses index).
2. Clicking on a course card leads to a Course description page with relevant course information and an Enrol call-to-action button.
3. Upon clicking on “Enrol”, a user is directed to an authentication form where he can either create an account or log in to the platform.
4. Authentication process includes validation by email upon account creation
5. Once logged-in, a user can enrol on a course and have direct access to course materials.

3. Challenges and solutions

3.1 Adapting the documentation into training materials

Transforming existing documents into engaging training materials presented significant challenges when the source materials were not inherently educational. The fundamental question that drove our approach was: "How could a training material add value beyond simply reading the original articles?" This question became especially relevant when facing source content that consisted primarily of information catalogues or prescriptive checklists rather than instructional narratives. Several articles were simply informational lists or procedural guidelines that, at first glance, seemed sufficient on their own without pedagogical enhancement.

To address these limitations, we developed three distinct adaptation strategies:

1. **Simplified visual transformations:** for content where comprehensive courses seemed excessive, we created concise infographics that synthesised and reorganised the information into visually appealing and structured formats. This approach preserved the essential content while making it more digestible than the original text-heavy documents. This strategy was applied particularly to the "Digital preservation" and "Open policies" courses, where complex information benefited from visual representation. Other courses, such as "Funding" and "Copyright and licenses," employed both comprehensive course materials and supporting infographics to address different learning preferences.
2. **Interactive self-assessment tools:** when dealing with best practice lists, we transformed passive recommendations into active engagement tools by developing checklists and self-assessment frameworks. We enhanced these tools by adding explanatory context—the "why" behind each practice and/or reformatting them as reflective questions that encouraged deeper consideration. This approach proved particularly effective for topics including "Gender diversity," "Multilingualism," "Accessibility," "Open review," "Choosing a platform," and "Communication strategies".
3. **Content enrichment:** In several cases, we expanded beyond the initial "repackaging" mission by researching and integrating supplementary information, examples, and contextual elements not present in the original documents. This enrichment strategy was notably applied to "Copyright and licenses," "Research integrity," and "EDIB checklists," where additional context and expanded explanations enhanced the educational value. While this enriched content has not yet been integrated back into the original Toolsuite articles and guidelines, a future development could involve incorporating these additional insights and expanded explanations into updated versions.

Throughout this process, collaboration between instructional designers and subject matter experts proved valuable, bringing pedagogical perspectives to specialised content whenever expert consultation was available. The adaptation process highlighted the practical balance needed between accurately representing source materials and providing the educational value that justifies such transformation.

3.2 Developing content for diverse audiences

The project faced the challenge of developing training materials for a wide and diverse target audience. This necessitated the creation of resources that could cater to individuals with varying levels of knowledge, skills, roles, and responsibilities, as well as those from different countries and institutional contexts.

DIAMAS content experts played a crucial role in addressing this challenge, as they had good knowledge of the DIAMAS stakeholders and were familiar with the complexities of the subject matter.

Another key element of the adaptation strategy was to gather comprehensive feedback from learners and to use it for continuous improvement – this topic is covered in the Evaluation section in Chapter 1. By analysing learner responses on prior knowledge, relevance to their roles, and specific contextual challenges, the instructional designers could adapt the training materials, and ensure they are appropriately tailored to individuals with varying levels of experience, diverse responsibilities, and different institutional and national backgrounds.

Regarding diverse responsibilities, it should be noted that the courses were designed primarily in relation to learning objectives rather than specific professional profiles or responsibilities. Furthermore, to address the full spectrum of learner diversity, it is anticipated that the Training Platform will host other courses that could address the same topics but are tailored for more specific audiences, such as those focused on a particular country, offered in a language other than English, or designed for a different level of prior knowledge. The platform is designed to accommodate this diversity, and further improvements will have to be done at later stages. For example, the search filters in the Course catalogue will enable users to distinguish between these different course offerings, and additional filters may be considered and implemented as the platform evolves to better address these diverse needs.

3.3 Known limitations and suggested mitigation measures

Some limitations and areas of vigilance related to the current general design and setup of the platform have been identified.

To ensure continuous improvement and further integration of the Training Platform within the CAP federated infrastructure, its interdependence with other systems, tools, and workflows has been assessed, and specific procedural and technical steps have been identified. These mitigation measures will be an integral part of future technical developments.

- **Information structure evolution (future course integration).** The platform's information structure – including course categories, filters, and metadata – has been designed with future expansion in mind. However, one anticipated challenge will be to maintain thematic coherence as new training materials are potentially integrated. It will be important to avoid content duplication or overlap, and to ensure that the overall structure remains navigable and meaningful for users. Any new course additions must continue to meet the platform's current standards for instructional quality and pedagogical soundness. This will be ensured by identifying the appropriate level of support and coordination with the community of contributors, so that future developments remain aligned with the platform's educational goals, informational and technical architecture.
- **Planned integration and federated authentication.** The Training Platform is expected to integrate with external installations to enable Single Sign-On (SSO) and federated authentication. This will involve technical steps such as role mapping, identity provider configuration, and secure user session management.
- **Limited multilingual support at launch.** Only English and French language packs are currently installed; other European languages are planned but not yet deployed.
- **No built-in analytics beyond course-level reporting.** The platform does not currently include advanced analytics for user behaviour or course performance beyond Moodle's native reporting tools. The use of a particular plugin is needed to activate this feature. As part of future developments, useful indicators will be defined, GDPR compliance will be cross-checked, and the plugin will be implemented.
- **Accessibility improvements pending formal audit.** Accessibility features (e.g., keyboard navigation, double navigation system) are in place. External WCAG 2.1 compliance audit will be performed.
- **Content creation centralised.** Course creation and updates are currently managed solely by OpenEdition; Self-authoring and external contribution

[D4.4 Training report]

workflows will be considered following an assessment of the platform's uptake and need for additional content.

- **Mobile optimisation not extensively tested.** The platform is responsive and mobile-compatible through Moodle's BoostUnion theme, but full testing across mobile devices is pending.
- **Security safeguards.** Specific measures to prevent spam registrations and denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks have not yet been implemented. CAPTCHA mechanisms, IP filtering, and advanced traffic monitoring – will be considered to strengthen the platform's resilience against automated abuse or service disruption.
- **Usage uncertainty and impact on platform performance.** The actual number of users and usage patterns remain unknown at this stage. Capacity adjustments may need to be planned and monitored over time to ensure continued performance.
- **Technical assistance response time.** Technical support is offered to users who experience difficulties with platform navigation, course access, or request consultation on the training material. The estimated response time is 2-3 business days, but no formal support service level agreement (SLA) is currently in place. As platform usage grows, support needs will be monitored and reassessed to determine whether escalation procedures are required to maintain service quality

4. Further Developments and Sustainability

4.1 Dissemination and engagement

The task organised two webinars to onboard users to the training platform. The first webinar, addressed to English-speaking users, took place on May 26 and was attended by 75 participants. The second webinar, aimed at French-speaking users, was held on May 28 and was attended by 58 participants. Recordings of both webinars will be uploaded to the training platform to help users understand the scope of the training pathway, become familiar with the courses, and navigate the sections of the platform.

The launch of the training platform was also announced on the project's social media accounts. A continuous communication campaign has been planned to foster engagement with the platform and build a community of users who will actively contribute to future updates and adaptations of its content.

4.2 Sustainability

The overall sustainability plan for the Training Platform is based on its integration into the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), which was launched in January 2025. The EDCH is a long-term initiative that supports the further development of Diamond OA in Europe. It is supported by a collective of institutions and six specialised Task Forces dedicated to maintaining its functionality and enhancing its resources. A roadmap for integrating the outputs of DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects is currently being developed. In this context, the Training Platform has been identified as one of the six core services offered by the EDCH. Its operation will be coordinated by the Skills and Competencies Task Force, and supported with structural funds.

4.3 Future iterations of the training programme

The further development of the training programme will focus on three key areas: (a) continuous improvement based on user feedback; (b) adaptation to changes in scholarly communication, and (c) potential translations to reach a wider audience. To improve the programme, we will develop a clear process to analyse feedback from questionnaires and Moodle usage. This analysis will guide updates to the content, identify areas for improvement, and ensure the programme meets user needs. To make sure the programme remains useful and sustainable, reviews by the members of the EDCH Skills and Competences Task Force will be planned to address important aspects of its continuous development and maintenance. The close collaboration of the EDCH Task Forces will ensure the programme remains current and relevant to other resources (such as the DOAS), as well as timely updates of training materials. Finally, the translation of

[D4.4 Training report]

the training materials into other languages will be prioritised to increase access and foster reuse across the European Research Area.

Conclusion

This report outlined the initial development of a training programme within the DIAMAS project, aiming to support journal editors and IPSP managers in their transition to Open Access publishing. By drawing on the project's evolving outputs, including the DOAS, Toolsuite, and Guidelines, this training programme represents a preliminary step in offering structured learning opportunities.

The collaborative efforts of instructional designers and subject matter experts have resulted in a foundational set of training materials, accessible through the Moodle platform. The programme's design, informed by the ADDIE methodology, seeks to provide a learner-centered experience, with the understanding that further refinement will be necessary to fully address diverse learning needs.

The implementation of this initial training programme is intended to contribute to the broader goals of the DIAMAS project in strengthening institutional Diamond Open Access publishing across the ERA. Future work will explore the translation of these materials to broaden their reach, and we anticipate that ongoing feedback and evaluation will be crucial in shaping the programme's future development and ensuring its continued relevance and effectiveness within the dynamic Open Access landscape.

Looking forward, the platform developed through this process is envisioned as a carefully curated space for a growing collection of high-quality training resources, complementing the foundational DIAMAS training programme. This may include materials in additional languages, resources tailored to specific contexts or aspects of Diamond Open Access publishing, as well as resources for more advanced learning needs. Continuous development of the platform will strive to ensure its ongoing utility and relevance for the wider community.

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Annexes

Annex 1 - Resource titles and types

Title of the course	Format of the resource	Title of the resources
General introduction		
Funding	H5P · Course presentation	Case study scenario
	PDF · Infographic	Visual guide
Ownership and governance	H5P · Course presentation	Case study scenario
Open policies	H5P · Course presentation	Sharing Research Data - Slideshow
	PDF · Infographic	Sharing Research Software · Visual guide
	PDF · Infographic	Sharing Research Protocols - Visual Guide
	PDF · Infographic	Sharing Negative Results - Visual Guide
Copyright and licenses	H5P · Interactive book	Interactive course
	PDF · Infographic	Visual guide
Preprints and repositories	H5P · Interactive book	Interactive course
Open peer review	H5P · Interactive book	Interactive course
	H5P · Documentation tool	Self-reflection guide
Editorial quality and management	H5P · MCQs	Peer Review Process · Activity
	H5P · MCQs	Editorial Transparency · Activity
	PDF · Infographic	Editorial quality · Visual guide
	PDF · Infographic	Editorial management · Visual guide
	PDF · Infographic	GDPR privacy notice · Visual guide
Research integrity	H5P · Interactive book	Interactive course
Choosing a software	H5P · Interactive book	Interactive course
	PDF · Checklist	Self-reflection guide
Metadata	H5P · Interactive book	Interactive course
	PDF · Infographic	Article metadata · Visual guide
Digital preservation	PDF · Infographic	Visual guide
Visibility, discoverability and impact	H5P · Interactive book	Visibility and discoverability · Interactive course
	H5P · Interactive book	Usage and metrics · Interactive course
	PDF · Infographic	Communications Strategies · Visual guide

[D4.4 Training report]

Equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging	H5P · Course presentation	Introduction to EDIB · Interactive course
	H5P · Documentation tool	Gender diversity · Self-reflection guide
	H5P · Documentation tool	Multilingualism · Self-reflection guide
	H5P · Documentation tool	Accessibility and inclusive language · Self-reflection guide

Annex 2 - Course transcripts

0. General introduction

About

The DIAMAS project has developed this training programme to advance Diamond Open Access within the European Research Area's institutional publishing landscape.

Whether you are affiliated with a publisher, a service provider, a journal editorial board, or involved in training activities, this programme is designed specifically for you. Whether you're just beginning to explore Diamond Open Access publishing or looking to improve your publishing operations, it aims to provide you with:

- A better understanding of the DOAS framework and its key components.
- Actionable strategies to effectively implement its standards within your publishing operations
- Guidance on aligning your publishing workflows with open science principles.

Building on previous outputs from the DIAMAS project, this programme focuses primarily on the foundational knowledge and skills needed to engage with the 7 core components of DOAS:

- Funding
- Ownership and Governance
- Open Science Practices
- Editorial Quality, Editorial Management, Research Integrity
- Technical Service Efficiency
- Visibility, Interoperability, Communication, Marketing, Impact
- Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB)

These core components provide a comprehensive framework to enhance the quality, sustainability, and equity of your open access publishing operations.

Navigating the programme

The programme is structured into 13 courses, each exploring a different aspect of Diamond Open Access publishing. Feel free to select the ones that are most relevant to your needs and goals.

Before diving in, we recommend that you:

- Complete the self-assessment tool to identify your specific training needs and areas for improvement.
- Review the DOAS core component related to the course you're interested in, to familiarise yourself with the framework.

While the related tool suite and guidelines are not required reading, they provide valuable supplementary resources should you wish to explore them further.

[D4.4 Training report]

Within each course, be sure to:

- Review the learning goals to ensure the content is adapted to your level and needs.
- Consult the glossary before the resources to familiarise yourself with key terms.
- Complete the 5-minute survey at the end – your feedback is very important to us.
- Mark the course as complete in your progress tracker.

After finishing a course, you can:

- Explore the "DIAMAS Related Resources" section for supplementary materials.
- Pick one of the suggested related courses to continue your learning pathway.

This approach will help you get the most out of this training programme.

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Implementation

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Contact Us

If you have any questions or require assistance, please contact the team in charge of developing the EDCH Training platform : moodle@openedition.org

Updates

Version 1 (May 2025)

1. Funding

Course details

Subtitle: How to develop strategies for sustainable and independent publishing

Duration: Approximately 45 minutes

Keywords: Funding, Sustainability, Budgeting, Independence, Grants

Abstract: Learn how to ensure the financial sustainability of a Diamond OA journal while upholding its core principles of transparency and editorial independence.

Introduction

Diamond Open Access publishing thrives on a sustainable mix of funding sources that are transparent and protect editorial independence. This course provides a foundational understanding of funding mechanisms and offers practical guidance for ensuring the financial sustainability of a Diamond Open Access journal while upholding its core principles.

In this course, you will:

- Explore funding sources that align with Diamond Open Access principles
- Discover common funding challenges and practical solutions

- Explore strategies to maintain editorial independence while ensuring financial sustainability

Glossary

Article Processing Charges (APCs): Fees paid by authors or their institutions to publishers to cover publication costs, allowing articles to be made freely available online without subscription barriers.

Paywall: A digital barrier that restricts access to online content, requiring users to purchase a subscription or make a one-time payment before they can view or download the complete material.

In-kind Support: Non-monetary contributions that significantly aid publication operations and sustainability, including volunteer editorial work, institutional server hosting, technical expertise, software licenses, or administrative services.

Voluntary Author Contributions (VACs): Optional financial donations made by authors to support open access journals, distinct from mandatory APCs, which help financially support publication while maintaining free submission and publication policies.

Training material 1: interactive course

Slide 1

Funding in Diamond Open Access Publishing

Diamond Open Access publishing faces diverse and unique funding challenges. This interactive course equips you with the fundamental strategies to overcome these obstacles and ensure the long-term sustainability of your journal.

Slide 2

Let's explore Diamond OA funding through a simulated conversation.

You'll step into the role of a publisher who wants to launch a journal in Open Access, chatting with someone who can provide guidance on how to achieve financial sustainability in Diamond OA.

Navigate by using the bar below. Each circle stands for an activity.

Duration : 11 slides | about 30 minutes

[[Click here to join the chat conversation](#)]

Slide 3

Learner: I need to understand the different funding models better.

Interlocutor: Of course, let's start with the basics. There are three main models: the subscription model, the Gold OA model, and the Diamond OA model. Can you tell the difference ?

Learner

1. Tell me about the Subscription Model.

This model places content behind a paywall, restricting access to subscribers. Readers or their institutions pay subscription fees to journals or platforms, providing the primary revenue stream

for publishers. This means that many researchers, students, and members of the public cannot access the content.

2. Explain the Gold OA Model.

This model ensures immediate accessibility upon publication. Readers access the content freely, while authors (or their institutions) cover the costs through Article Processing Charges (APCs). These APCs become the publisher's primary revenue source. While improving accessibility, Gold OA can create financial barriers for authors, creating inequalities and limiting diversity in research. Some publishers use a "moving wall" which is a set period – commonly 6 months to 5 years – after which content from a subscription-based journal becomes freely accessible (i.e. open access). The "wall" moves forward in time with each new volume or issue published.

3. How does the Diamond OA Model work?

The Diamond OA Model offers open access without any fees for authors or readers. It relies on alternative funding sources, ensuring accessibility for both authors and readers.

4. It's all good for me!

Slide 4

Learner: So, if Diamond OA doesn't rely on APCs or subscriptions like the other models, how is it supported financially ?

Interlocutor: Well, have a guess : [User is asked to match the items with the suggested categories]

Categories	Items
*Appropriate for Diamond OA publishing	*Voluntary author contributions (VAC) *Library memberships *Public grants *In-kind support *Print sales *Donations
Not appropriate or Diamond OA publishing	Article Processing Charges (APCs) Subscription fees Pay-per-view

Slide 5

Interlocutor: Nice try : you've identified some key funding sources. Diamond Open Access publications are often funded through a mix of various revenue streams for sustaining their operations, and direct monetary funding is used in combination with in-kind support.

To further explore these options, I suggest consulting the DIAMAS guide, '[Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access.](#)' This document is designed to help journal publishers navigate the different options available and in understanding the pros

[D4.4 Training report]

and cons of each, and assist them in deciding which is most suitable for their field, business model, and size.

Now if you want to know more about in-kind support in Diamond Open Access, this document is for you : '[The centrality of the workforce for Diamond OA: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work](#)'.

Slide 6

Learner: It seems that there are a lot of opportunities to rely on, but piecing them together must be difficult.

Interlocutor: You're right. Let me share a story that illustrates some of these difficulties.

A Diamond OA journal, launched by a university, initially thrived with a grant from the Ministry of Education. But when the grant ended due to shifting priorities and budget cuts, the journal faced a funding crisis. They eventually found a new funding source, but this created a new problem: the sponsor attempted to influence the journal's editorial direction to align with their own business interests.

What problems do you think this journal has encountered ?

Well, from what I understood, it faced multiple challenges :

(true) Long-term sustainability.

Correct. The journal's funding crisis highlights the challenge of maintaining financial stability over time.

(true) Dependency on diverse funding contexts.

Correct. The shift in funding sources demonstrates the need for a variety of support to avoid reliance on a single source.

(true) Editorial independence from financial supporters.

Correct. The influence of the new sponsor on editorial direction shows the risk to independence when funding comes with strings attached.

(false) Inappropriate funding mechanism.

You missed: While the journal faced challenges, the funding sources themselves were not inherently inappropriate; rather, the dependence on them created issues.

Slide 7

Interlocutor: That's right, you've identified three core challenges for Diamond OA. Let's explore each one in more detail.

- Long-Term Sustainability

Finding reliable, long-term funding is crucial. Many Diamond OA journals start with short-term grants, which are essential to develop new services, but don't provide for maintaining operations and ongoing development in the longer term. Sustainability is important to ensure editorial consistency, to make improvements to meet evolving quality standards in publishing, and to ensure that published content remains accessible. .

Adapting to diverse funding contexts: There's no one-size-fits-all solution for Diamond OA funding. Diamond OA journals must develop funding models tailored to their specific circumstances. Factors to consider include:

- *Location*

Finding reliable, long-term funding is essential for Diamond Open Access publishers.

Many Diamond OA journals start with short-term grants, which are essential to develop new services, but don't provide for maintaining operations and ongoing development in the longer term.

Sustainability is important to ensure editorial consistency, to make improvements to meet evolving quality standards in publishing, and to ensure that published content remains accessible.

- *Adapting to diverse funding contexts*

There's no one-size-fits-all solution for Diamond OA funding. Journals must develop models tailored to their circumstances. Key factors include:

- **Location:** Funding opportunities vary across different geographical levels. Journals must navigate these landscapes to identify suitable options.
 - **Disciplinary norms:** Journals need to align with their discipline's characteristics: Disciplines with active scholarly societies can leverage membership fees. / VACs can be a good redistributive mechanism – one VAC often covers more than one article – but heavily depend on the discipline's ability to capture grant funding, as well as the location and policies of the institutions authors are affiliated with.
 - **Ethical considerations:** Not all funding mechanisms are suitable for every journal. Journals should carefully evaluate funding mechanisms to avoid ethical conflicts, ensure alignment with disciplinary values, and protect editorial independence from potential external influences.
- *Balancing sustainability and editorial independence from financial supporters*

Diamond Open Access journals rely heavily on external funding sources, and there's a risk that these financial supporters may attempt to exert influence over editorial decisions or content.

Slide 8

Learner: I understand how complex it can be. So, how do Diamond Open Access publishers typically handle these challenges? Are there any common approaches?

Interlocutor: Well, every journal's situation is unique, and yet successful Diamond OA publishers do tend to follow similar best practices. [This infographic](#) provides a visual overview of the common strategies, which might be helpful to see all in one place.

Slide 9

Interlocutor: Now, the real challenge lies in applying these principles. Let me share a few situations I've encountered. I'd love to hear your perspective on how you'd approach these challenges.

[D4.4 Training report]

1. A journal hosted by its institution currently covers its operating costs via APCs. What options could it explore to move to a diamond model?

(false) *Implementing subscription fees to replace APCs. Feedback : Subscription fees contradict the free access principle of Diamond OA*

(true) *Seeking long-term support from national or international organisations. Feedback : External funding provides a sustainable Diamond OA model.*

(true) *Petitioning additional funding from the institution. Feedback : Institutional support can replace APCs, enabling Diamond OA.*

2. A commercial entity offers to sponsor a Diamond OA journal in exchange for placing their logo on the journal's website and a brief acknowledgment in the journal's footer. Should the journal accept?

(true) *Yes, if the values of the commercial entity align with the values of the journal. The journal should establish a clear written agreement outlining the terms of the sponsorship, ensure it doesn't influence editorial decisions, and maintain full transparency about the sponsorship on the journal's website. Feedback : Sponsorship can provide a valuable source of income for a journal. Before proceeding:*

Consider ethical implications: Investigate the commercial entity's background and values, and ensure that these align with those of the journal and discipline. Ensure editorial independence and avoid conflict of interest. Protect editorial independence explicitly as part of a contract to ensure that there is no link between financial support and editorial decision-making and content. Be transparent. Include details of the sponsorship arrangement on the journal website.

(false) *No. Any form of commercial sponsorship creates a potential conflict of interest and compromises the journal's commitment to unbiased, independent publishing.*

3. A university library wants to support Diamond OA journals. What are effective ways to do this.

(true) *Provide direct financial support for journals, or invest in new models that support diamond open access publishing.*

Feedback: Libraries can reallocate funding from other budgets to support diamond open access journals and infrastructures. They can also invest in models that support diamond open access publishing, such as collective action models, subscribe to open, or freemium models.

(true) *Promote Diamond Open Access journals within the university and to the wider scholarly community.*

Feedback : Libraries can promote Diamond journals as a trusted source of research content to researchers and students through training and services. When advising researchers on suitable publication venues, they can also recommend diamond open access journals as an alternative to subscription or APC-based journals.

4. A Diamond Open Access journal, initially funded by a public grant, expects its funding to decrease. Which of the following strategies best aligns with Diamond OA principles while addressing the journal's financial challenges?

(false) Implement a model without publication charges but with optional paid-for features for authors such as enhanced visibility, expedited peer review, or consultancy services for manuscript improvement.

You missed: Optional paid services, if any, should be completely separate from the publication process itself and should never give paying authors an advantage, for example, post-acceptance language editing or typesetting services.

(false) introduce an article processing charge for authors.

You missed: Implementing any mandatory fees is incompatible with Diamond Open Access, and creates barriers for authors to publish. They should explore alternative funding streams.
(true) Introduce voluntary contributions from authors or institutions.

Voluntary Author Contributions (VACs) are an option, as long as it is clearly indicated on the website at the journal level that delivered publication services are not contingent on the payment of any fees by the authors.

For an example see the journal Glossa Psycholinguistics' policy on VACs: <https://escholarship.org/uc/glossapsycholinguistics/Contributions>

(true) Generate revenue by offering a subscription for premium services or additional content to libraries.

Correct. Freemium services, such as that offered by OpenEdition, ensure open access to the HTML article, while generating income from alternative value-added services, such as access to the PDF and ePub. Another option is the Subscribe to Open Model, which repurposes existing subscriptions to make content open access.

5. A university department wants to launch a new journal. What steps could it take to ensure that it meets best practices and is financially sustainable ?

(true) Develop a sustainability plan setting out expected costs and available funding sources.

Correct. A sustainability plan ensures the new journal can identify and leverage available funding streams, aligning them with expected costs to support long-term operations.

(true) Use a budgeting system to ensure that annual costs are balanced with expected incomes and in-kind contributions

Correct. A budgeting system will help the new journal to track expenses and incomes, ensuring financial stability and enabling proactive cost management for the journal.

(true) Investigate university or disciplinary shared platform that could be used to reduce costs and ensure efficiency

Correct. Using shared platforms can significantly reduce technical costs for the new journal.

Interlocutor: You did well. These scenarios highlight the diverse challenges of funding Diamond Open Access journals. It requires an adaptable funding approach, balancing practical needs with adherence to Open Access principles of transparency, independence, and open access.

[D4.4 Training report]

Learner: I understand. Now I'm curious about the benefits for funders. What do institutions, funders, and Open Access advocates gain from supporting and sustaining Diamond OA publishing? What's in it for them, essentially? How can arguments be leveraged?

Interlocutor: You might find what you're looking for in that document: '[Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access](#)'.

Slide 11

Interlocutor: I need to go now. I hope this was useful to you. If you need further assistance, the following resources may be of use:

For information on sustaining institutional publishing: [Sustainability Resources](#) - This resource suite offers tools, case studies, and templates for publishers, service providers, and funders.

For details on kick-off funding for open access journals: Kick-off funding - OA Journals Toolkit - This article provides additional information on securing initial funding, including longer-term support options and examples.

You can also refer to the infographic I shared previously.

Learner: Thank you for your guidance, this gives me a lot to think about. See you later!

Training material 2 - Infographic

Funding strategies in Diamond Open Access publishing

Balancing free access with financial stability is a key challenge for Diamond OA publishers. Here are 8 strategies you can use to secure sustainable funding while ensuring open access, transparency, and independent editorial control.

Diverse funding sources

Relying on a single funding source is risky. Actively seek funding from a mix of local, regional, national, and international sources, to provide a robust financial foundation.

Long-term funding

Prioritise long-term funding from academic institutions, ministries, research funding agencies, and avoid contributions that are tied to individual outputs or groups of authors. This provides financial stability and allows for strategic planning and development.

Shared value

Ensure funding sources align with the values and traditions of the disciplines served. Avoid conflicts of interest and maintain editorial independence.

Clear policies

Publish clear policies for accepting external funding, to ensure transparency and maintain editorial independence.

Sustainability plan

Create a comprehensive sustainability plan outlining the journal's medium-term economic viability.

This plan should include:

- Projected costs and revenue streams.
- Strategies for resource allocation and cost reduction.
- Plans for leveraging shared infrastructure and collaborative partnerships.

Year-on-year cost identification

Plan your annual costs and balance them with expected incomes and in-kind contributions using a tracking system, such as a budget.

Resource sharing and collaboration

Partnering with other institutions, libraries, or service providers can unlock access to resources, expertise, and cost-saving shared services.

National or regional publication portals often provide low- or no-cost publishing infrastructure, reducing the need for additional technical funding.

Strong relationships with host institutions are also crucial for funding (monetary and or in-kind) and support.

Transparency

Transparency is important to build trust and demonstrate integrity. Publish a clear statement about funding sources on the journal website, and include acknowledgement of donations, project funding, and in-kind and voluntary contributions. Indicate any conflicts of interest.

2. Ownership and governance

Details

Subtitle: Building trust through transparent structures and community control

Duration: Approximately 45 minutes

Keywords: Ownership, governance, community, transparency, independence.

Abstract: Explore the essential aspects to consider when establishing governance and ownership structures in Diamond OA publishing.

Introduction

The quality and sustainability of a Diamond Open Access journal rely heavily on its ownership and governance structure. This course will guide you through the essential aspects to consider when establishing or refining these structures.

Through a fictional chat conversation, you'll follow a publisher's successful transition journey, gaining valuable insights to inform your own journal's path.

In this course, you will learn:

[D4.4 Training report]

- How Diamond Open Access core principles guide publisher's governance and ownership practices
- How to apply these principles across all operational levels, from institutional relationships to editorial workflows
- Key steps involved during the transition process

Glossary

Beneficial Ownership: A system where the editorial team and board of a journal are granted significant control and influence over its operations, even though legal ownership remains with the IP. This model prevents the sale of journals to commercial publishers and ensures community control.

Community ownership of journal titles: It means that an IP can easily change its service provider without changing the journal title, since ownership of the journal title always remains vested in the IP and its community.

Governance: Refers to the set of processes, policies, and structures that regulate the functioning and decision-making uniformly across all publications in a journal. It is good practice to fully articulate the relationship between publishing services and the publications resulting from them.

Internal governance: The way in which decisions are reached within the IP, its governance model and organisation chart.

Non-transferable ownership: A model where ownership of a journal title remains with the IP and its community, ensuring it cannot be transferred to commercial entities. This concept empowers the journal's community and facilitates changes in service providers without altering ownership.

Ownership statement: A formal declaration that details the ownership of journals published by the IP. It includes legal parameters governing the journal-IP relationship, rights and duties of editors, and provisions for journal discontinuation and asset transfer.

Strategic governance: Indicates how a particular IP relates to its scholarly community stakeholders and its host institution.

Training material 1: Interactive course**Slide 1**

Ownership and Governance in Diamond Open Access Publishing.

The quality and sustainability of a Diamond Open Access journal rely heavily on its ownership and governance structure. This course will guide you through the essential aspects to consider when establishing or refining these structures.

Slide 2

Let's explore Diamond OA funding through a simulated conversation.

You'll step into the role of a publisher who wants to launch a journal in Open Access, chatting with someone who can provide guidance on how to achieve financial sustainability in Diamond Open Access.

[Navigate by using the bar below. Each circle stands for an activity]

Duration: 17 slides | about 30 minutes

[[Click \(here\)](#) to join the chat conversation]

Slide 3

Interlocutor: Hello, it's great to hear from you! I'm happy to share our experience. What would you like to know ?

Learner: Thanks a lot for your time! Well first, I'd like you to tell me what motivated you to switch to the Diamond Open Access model.

Interlocutor: We wanted to ensure the journal remained fully controlled by the academic community, free from commercial pressures. Under our previous governance structure, decisions were often driven by commercial interests rather than what was best for our authors and readers.

Switching to Diamond Open Access allowed us to restructure ownership, making it transparent and community-based, while ensuring that all decisions reflect scholarly priorities. It also gave us the flexibility to change service providers in future without losing control of the journal.

Slide 4

Learner: That makes sense. How exactly did you restructure your ownership to achieve this?

Interlocutor: Well, our journal is now owned by the academic institution we're affiliated with. Everything is clearly stated on the website, as transparency in this matter is a core principle of DOA. Take a look:

The European Journal of Applied Linguistics (EJAL) is owned by the University of Aethelburg Library, having transitioned from Mindspark Publishing in 2022 in order to reflect our commitment to Diamond Open Access.

The Library provides hosting and infrastructure, but the journal's editorial independence is guaranteed by a Memorandum of Understanding. Any changes to this ownership structure require joint approval from both the Editorial Board and the Library Director. The EJAL is committed to remaining Diamond Open Access and will not transition to closed-access or hybrid publishing.

Learner: Is being owned by a university a requirement for Diamond Open Access?

Interlocutor: Well, have a guess:

"Any not-for-profit academic or scholarly organisation can own a Diamond OA journal. The key is to ensure it remains driven by scholarly communities and maintains open access integrity."

"Not necessarily, a Diamond journal can be owned by any organisation, including commercial entities, as long as it follows open access principles."

Slide 5

Interlocutor: This is actually important: you should avoid giving commercial publishers ownership of your journal title. A good way to do this is by granting beneficial ownership to your editorial team and board. This creates what's known as "**non-transferable ownership**", meaning the journal is owned by its community. It makes it hard to sell and ensures decisions are made for scholarly, not commercial reasons. This way, you maintain control and uphold the journal's academic integrity.

Learner: I understand. And what types of non-profit academic or scholarly organisations are eligible to own a DOA journal?

Interlocutor: These include but are not limited to research performing organisations (RPOs), research funding organisations (RFOs), organisations connected to RPOs (university libraries, university presses, faculties, and departments), research institutes, and scholarly societies.

Slide 6

Learner: Ok, so that's why you switched from a commercial publisher to a university library. Did you encounter problems during the transition process, or did you get everything the way you wanted?

Interlocutor: It was a significant undertaking involving several key steps: transferring intellectual property rights from Mindspark (such as the journal name, logo, website, and archives), as well as migrating all previously published articles to our new platform. We also developed a robust technical infrastructure to support the journal and addressed concerns from authors and stakeholders to ensure a smooth transition. The non-transferable ownership structure proved invaluable, allowing us to change service providers seamlessly.

Slide 7

Learner: Did you keep your community informed?

Interlocutor: "Of course. We published regular updates to ensure stakeholders were informed at every stage, and to address common concerns. ... [screenshot to the announcement].

The Editorial Board of the European Journal of Applied Linguistics is pleased to announce the commencement of a transition to the Diamond Open Access (DOA) publishing model. This strategic decision reflects our commitment to advancing open scholarship and ensuring the widest possible dissemination of high-quality research.

We are committed to maintaining transparency throughout this process. Regular updates regarding the progress of the transition will be provided on this webpage. We encourage all stakeholders to check back frequently for the latest information.

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

- *What is Diamond Open Access?*
- *What does this change mean for me as an author or reader?*
- *Will the peer-review process be affected?*
- *What will happen to articles published before the transition?*
- *How will the journal be funded?"*

“We are pleased to announce that the European Journal of Applied Linguistics has successfully transitioned to the Diamond Open Access model. This means all articles are now immediately and permanently free to read, download, and share, with no author fees or subscription costs. This step reflects our commitment to open scholarship and ensuring equitable access to research for everyone.

Our editorial team remains dedicated to maintaining rigorous peer-review standards and upholding principles of fairness, transparency, and scholarly rigor in evaluating submissions.

We are grateful to the University of Aethelburg for their invaluable support in making this transition possible.

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

- *What is Diamond Open Access?*
- *What does this change mean for me as an author or reader?*
- *Will the peer-review process be affected?*
- *What happens to articles published before the transition?*
- *How is the journal funded now?”*

Slide 8

Learner: That’s inspiring, you handled it with utmost care and transparency.

Interlocutor: Yes, we communicated the changes clearly to all stakeholders, updated our legal documents, and ensured that all the rights and duties were properly transferred.

Slide 9

Learner: So, in short, if I want to switch to DOAM, the core components in terms of ownership are transparency and scholarly community. I’ll have to be very clear and open about the processes and decisions, and to maintain ownership within the community.

Interlocutor: Precisely. And Diamond Open Access is about more than ownership:

- One of the key characteristics of the DOAM is to prioritise community governance and scholarly integrity over commercial profit, ensuring that the primary focus remains on the quality and accessibility of research.
- As for transparency, it’s a cornerstone of this model: not only does it enhance the credibility and reliability of the scholarly content but it also fosters trust among authors, reviewers, and readers.

Slide 10

Learner: About governance now. I’d like to know more about the set of processes, policies, and structures that regulate the functioning and decision-making across all publications of your journals. How did it change for you? What differs between the DOAM and traditional publishing models?

Interlocutor: When we transitioned to DOA, we restructured our governance to align with its principles. This commitment shapes how each journal governs and manages its publications, relationships, and processes. The key difference is that DOA governance is community-led. This

[D4.4 Training report]

means the scholarly community – authors, editors, reviewers, readers, and institutions – actively participates in shaping the journal's policies and operations. Let me highlight the core principles of DOA governance that guide us:

Transparency: All policies (from governance to editorial), procedures, financial records, and editorial workflows are publicly accessible, in clear, jargon-free language. Anyone can easily find details on our website about how decisions are made, what criteria are used for publication, and who is responsible for what.

Inclusivity: Governance is designed to include diverse voices from the global scholarly community, ensuring representation across disciplines, regions, and institutions.

Accountability: Decision-making processes are clearly defined, traceable and tied to community feedback.

Collaboration: We emphasise partnerships between stakeholders – authors, editors, reviewers, funders, and institutions – so that everyone has a role in shaping the journal's future. Community members can raise concerns and seek resolution through established avenues. We also evaluate our governance and make improvements based on community input, ensuring responsiveness and decisions aligned with scholarly communication's best interests.

Slide 11

Learner: That must have been a big shift! Your journal moved from a top-down model to one where major decisions involve community consultation. How did you proceed, how did you integrate these principles into your work?

Interlocutor: Well, first, governance involves managing relationships at multiple levels:

Our governance structure: This refers to how we organise ourselves internally and how decisions are made within the organisation. It includes our governance model, organisation chart, and the way we reach decisions. It's also about how we interact with external stakeholders, such as our scholarly community and host institution.

Our relations with SPs: Service Providers, whether commercial or non-commercial, handle various aspects of the publishing process, such as ownership of infrastructure, copy-editing and typesetting services used, etc. Our relationship with them ensures that these workflows run smoothly and efficiently.

Our relationship with the journals we publish: This area focused on how we work with the journals we support, including the processes and structures that guide their operations and ensure alignment with our overall goals.

Slide 12

Interlocutor: Now, moving from a top-down model required a fundamental shift in our organisational culture, prioritising transparency and accountability.

For instance, the relationship between our host institution and each journal, including agreements and responsibilities, is clearly documented on our website.

Regarding external partnerships, we're open about our collaborations with both commercial and non-commercial service providers. Our website lists our partners, the services they provide, and the policies governing these relationships. Each journal also has its own protocols for working

with service providers, ensuring clear communication and accountability at every level. Where we collaborate with other infrastructures, for example, co-edition, then we make sure that the agreement is formalised with a contract.

Slide 13

Learner: What about internal and editorial governance? How has that changed?

Interlocutor: In practice, this means our editorial processes operate as follows:

Defined Roles and Responsibilities: Every journal has a clear document outlining the roles and responsibilities of its editorial board. This covers their duties towards authors, reviewers, readers, the broader scientific community, the journal and platform owners, us (the publishing initiative), and the public.

Transparent Selection Processes: Each journal has established transparent procedures for selecting their governance bodies (such as advisory or editorial boards), based on their functions and responsibilities. These selection processes, including a detailed procedure for the duration of the positions, the required profiles, and the established time, when and how it is renewed, are publicly available.

Publication Planning: Clear guidelines exist for publication planning, outlining how decisions are made regarding content and scheduling, and specifying the roles of different stakeholders in this process.

Decision-Making Processes: We've formalised our decision-making processes. This includes clearly defining who makes editorial decisions, how consensus is reached (including the role of community consultation), and the frequency of editorial meetings when there are some. We also made a clear distinction between decisions made at the journal level and those made at the publishing initiative level. This clarifies responsibilities and ensures accountability.

Slide 14

Learner: Regarding community consultation, this must have been a significant change, giving the community a much stronger voice. When do you consult with it?

Interlocutor: We consult with them whenever we make significant editorial or policy changes, for example, if we want to transition to open or post-publication peer review. We also gather input and feedback on our processes on an ongoing basis, for example through author surveys.

Slide 15

Learner: Do you regularly review and update your governance systems to ensure they stay relevant and effective?

Interlocutor: You're right, that's an important point.

Each of our journals follows a set timetable specifying how often editorial policies are reviewed and how new elements and changes are introduced into the editorial guidelines and practices. This ensures continuous adaptation to best practices while keeping our governance framework stable yet flexible to meet the community's evolving needs.

Slide 16

Learner: I've heard about initiatives like DORA and CoARA that are working towards reforming research assessment so that it reflects more diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. How about journals? I know that my institution has signed up, but how can diamond journals contribute to this movement?

Interlocutor: Journals play an important role in contributing to fair, transparent and responsible research assessment. For example, none of our journals display journal-level metrics on their webpages, as they are not indicators of article quality. Journals can also accept and encourage a more diverse range of research outputs, for example negative results or datasets.

Slide 17

Learner: That's inspiring. Now, if I want to start moving my journal towards Diamond Open Access, what are the most important first steps I should take regarding governance?

Interlocutor: Based on our experience, I highly recommend creating a formal document outlining your journal's mission, governance structure, and operating procedures as you transition to Diamond Open Access. This document should clearly define roles, responsibilities, decision-making processes, and how the journal will be owned and managed.

You can look at examples like [Glossa's constitution](#) for inspiration.

And of course, consider displaying this document on your web page.

Slide 18

Learner: Thank you so much, this was very helpful.

Interlocutor: I'm glad to hear that. I also recommend networking with other IPSPs. They can offer valuable insights and support. Good luck with your journal!

Learner: Will do. Thank you again!

3. Open policies

Details

Subtitle: Opening the research process beyond publications

Duration: Approximately 30 minutes.

Keywords: Policies, transparency, data, protocols, software, integrity

Abstract: Learn how to implement effective sharing policies for data, protocols, software, and negative results in Diamond OA publishing to enhance research quality, transparency, and impact.

Introduction

Opening up the entire research process by sharing research outputs beyond the article itself (eg. data, protocols, software, negative results...) can significantly enhance the quality, transparency, and impact of scholarly publishing.

Discover how Diamond Open Access publishers can implement effective sharing policies, with practical guidance on key considerations to implement them effectively.

In this course, you will learn:

- Why sharing this information is so important to advance research.
- How to encourage researchers to adopt open sharing practices.
- Key considerations when writing a data sharing policy.

Glossary

Negative results: The result of an experiment can be considered as “negative” or “null” when it does not support with sufficient statistical evidence the previously stated hypothesis. It does not necessarily mean failure as an unexpected outcome worthy of exploration might stem from it. Reference/derivation: [DATAACC](#)

Open research software: Software developed for research purposes whose source code is freely available and licensed for anyone to use, modify, and share.

Open Science: Open science (OS) is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. Reference/derivation: [Unesco Recommendation on Open Science](#)

Persistent identifiers: A persistent identifier (PID) is a long-lasting reference to a digital object, person, organisation, or other entity. It is unique to an entity and remains stable over time, i.e. it resolves even if the location of the entity changes.

PIDs widely used in scholarly publishing:

- DOI (Digital Object Identifier)
- Handle
- Archival Resource Key (ARK)
- URN (Uniform Resource Name)
- ISBN (International Standard Book Number)
- ISSN (International Standard Serial Number)
- ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)
ROR (Research Organization Registry)
- ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)

Reference/derivation: PID Services Registry: <https://pidservices.org/>

Research protocols: A Research Protocol is a detailed document prepared before conducting a study, often written as part of ethics and funding applications, that includes information relating

[D4.4 Training report]

to the background, rationale and aims of the study, as well as the hypotheses which reflect the researchers' expectations, and a "recipe" for conducting the study, including methodological details and clear analysis plans ([FORRT – Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training Glossary](#)). Research protocols are publicly shared to attract new collaborators or facilitate efficient collaboration across labs (e.g. <https://www.protocols.io/>). In medical and educational fields, protocols are often a separate article type suitable for publication in journals.

Training material 1: Sharing research data - Slideshow

Why sharing research data matters

Research data is an essential part of scientific discovery, both as a standalone scientific resource and as a foundation to the research they support. The publishing system can greatly benefit from open data, in different ways:

- Advance research: Datasets are essential resources that drive future discoveries and inspire new research directions.
- Uphold integrity: Connecting publications with their data enables the validation of results, transparency of the research process, and the reproducibility of research findings.
- Foster collaboration: Sharing research data prevents duplication of effort and promotes research continuity and collaboration within the research community.
- Prevent data loss: Depositing research data in repositories helps safeguard valuable datasets for future use.
- Increase reuse and impact: Other researchers, industry, journalists, and the public can reuse shared data, amplifying the research's impact beyond the original publication.
- Meet funder requirements: Many research funders require data sharing using an 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary' approach.

How to support data sharing

Encouraging data sharing goes beyond making research freely accessible: it is a cornerstone to opening up the entire research process. As an OA publisher, you can support data sharing by implementing these Diamond OA Standards:

- A data sharing policy
 - Implement an output-level policy for research data in your journals.
 - The policy can be different for each journal.
 - Display it on your website or the journal's website.
- Early data sharing
 - Encourage authors to submit data during the manuscript review process.
- FAIR datasets
 - When published, encourage:
 - FAIR access via repositories

- PIDs linking publication & data
- Public metadata

What to consider

Responsible data sharing involves adhering to ethical guidelines and protecting the privacy of research participants. When developing your data sharing policy, consider the following key points:

- Ethical standards
 - Research involving human data must have been performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.
 - Where applicable, the studies must have been approved by an appropriate Ethics Committee.
- Sensitive data
 - Ensure compliance with GDPR* and other data protection policies.
 - Without participants' explicit informed written consent for public availability, do not share personal and sensitive data that cannot be effectively de-identified. * See this infographic on how to write a GDPR privacy notice

Making data as open and accessible as possible maximises its potential for reuse and enhances research transparency. When developing your data sharing policy, consider the following key points:

- Data accessibility
 - Require authors to include a Data Accessibility Statement in their submission before the reference list, with the data's DOI.
 - If data is restricted, authors must explain why. Make the statement public upon publication.
- Open licenses
 - Open research data should be deposited under an open license that permits unrestricted access (e.g., CCO, CC-BY).
 - More restrictive licenses should only be used if there is a valid reason to do so (e.g., legal).

Promoting responsible and effective data sharing practices requires clear guidance for authors. Encourage them to follow these key steps to ensure data is properly cited, accessible, and reusable:

- When citing or making claims based on data, author should provide the reference to data in the same way as they cite publications.
- We recommend the format proposed by the FORCE11 Data Citation Principles.
- Make sure that data is deposited in a FAIR- compliant trustworthy repository
- Describe the deposited data in such a way that users can make sense of it (e.g., sensible column headers, descriptions in a readme text file).
- Make sure that data is available in an open, non-proprietary format.

Data policy template

Here's a data sharing policy template that includes the previous considerations. Feel free to adapt it to align with your choices.

[A journal] encourages/requests [select your preferred option] authors to share research data that are required for confirming the results published in the manuscript and/or enhance the published manuscript under the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. We encourage authors to share supporting software applications, high-resolution images, background datasets, sound or video clips, large appendices, data tables and other relevant items that cannot be included in the article.

Authors may deposit relevant data in a FAIR-compliant repository – institutional, disciplinary, or general-purpose (e.g. Zenodo). If you need assistance in finding a FAIR compliant repository, check these links: <https://repositoryfinder.datacite.org/> and <https://www.re3data.org/>. Authors should also provide via the repository any information needed to replicate, validate, and/or reuse the results / their study and analysis of the research data. This includes details of any software, instruments and other tools used to process the results. Where possible, the tools and instruments themselves should also be provided. A DOI will be assigned to each research data file, enabling the research data to be cited the same way as publications.

Authors affirm that data protection regulations, ethical standards, third party copyright and other rights have been respected in the process of collecting, processing and sharing data.

Exceptions: We recognize that open sharing of data may not always be feasible. Exceptions to open access to research data underlying publications include the following: obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, the obligation to protect personal data and other legitimate constraints.

Where open access is not provided to the data needed to validate the conclusions of a publication that reports original results, authors should make metadata available explaining the research and access rules to the data.

If data access is restricted for ethical or security reasons, the manuscript must include:

- *a description of the restrictions on the data;*
- *what, if anything, the relevant Institutional Review Board (IRB) or equivalent said about the data sharing;*
- *all necessary information required for a reader or reviewer to apply for access to the data and the conditions under which access will be granted.*

In instances where the data cannot be made available, the manuscript must include:

- *an explanation of the data protection concern;*
- *any intermediary data that can be de-identified without compromising anonymity;*

- *what, if anything, the relevant IRB or equivalent said about data sharing; and*
- *where applicable, all necessary information required for a reader or peer reviewer to apply for access to the data and the conditions under which access will be granted.*

Training material 2: Sharing research software - Visual guide

Open research software in Diamond Open Access Publishing

Open research software is software developed for research purposes whose source code is freely available and licensed for anyone to use, modify, and share.

5 reasons to encourage sharing research software

- **Reproducibility:** It enables to replicate published findings by running the same computational tool on data generated by the study.
- **FAIR Principles:** It ensures research tools are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
- **Lower retraction risk:** Making research software openly available enables transparency, reproducibility, and independent verification of results, reducing the likelihood of errors, misconduct, or unverifiable findings.
- **Collaboration:** It facilitates community-driven development and fosters new scientific advancements.
- **Credit and recognition:** Formal citation of software ensures proper attribution, encouraging further development of research tools.

Despite its crucial role in research, there is little support across the scholarly ecosystem for software acknowledgement and citation. It is generally not formally cited in scholarly publications and is at best either mentioned in the methods section of an article, or identified through the dependencies of research code deposited by the authors.

What you can do as a publisher

- Define a policy on the availability of research software.
- Ask authors for a statement of software availability.
- Consider software a legitimate and citable research output.
- Require software citations like for publications and data: ask authors to include them in the reference list of a journal article.
- Where applicable, ask authors to make available their scientific code, scripts or models openly in a code repository.

Training material 3: Sharing research protocols - Visual guide

Open protocols in Diamond Open Access publishing

- A Research Protocol is a detailed document prepared before conducting a study.
- It is often written as part of ethics and funding applications.
- In medical and educational fields, it may be published as a separate article type.

[D4.4 Training report]

- Background, rationale, aims of the study, hypothesis, methodology, analysis plan

Why should Diamond Open Access Journals encourage sharing research protocols?

- Transparency. It creates a foundation of openness that enhances credibility of findings and allows for proper verification.
- Reproducibility. It makes it easier to replicate and build upon published research, improving scientific advancement.
- Collaboration. It attracts new collaborators or facilitates collaboration across labs.
- Priority of discovery. It establishes priority of research, reducing the risk of being "scooped".

What can you do as a publisher?

- Define policies for the availability of research protocols.
- Encourage sharing protocols in public repositories that use PIDs (Persistent Identifiers).
- Display this information on the journal website.

Reporting standard template (Example)

[Journal's title] is committed to serving the research community by ensuring that all articles include enough information to allow others to reproduce the work. A submitted manuscript should contain sufficient detail and references to permit reviewers and, subsequently, readers to verify the claims presented in it – e.g. provide complete details of the methods used, including time frames, etc. Authors are required to review the standards available for many research applications from Equator Network and use those that are relevant for the reported research applications. The deliberate presentation of false claims is a violation of ethical standards.

Training material 4: Sharing negative research results - Visual guide

Handling Negative Results in Diamond Open Access Publishing

- A negative or null result occurs when an experiment fails to provide sufficient statistical evidence to support the initial hypothesis.
- Often dismissed as failures or less noteworthy, they are frequently left unpublished, creating a bias toward positive findings that undermines the completeness, verifiability and reliability of research.

Why should you publish negative results?

- **Complete the picture.** It ensures science reflects both successes and failures for a more accurate understanding.
- **Build upon existing knowledge.** It prevents others from repeating experiments and starting from scratch, saving time and effort.
- **Learn from it.** Insights from what didn't work can reveal patterns, challenge theories and inspire new ideas.
- **Support Open Science.** Sharing all results fosters transparency and collaboration in research.

What can you do as a publisher?

- Establish and share policies encouraging and valuing negative results, replication studies, and unexpected findings. E.g. The University of Liège's open science policy.
- Encourage early sharing and registering of the study designs and reporting on the negative results.
- Correct bias towards positive results by paying particular attention to replication studies that fail to reproduce findings.
- Raise awareness among editorial teams about biases toward positive results.
- Include all fields. Non-data-driven disciplines, from philosophy to comparative literature and history, can also yield valuable negative findings such as the absence of expected archival material.

To go further...

- DATACC - Why Are Negative Results Still Six Feet Under? This is a report highlighting the significance of reporting negative results and emerging initiatives. More information can be found at: <https://www.dataacc.org/en/best-practices/reporting-negative-results/why-are-negative-results-still-six-feet-under/>

4. Copyright and licenses

Details

Subtitle: How to protect authors and support reuse

Duration: Approximately 45 minutes

Keywords: Copyright, licenses, Creative Commons, author rights, policies, integrity

Abstract: Learn how to implement effective copyright and licensing policies that balance author rights with open knowledge-sharing principles in Diamond OA publishing.

Introduction

Copyright ownership and right management ensure research is both accessible and legally protected. This course provides essential guidance for implementing effective policies that balance author rights with knowledge-sharing principles, ensuring your publishing activities align with Open Science values/practices.

In this course, you will learn:

- How to select appropriate open licenses that maximise research impact
- How to develop and communicate transparent policies that both protect scholarly work and promote open knowledge sharing
- Practical approaches for addressing third-party content and implementing best practices for license display

Glossary

Authors' rights or copyright: A rights regime that grants exclusive rights to creators of original works, including literary, artistic, musical, and other creative expressions, allowing them to control how their works are used and distributed. Open licence

Open Science: Open science (OS) is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. Reference/derivation: [Unesco Recommendation on Open Science](#)

Training material 1: Interactive course

This course provides essential guidance for implementing copyright and licensing practices that align with Diamond Open Access publishing.

You'll learn to navigate rights management, select appropriate licences, and develop transparent policies that both protect scholarly work and promote open knowledge sharing – advancing the core principles of Open Science through your publishing activities.

Step 1. Introduction to Copyright

Foundational concepts

If you're already comfortable with copyrights basics, feel free to skip ahead or take the True/False quiz below as a quick refresher. If you're not or would like a review, please read through the chapter carefully and then test your knowledge with the quiz.

What is copyright?

Copyright is a legal right that protects the creator(s) of original works of authorship, such as text, music, images or code. In the context of scholarly publishing, this typically refers to works like research articles, books, datasets, illustrations, charts, multimedia elements and code. This right gives the copyright holder exclusive control over how their work is used, reproduced, and distributed.

What does copyright protect?

Copyright protects the *expression* of an idea, not the idea itself. That means you can't claim ownership of procedures, methods or concepts, only how authors articulate them in their work. For a research article, copyright protects its specific wording, structure, and organisation, but not the underlying research methods, data sets, or scientific concepts discussed within it.

The distinction between ideas and expression is a key aspect of copyright law and plays a central role when reusing or building upon someone else's work. If you are using the work itself – such as

quoting text or replicating its unique structure – this will likely involve copyright considerations. However, if you are drawing on the ideas or concepts represented in the work, copyright may not apply.

What kind of rights are we talking about?

Copyright grants two main types of rights: *moral rights* and *economic rights*.

- Moral Rights: These are the author's personal rights, connected to their authorship of the work. That means that even when reuse is allowed, users must:
 - Credit authors appropriately.
 - Avoid altering the work in a way that could harm the author's reputation.
- Economic Rights: These rights relate to the financial exploitation of the work. This means that anyone wishing to copy, share, translate, or modify the work must obtain permission from the copyright holder—unless an exception applies or the work is covered by an open license.

When does it start, and how long does it last?

Copyright protection begins the moment a work is created and saved in a tangible form – for example, when it's written down, recorded, or saved electronically. It doesn't require formal registration. That means you can't assume a work is free to use just because it lacks a formal copyright notice or registration.

The duration of copyright protection varies:

Economic Rights: These typically last for the author's lifetime plus a minimum of 50 years, as per the Berne Convention. Many countries extend this to the author's lifetime plus 70 years. After this period, the work enters the public domain, making it freely available for anyone to use, adapt, and redistribute without needing permission for these economic uses.

Moral Rights: In many jurisdictions and most European countries, moral rights are perpetual or last considerably longer than economic rights. Even after a scholarly work enters the public domain, the author's right to attribution and the right to protect the integrity of their work often remain. However, in some jurisdictions, moral rights expire alongside economic rights (e.g., in the UK).

Is copyright the same everywhere?

Copyright is regulated by the copyright acts of each country, and different legal systems around the world use different words and legal provisions for the concept of rights that authors have over the works they have created. Because of these variations, publishers and users should verify copyright duration in both the author, the copyright holder's country and the country where they intend to use the work to ensure compliance with applicable laws.

For example, in most European countries, copyright lasts for the author's lifetime plus 70 years, but the UK has additional rules, such as the "2039 rule," which protects some unpublished works until December 31, 2039. Moral rights also differ: in France and Germany, they are perpetual, while in the UK, they expire alongside economic rights. Other differences include how exceptions for education or research and licensing systems are regulated across European jurisdictions.

[D4.4 Training report]

However, there are some basic common understandings related to copyright (or authors' rights) in scholarly publishing. Some international agreements are in place (such as The Berne Convention, or the WIPO Copyright Treaty) that allow us to have some minimal common ground to apply the same procedures globally.

Are there exceptions?

Copyright law seeks a balance between protecting creators' rights and ensuring reasonable public access. This balance is achieved through specific exceptions and limitations to copyright.

In some jurisdictions, these are referred to as "fair use" or "fair dealing", which allow the use of copyrighted works without permission or payment in certain circumstances. The specific exceptions and limitations are defined by national copyright laws and vary significantly internationally, which is why publishers must be aware of jurisdictional differences to ensure compliance.

They usually include the use of works for purposes such as quotation, creating accessible versions for print-disabled individuals, or text and data mining for research. These exceptions often support education, research, and accessibility, ensuring that copyright does not overly hinder societal progress.

Step 2. Activity: True or False? Questions to check your understanding

Options

1. Copyright protects the idea itself, not just its expression. (False)
2. Copyright begins when a work is published. (False)
3. Copyright protection requires formal registration. (False)
4. Moral rights include the right to be attributed as the author. (True)
5. Moral rights last until the works enter the public domain. (False)
6. Translating a work into another language requires permission from the copyright holder. (True)
7. The use of copyrighted works for disabled people and educational purposes is allowed without attribution. (False)
8. Adapting a copyrighted work in a new format (book to movie) does not require permission from the original copyright owner. (False)
9. Since the Berne Convention, all member countries must implement identical copyright laws. (False)

Feedback

1. **Incorrect.** Copyright protects how an idea is expressed, not the idea itself.
2. **Incorrect.** It begins upon creation in a tangible form (written, recorded, etc.), not when published.
3. **Incorrect.** Copyright exists automatically upon creation of a tangible work.
4. **Correct!** Moral rights protect your connection to the work – your right to be known as the author and to prevent alterations that harm your reputation.

5. **Incorrect.** Unlike economic rights that typically expire 70 years after the author's death, moral rights are perpetual in most of the jurisdictions, or last considerably longer than economic rights.
6. **Correct!** Translation is a form of adaptation and requires permission from the holder of the economic rights. If the original author still retains these rights, they may be the same person or entity.
7. **Incorrect.** While exceptions exist for disability and education, they often still require attribution and may have other limitations.
8. **Incorrect.** Adaptations like book-to-movie require permission as they create a derivative work.
9. **Incorrect.** The Berne Convention sets *minimum* standards, not identical laws. Countries can have their own variations as long as they meet the minimum requirements.

Step 3. Who can own the rights and how?

The initial copyright holders can be the author or its employer

In most cases, the author(s) of a scholarly work are the initial copyright holders. This means they have the initial right to determine how their work is used and distributed. Some legal systems reinforce this by stipulating that only natural persons (individuals) can be the first owners of copyright, excluding companies or institutions (legal persons).

A key exception is the concept of "work for hire." In some legal systems, the employer can be considered the legal author and copyright owner from the moment of creation. The author(s) only retain their moral rights to the work created, as they are non-transferable in most legislations – that means publishers must always respect authors' moral rights by crediting them clearly and obtaining approval for significant alterations to their work.

This is more common in corporate settings but can sometimes apply to scholarly works, when authors are employed by academic institutions. Even in such situations, most academic institutions usually (informally or explicitly) leave the disposal of copyright to the authors who can decide how and where to publish their works.

Publishers need to be certain who holds the economic rights to a work before signing agreements or publishing. While authors are often assumed to be the rights holders, this isn't always the case. Copyright might automatically belong to an author's employer (e.g., a university) if the work was created as part of their employment. Publishers might need to engage them with both the author AND their institution to secure necessary rights, adding complexity to the process.

Copyright transfer in scholarly publishing

In scholarly publishing, authors can transfer their copyright to the publisher or retain it. These two paths have significant implications for how their work is disseminated and reused.

Traditional subscription-based journals often require authors to transfer their copyright to the publisher. This transfer can significantly limit how authors can use their own work, but authors and publishers can negotiate various terms. The transfer can be full or partial, and for a limited or unlimited time. A full transfer gives the publisher extensive control over the work's use,

[D4.4 Training report]

including reproduction, distribution, adaptation, and display. A partial transfer allows authors to retain some rights, such as self-archiving or educational use.

This model also limits the accessibility and dissemination of research, frequently placing it behind paywalls. This is why it doesn't align with Open Access principles. Open Access aims to fundamentally change this dynamic by prioritising free access to research for everyone and empowering authors to control the dissemination of their work. This is achieved by supporting author rights.

Rights retention in scholarly publishing

Rights retention policy is a requirement in the Diamond Open Access Standard. Diamond Open Access publishers should guarantee that authors retain sufficient rights for their works to enable them to be openly accessible and immediately reusable.

This is typically achieved through a clear copyright policy where authors retain full rights and grant the publisher a non-exclusive publishing license.

This allows authors to:

- Reproduce their work in various formats.
- Adapt their work, creating translations or revised editions.
- Distribute their work widely via repositories, websites, and other platforms.
- Publicly perform or display their work.

Retaining these rights empowers authors to maximise the impact of their research.

While Diamond Open Access strongly recommends this approach, other options are possible. Journals can claim the exclusive right to exploit the work, or the right to exploit it for some purposes and in some ways (e.g. the right to decide on commercial uses or the right to adaptations). The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) does not consider this a recommended practice but accepts such journals as well

Step 4. Activity: MCQs: Questions to check your understanding

[Correct answers underlined]

What is "work for hire" in the context of copyright?

- When an employer is considered the legal author and copyright owner from the moment of creation.
- When an author hires someone to edit their work.
- When a publisher pays an author to write a work, but the author keeps the copyright unless stated otherwise.
- When an author gives permission to a publisher to distribute their work but keeps the copyright.

What are moral rights in copyright?

- Non-transferable rights of the author to be attributed and prevent alterations to their work.
- Rights related to the ethical implications of the research.
- Rights that allow the author to control commercial use of their work.

- Rights that allow the author to distribute their work freely.

What is the primary difference between copyright transfer and rights retention?

- Copyright transfer gives the publisher exclusive rights. Rights retention lets authors keep most rights.
- Copyright transfer is common in traditional publishing. Rights retention is popular in Open Access.
- Copyright transfer often allows broader reuse; rights retention restricts reuse.
- Rights retention guarantees moral rights to the publisher, while copyright transfer does not.

How does Open Access differ from commercial copyright transfer models?

- Authors retain most of their rights.
- Authors grant publishers a license to publish the work.
- The author's institution is the copyright owner from the moment of creation
- Copyright transfer is required to protect and publish authors.

This idea is a myth: copyright transfer often strips authors of control over their work, limits dissemination, and primarily benefits publishers. Learn more here: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/scholcom/98/>

Why should Diamond OA journals let authors retain rights instead of requiring copyright transfer?

- This allows authors to share and reuse their work freely, aligning with open access principles.
- This ensures the journal can't modify the work without authors' approval.
- This helps attract more submissions.
- This limits the journal's ability to distribute the work.

Which of these rights are typically retained by authors in Diamond Open Access?

- The right to reproduce and distribute their work.
- The right to adapt their work.
- The right to publicly perform or display their work.
- The right to prevent all forms of reuse.

Why does Diamond Open Access strongly discourage copyright transfer?

- It limits authors' ability to reuse their work
- It increases the cost of publishing for authors

Step 5. Transparency on copyright policy

It is a good practice that all prospective authors are informed about the copyright policy of each journal they are considering for submissions.

Information on copyright should be stated in several places:

1. In the instructions for authors.
2. On separate pages or sections of a journal / a publisher dedicated to copyright and/or open access.

[D4.4 Training report]

3. In publishing contracts/agreements if they exist (regardless of what they are called: publication statements, publication permissions, licenses to publish, copyright agreements...).
4. In the full text of the works/paper (stating who is the copyright holder).
5. In the metadata description of the work (indicating who is the copyright holder), but this often depends on the capabilities of the platform.

It is very important to state who is the copyright holder, so that those who want to request permission for commercial use or adaptations and derivative use know who to contact. Stating that the copyright holders are both the publisher/journal and the authors is unclear and isn't helpful in such situations.

Step 6. Third party copyright

Including excerpts, images, or other content created by others can significantly enrich a publication. However, using third-party copyrighted material requires careful attention to legal and ethical considerations.

While the author bears the primary responsibility for obtaining these permissions, the journal or publishing service are responsible for ensuring compliance and upholding copyright law. Here's how

- Clearly inform authors: Instructions for authors should explicitly state the need for permissions and specify the type required (usually non-exclusive, but unlimited in scope and duration).
- Obtain author confirmation: Require a statement from the author confirming that all necessary permissions have been obtained.
- Verify citations: check whether all sources are properly cited in the article.
- Specify terms of use (when necessary): clearly state the terms of use (e.g., the third-party work's license) separately for individual elements in the work.

Open Access and Third-Party Materials

A common misconception is that open-access publishing restricts the use of third-party materials. The following video clarifies this point: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8KfY8CzR9HE>

In this video, Jan M. Ziolkowski, Arthur Kingsley Porter Professor of Medieval Latin at Harvard University and author of the open-access book series, *The Juggler of Notre Dame and the Medievalizing of Modernity*, debunks this myth. He explains how copyrighted images and other third-party materials can be incorporated within open-access publications, provided the necessary permissions are obtained. This reinforces the importance of the steps outlined above for all publications, regardless of their access model.

Step 7. Activity: Multiple formats

True or False

1. An image found on Google Images can be used in a publication as long as it's cited.
False. Images found on Google Images are not necessarily free to use. Google Images is a search engine, not a source of free images. Check the licence on the image, permission is required from the copyright holder, even with citation.

2. If a work is very old, it's automatically in the public domain and can be used freely.
False. Works enter the public domain after a specific period, but this period varies by country and the date of creation/publication. "Very old" doesn't automatically mean public domain.
3. If an author creates a chart based on data from a spreadsheet/table, they need permission to use it.
True. Creating a chart based on data organised in a spreadsheet or a table can infringe on the copyright, unless the table is published under a licence allowing remixing.
4. An author can use an image they found on a website that states "all rights reserved" as long as they credit the website.
False. "All rights reserved" explicitly indicates that the copyright holder retains all rights and permission is required for any use. Crediting the website is not enough. Permission is required even if there is no copyright symbol and/or statement. Unless explicitly stated otherwise (e.g. by using an open licence), all rights are reserved.

MCQs

1. Why is it important for Diamond OA publishers to require authors to ensure copyright clearance prior to submission? Copyright clearance is the process of obtaining permission from the copyright holder to distribute their work. *[correct answers underlined]*
 - To avoid legal issues related to unauthorised use of copyrighted material.
 - To ensure the work can be shared and reused under an open licence.
 - To be able to control future licensing and commercial use of the work.
 - To be able to take copyright for themselves.
 - To prevent multiple versions of the work from being published elsewhere.
2. What should a publisher do if authors assert that they own the work or have obtained copyright clearance, but an illustration appears to belong to a third party?
 - Ask the author for proof of permission or a replacement
 - Assume the image is free to use and publish it
 - Publish the image but include a disclaimer
3. An author wants to include a chart from another journal in their article. What is the correct approach?
 - Request permission from the copyright holder and cite the original
 - Redraw the chart exactly as it appears and cite the original
 - Include the chart with a note saying "used with permission"

Short scenarios

1. An author adapts 19th century illustrations, changing colours and adding minor details. Does this create a new copyrighted work?
Not necessarily. Minor changes may not be sufficient to create a new copyright. "Derivative works" require permission.
2. An author has verbal permission to use a colleague's conference presentation slides in their book chapter. Is verbal permission sufficient for publication?

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No. Written permission is required for publication, such as a formal license agreement signed by the copyright holder (the colleague).

3. A group of authors have published a paper with a commercial publisher and have transferred copyright to the publisher. Can they translate the paper to their native language and publish it in a Diamond Open Access journal without permission?

No. They need permission from the original paper's copyright holder.

Step 8. Introduction to licenses

Foundational concepts

If you're already comfortable with these concepts, feel free to skip ahead or use the flash cards below as a quick refresher. If you're new to licensing or would like a review, please read through the chapter carefully and then test your knowledge with the flash cards.

What are licences?

Licenses are legal agreements that allow copyright holders to define how the work can be used, copied, shared, and adapted, under specific terms and conditions.

Different licensing models cater to various publishing approaches, from traditional subscription-based models to open access.

Why are licenses needed if copyright already exists?

The use of all published works, unless otherwise specified, is fully defined by copyright regulations in the respective country. Legal regulations on copyright are today largely harmonised around the world, and while copyright laws generally allow for the use of copyrighted works by the public for some purposes without asking for permission, they are still too restrictive for all the benefits of open access to be realised.

Licenses offer a more flexible approach to copyright management, particularly in the context of open access publishing.

Proprietary Licenses

Traditional publishing, often involving copyright transfer, typically uses proprietary licenses that grant the publisher exclusive rights and restrict how others can use the work. These licenses may include specific exceptions for authors, such as allowing self-archiving or educational use. The specific terms and conditions of these proprietary licenses can vary significantly between publishers.

Open Licences

Open licenses provide a standardised and flexible framework for facilitating the broad dissemination and reuse of creative works. In the world of scholarly publishing, the Creative Commons (Cset of licences is today recognised as the gold standard to ensure the widest possible dissemination and reuse of research.

CC licences are built upon a modular system, allowing copyright holders to grant usage rights while retaining certain rights. All but one (CC0) of the CC licenses require attribution (BY), meaning anyone using the work must credit the original creator. Additional conditions include:

- Non-Commercial (NC): Restricts the use of the work to non-commercial purposes. This prevents others from profiting from the work without explicit permission.
- No Derivatives (ND): Prohibits the creation of adaptations or modifications of the work. This ensures the work remains in its original form.
- ShareAlike (SA): Requires any adaptations of the work to be shared under the same CC license as the original. This promotes a culture of reciprocal sharing and ensures that derivative works remain open.

These conditions can be combined to create six main CC licenses, ranging from the most permissive (CC BY) to the most restrictive (CC BY-NC-ND).

Choosing the right Creative Commons license involves balancing author preferences with the goals of maximising dissemination and encouraging appropriate reuse. Consider the specific needs of the research area and the potential impact of different licensing options. A CC-BY Licence is a preferred open licence in the Diamond Open Access Standard to ensure further reuse without restrictions.

Resources

To help you understand CC licenses better, here are some resources:

- Foter : How to Attribute Creative Commons Photos : [\[link\]](#) - This infographic provides a visual guide on properly attributing CC-licensed images.
- Creative Common Kiwi: Creative Commons Explained: [\[link\]](#) - This video uses sketchnotes to explain Creative Commons in an engaging and easy-to-understand format
- CreativeCommons.org: Creative Commons License Chooser: [\[link\]](#) - This interactive tool helps you choose the right CC license for your work by asking simple questions about your desired usage restrictions

Step 9. Activity: Flashcards

Test your understanding with these flashcards. Look at the question on the front of the card, think of the answer in your head, then flip the card over and check your answer.

What are licenses? [Legal agreements that define how copyrighted work can be used, copied, shared, and adapted]

What are the benefits of using licenses compared to relying solely on copyright law? [It provides a more flexible approach to copyright management. / It offers more granular control over how published works are used]

What licensing model best aligns with the principles of open access, and why? [Open Licenses, especially Creative Commons, because it maximises dissemination and reuse of research.]

What is the core requirement of all CC licenses? [Attribution (BY) - users must credit the original author.]

What do the additional conditions mean: 💰 NC, 🗝️ ND, 🔗 SA? [Non-Commercial, No derivatives, ShareAlike]

Step 10. Choosing a licence

When selecting and applying licences for open access publications, it is essential to consider various factors.

In Diamond Open Access Standards

In Diamond Open Access, all scholarly works should be made openly available directly at the time of publication and reusable under the terms of an open licence so that content is truly open and knowledge is available to be both used and reused.

If OA journals wish their content to be truly open for different kinds of use and reuse, by all users, without the need to seek permissions, they can do so by granting such permissions in advance, clearly and publicly. Granting such liberal permissions in advance is best achieved by using standardised and machine-readable open licenses.

Since the definition of Open access as it is set out in the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI, 2002) and Berlin Declaration (MPG, 2003) is to grant full reuse of published academic outputs, subject to proper attribution of authorship, we can see that CC BY is the preferred license to be applied to scholarly works.

For OA journals (and for the authors of their content), a CC BY licence brings clear benefits and advantages. It enables full reuse and application without barriers in different contexts: research, innovation, education, culture, and business. It enhances the impact of published works, both academic and societal. At the same time, it provides legal protection for authors and rights holders, as the condition of attribution always applies. In the domain of journal publishing, attribution means that the original authors and place of publication should always be cited and linked, ideally by using persistent identifiers.

What to consider

While CC BY is clearly the recommended license for OA journals, the ultimate choice of license for each journal should be a result of thoughtful consideration, and all stakeholders (editors, owners, publishers, authors and reviewers) should be made fully aware of the implications of the licence chosen.

Various factors can influence the journal's decision on a specific/recommended license:

- Tradition Customs and culture in a specific scientific discipline (e.g. some fields of humanities are reluctant to implement licences that permit derivative works since they prefer to control the rights to translations, for example)
- Research funder requirements (e.g. some European and international funders require CC BY for grantees)
- Requirements of some databases (e.g. DOAJ requests that the journal use one of the CC licenses, but does not require a specific one)

How to assign a license

Depending on who the holder of the copyright is (or who has the exclusive right to publish the work), assigning a license typically follows one of two routes:

A - If the author has retained the rights (which is the recommended practice for OA journals), the author should choose or approve the license (via contract, statement or during the online manuscript submission)

B - If the publisher is the holder of exclusive rights, they can determine the license independently and assign them to the published works.

Applying licenses to older works

For either route, the journal's decision at one point in time to use a certain license does not automatically mean that this license applies to all older works of the journal.

If authors retain their rights (situation A), the journal must obtain permission from the authors (right holders) to apply a license to older content.

If the journal holds exclusive rights (situation B), they can decide independently to apply open licenses to backfile content.

Applying licenses to new work

All journal content. Usually, one licence is used for all journal content (or even for all of the journals of one publisher), but in some cases, journals can opt for the adoption of several licences and leave the decision on a licence to the authors of each article.

Different manuscripts. A journal may impose different types of licenses for different versions of a manuscript (preprint/postprint/final version), however, this is not recommended for OA journals. OA journals should leave the authors to decide under the terms of which licence they will distribute the preprint or the author-accepted manuscript versions.

How to display a licence

When a journal decides on the license that will be used, it needs to take care both that the license is actually assigned to the published content and that the content is distributed under the terms of that license.

Licensing policies should be stated:

- In the instructions to the authors
- On separate pages/sections dedicated to copyright and/or open access
- In publishing contracts or agreements, if they exist
- By registering policies in in Open Policy Finder: <https://openpolicyfinder.jisc.ac.uk/>
- By recording policies in DOAJ
- On the journal pages of the publishing service's platform of choice

The licenses themselves should be displayed:

- In the articles/chapters themselves, in all formats of the complete text (e.g. PDF and HTML). It should be:
 - machine-readable : as a URL to the license text

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- human-readable :
 - Icons. Eg. the CC logos
 - hyperlinks to the full legal text of the licence. E.g. [This](#).
 - the short descriptive text in the article. E.g. *“You are free to share and adapt this work, but you must give appropriate credit and distribute your contributions under the same license”*.
- In the metadata description of the works: ensure the licence information is embedded in the metadata. Learn more in the Metadata course.

Discipline- and format-specific considerations on licences

In some scholarly fields, the use of so-called “third-party copyright” (materials for which other persons or institutions are authors, owners and rights-holders) is more common than in others, such as, for instance, in art history. Where that is the case, journals should give detailed advice to authors on how to acquire permission to use such materials for them to be able to insert them into their own works and distribute them under the open licence. When it is not possible, such third-party materials should be clearly labelled to communicate that they are not being distributed under the same licence as the work in a whole. In some cases, it can even be required that such materials be omitted from the OA editions (Hudson & Aplin, 2023)

Step 11. Conclusion

Managing copyright and licensing in Diamond Open Access publishing depends on well-defined practices that balance protecting authors' rights, enabling reuse, and ensuring accessibility and compliance.

This course has provided the essential knowledge to implement clear policies, choose and apply appropriate licences, and handle the complexities of copyright management, including guiding authors on retaining rights and licensing options, incorporating third-party content responsibly, and addressing discipline-specific copyright considerations.

For quick reference, a guide summarising where and how to display licenses and copyrights is available here :

https://training.diamas.org/pluginfile.php/246/mod_resource/content/3/DOAS%20-%20Copyright%20and%20licenses%20-%20Visual%20guide.pdf

Training material 2: Infographic**What information to display, where and how: a short guide for journal publishers**

Copyright owners and licensing policies

- Author instructions
- Dedicated copyright and/or Open Access pages.
- Publishing contracts/agreements (if applicable)
- Open Policy Finder + Directory of Open Access Journals databases
- Full text of the work/paper

- Metadata description of the work

Licenses

In all formats of the articles (e.g. PDF, HTML):

- Name of the license
- License icon. eg. the CC logos
- Hyperlinks to the full legal text of the licence. e.g. "This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#)."
- Short descriptive text in the article. e.g. "You are free to share and adapt this work, but you must give appropriate credit and distribute your contributions under the same license"

In the metadata description in the article:

- Name of the license
- URL to the licence text
- In the metadata submitted when registering article persistent identifiers (DOI, ARK, URN, etc.)

Guidelines for Third-Party Copyright

Requirements for authors:

- Obtain necessary permissions
- Properly cite all third-party content
- Include separate license information if needed

General best practices

- Clarity is key: write precise and easy-to-read content.
- Machines matter: ensure accurate and properly formatted metadata.
- One policy, all platforms: maintain consistent policies across journals and platforms.
- Legal harmony: copyright and licensing should not contradict each other.
- Stay up-to-date: regularly review and update policies.

5. Preprints and repositories

Details

Subtitle: Early sharing, long-term access

Duration: Approximately 30 minutes

Keywords: Preprints, repositories, archive, deposit, dissemination/visibility, preservation

[D4.4 Training report]

Abstract: Learn how to implement preprints, repository deposits, and self-archiving practices in your Diamond OA publishing workflow to enhance research visibility/dissemination and preservation/long-term accessibility.

Introduction

The scholarly community is increasingly using preprints, self-archiving, and repositories as essential pillars of open science. These practices are transforming how research is shared, discovered, and preserved.

This course will help you understand the role of preprints and repositories in open science while guiding you through practical approaches to encourage their use.

In this course, you will learn:

- How preprints and repositories can complement formal journal publishing
- How to encourage and guide authors on using repositories and preprints effectively.
- How to integrate repository deposits into your publishing workflow

Glossary

Open Science: Open science (OS) is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. Reference/derivation: [Unesco Recommendation on Open Science](#)

Persistent identifiers: A persistent identifier (PID) is a long-lasting reference to a digital object, person, organisation, or other entity. It is unique to an entity and remains stable over time, i.e. it resolves even if the location of the entity changes.

PIDs widely used in scholarly publishing:

- DOI (Digital Object Identifier)
- Handle
- Archival Resource Key (ARK)
- URN (Uniform Resource Name)
- ISBN (International Standard Book Number)
- ISSN (International Standard Serial Number)
- ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)
- ROR (Research Organization Registry)
- ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)

Reference/derivation: PID Services Registry: <https://pidservices.org/>

Preprints: Preprints are often defined as complete and public drafts of scientific documents, not yet certified by peer review. However, some authors of preprints do not intend to publish them in a peer-reviewed publication. Additionally, a preprint can be large datasets with descriptions, protocols, (parts of) a thesis, presentations, reports of negative results, commentaries, videos, and more, which do not pass a standard peer review process. A preprint can also be peer-reviewed by a community, by a combination of artificial intelligence with human expert peer review, or by reviewers exclusively. Ambiguities and disagreements around the definition of preprints need to be addressed to offer more precise and less anachronistic terms in such an innovative area. The main purpose of preprints is to disseminate research results to the scientific community, establish ownership of results, and receive feedback from the professional community before submission to a journal. Preprints, “not filtered by their perceived quality or pertinence”, can reduce the competitive pressure imposed on researchers and reduce the negative consequences of filtering scholarly information.

Reference/derivation: Stojanovski, J., Marušić, A. (2024). Preprints Are Here to Stay: Is That Good for Science?. In: Eaton, S.E. (eds) Second Handbook of Academic Integrity. Springer International Handbooks of Education. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_145

Training material 1: interactive course

Step 1. Introduction

The scholarly community is increasingly using preprints, self-archiving, and repositories as essential pillars of open science. These practices are transforming how research is shared, discovered, and preserved.

As a Diamond Open Access publisher, this course will guide you through understanding preprints, repositories, and self-archiving, while providing practical guidance on implementing and managing these practices effectively in your publishing operations.

Step 2. Definition - What are preprints, self-archiving, and repositories ?

A **preprint** is a scientific manuscript publicly shared on an online platform before undergoing formal peer review and publication in a journal.

Researchers often **self-archive** preprints and other versions of their papers to ensure their permanent availability and broader reach. Self-archiving involves depositing a free copy of an electronic document into digital platforms called **repositories**.

This practice extends beyond preprints and often includes peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers – often the Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) – as well as theses, dissertations, book chapters, and other research outputs.

Researchers may choose institutional repositories, disciplinary repositories specific to their field, general-purpose repositories like Zenodo, or dedicated preprint servers.

Examples of preprint servers/repositories: [Zenodo](#) – multidisciplinary; [ArXiv](#) – physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical

[D4.4 Training report]

engineering and systems science, and economics; [bioRxiv](#) - life sciences; [medRxiv](#) - medicine and health sciences; [SocArXiv](#) - social sciences and humanities; [PsyArxiv](#) - behavioural sciences; [LawArXiv](#) - law; [MediArXiv](#) - media and communication studies; [Knowledge Commons](#) (formerly Humanities Commons). Use the Directory [of Open Access Preprint Repositories](#) to find more (you could browse by disciplines).

What's the difference between repositories and platforms like ResearchGate and Academia.edu?

ResearchGate and Academia.edu are commercial social networking sites that generate revenue from user content. While these platforms can be valuable for networking with other researchers and sharing work informally, they lack proper copyright oversight and don't guarantee long-term preservation of your work.

For reliable open access archiving that meets institutional requirements, an academic repository is the appropriate choice, though you may choose to use both types of platforms for their distinct benefits.

Learn more : <https://osc.universityofcalifornia.edu/2015/12/a-social-networking-site-is-not-an-open-access-repository/>

Step 3. Benefits - Why use preprints and self-archiving ?

Preprint publication is an alternative route that provides a complementary approach to traditional publishing, allowing researchers to share their work in a different format.

Let's compare their workflows with the following figure.

[The image below is interactive. To explore the different stages, please click and drag the slider bar (the horizontal control found beneath the image) from left to right. As you move it, the image will change, revealing each step of the workflows.]

Once you have viewed all the stages, answer the question that follows.

Figure text alternative: Preprint workflow

Manuscript → Uploaded to a preprints server → Published and accessible to the community. This process takes a few days. The preprint gets a DOI, timestamp, and community feedback once published.

At the same time as the preprint is uploaded, or once the preprint is published (with or without editing):

Journal Workflow: Manuscript → Submission to a journal → Assessment by the editor → Reviewing by peer Reviewers → Published and accessible to the community. This process can take months or years. The published article gets a DOI, timestamp, and community feedback.

Step 4. Activity

Based on this figure, which of the following do you think are benefits of using preprints? [correct answers marked with an asterisk]

***Faster sharing of research findings.** *Feedback: Researchers can share their work before or while the formal peer review process proceeds in parallel.*

***Protection against plagiarism.** *Feedback: Preprints provide a timestamp, ensuring credit for discoveries and protecting against plagiarism.*

***Receiving early feedback from the scientific community.** *Feedback: This fosters collaboration among researchers and helps researchers refine their manuscript before journal submission.*

Replacing peer reviewed journal submission. *Feedback: Preprints complement but do not replace the peer review process and formal journal publication.*

As you can see, preprints present a valuable opportunity for publishers to support transparency, accelerate knowledge sharing, and engage with the evolving needs of the research community.

Beyond faster dissemination, plagiarism protection, and early feedback opportunities, preprints also act as proof of productivity for funding applications and hiring processes, increase citation potential through enhanced visibility, and make research widely accessible via platforms like Google Scholar and Europe PMC.

Given these numerous benefits, it's no surprise that preprints and self-archiving have become increasingly popular practices in open access publishing, with a growing number of journals accepting manuscripts that have been previously posted as preprints – for a detailed overview, you can refer to [this list of academic publishers by preprint policy](#). You can click the link to open it, then use your browser's back button to return to the course.

What's the difference between repositories and platforms like ResearchGate and Academia.edu ?

ResearchGate and Academia.edu are commercial social networking sites that generate revenue from user content. While these platforms can be valuable for networking with other researchers and sharing work informally, they lack proper copyright oversight and don't guarantee long-term preservation of your work.

For reliable open access archiving that meets institutional requirements, an academic repository is the appropriate choice, though you may choose to use both types of platforms for their distinct benefits.

Learn more:

- <https://osc.universityofcalifornia.edu/2015/12/a-social-net-working-site-is-not-an-open-access-repository/>
- <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1099&context=scholcom> : Myths
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bvPrDSyZ3z4> (9") This video features members of the UK Reproducibility Network community sharing their experiences of preprints.
- You can also have a look at [first-hand stories from researchers](#) about their experience with preprints and the impact it had on their science and interactions with their community.

Step 5. Practices - What you can do as a publisher

Early and open sharing is a cornerstone of transparent research practices and a key measure to enhance the reproducibility of research outputs.

As a publisher, you should encourage the free circulation of knowledge rather than restrict it, fostering a culture of openness and collaboration in scholarly communication. Here's what you can do.

1. Allow preprints

Authors should be allowed to disseminate their preprint version/s at any time before and after the article acceptance and publishing. That means you should:

- Allow preprint dissemination: You should allow the deposit of any version of the published work in open repositories of authors' choice, before or after the publication.
- Consider accepting preprint submissions: You should consider accepting the submissions of unreviewed and peer reviewed preprints that are already available on preprint servers or in open repositories.

2. Define a clear preprint policy allowing preprint submissions

- Allow authors to submit manuscripts made available as preprints and include reviews made on a preprint peer review platform such as PCI. Include a note in your Author's responsibilities/Guidelines clauses that posting of preprints on preprint servers or repositories is not considered prior publication.
- Require authors to disclose details of preprint posting upon submission of the manuscript, including a link to the location of the preprint.
- Should the submission be accepted and published, remind authors to update their preprint record on the preprint server/repository with a link to the final published version in your journal, including its DOI.

3. Define a clear self-archiving policy

You can re-use our model wording below to develop your self-archiving policy:

Authors can deposit preprints (versions before peer review) at any time, Author Accepted Manuscripts (AAMs) after acceptance, and/or Versions of Record (VoRs) after publication in a repository of the authors' choice (e.g. an institutional, disciplinary and general-purpose repository. etc.).

Full bibliographic information (authors, article title, journal title, volume, issue, pages) about the original publication must be provided and links must be made to the article's DOI and the license.

4. Align with licensing and peer review

- If you use a CC BY licence, and/or if you have a policy where authors retain publishing rights, the right to deposit and share is already granted to the authors. You could let authors decide on the licence used when depositing their content, or recommend your preferred licence.
- If you allow preprints, double-blind review is not an option for your journal because it is impossible to ensure the anonymity of authors.

5. Guide authors on best practices

- Explain to your authors that sharing through academic networks and social media is not equal to the benefits of repositories. Repositories are usually non-profits, open and interoperable and ensure long-term preservation and access. See more details here: [A social networking site is not an open access repository](#).
 - Encourage supplementary material deposits. Recommend/require authors deposit all supplementing materials (e.g. research data), and establish links between those deposits and the article.
6. [Consider adopting/implementing the Publish, Review, Curate \(PRC\) model](#)

The Publish, Review, Curate (PRC) model offers publishers an innovative way to integrate preprints into scholarly publishing while maintaining rigorous peer review.

PRC is a researcher-driven model that involves the review, validation, and editorial commentary of preprints.

As part of the Diamond Open Access ecosystem, it can be implemented in low-cost environments and can accommodate a wide variety of editorial workflows, types of peer review, and research outputs, as demonstrated by several flavours of PRC that are already operational – from overlay journals that more closely mirror a typical journal publication, to approaches that are adopting very innovative practices.

See [Peer Community In](#), [Episcience](#), [eLife](#), [PREreview](#), and [Psicológica](#),

Learn more

- about the benefits of PRC <https://coar-repositories.org/what-we-do/recommendations-and-best-practices/overlay-journals/>
- If you are interested in starting an overlay journal, [DARIAH Open](#) has a number of helpful guidance and information resources available on their website. And [read this Case Study on Psicológica Overlay Journal Workflow](#).

Step 6. Knowledge check

You can now test your understanding of key preprint concepts with the following activity. Below are 12 statements about preprint policies and practices, presented by pairs. In each pair only one affirmation is correct.

Select all accurate statements to create a comprehensive overview of what you've learned. [Correct answers marked with an asterisk]

*Preprints allow researchers to gather feedback before formal publication.

Repositories primarily serve as backups for research data.

*Self-archiving in repositories can increase citations for research articles.

Preprints cannot be cited in formal research articles due to their lack of peer review.

*Preprints work with peer review models like PRC.

Research has to be finalised to be archived in a preprint repository.

[D4.4 Training report]

*When using preprints, double-blind peer review is not possible due to author anonymity issues.

A clear preprint policy should state that posting preprints is considered prior publication.

*A CC BY license grants authors the right to share and deposit preprints.

Preprints can't be used to protect against scooping.

*Authors should add DOIs and bibliographic links to preprints.

Once a paper is published in a journal, the preprint version should be removed from repositories.

Step 7. Conclusion

This course has provided a foundational understanding of preprints, self-archiving, and repositories, and their role within Diamond Open Access publishing.

For further reading, here are additional resources :

- Preprint resource center: FAQs, policies, and materials. <https://asapbio.org/preprint-info>
- Consortium of the DIAMAS project. (2024). The Diamond OA Standard(DOAS) - version 1.1. <https://doi.org/10.58121/Z15S-JY03>

6. Open Peer Review

Details

Subtitle: Exploring the spectrum of open peer review

Duration: Approximately 45 minutes

Keywords: Peer review, transparency, evaluation, policy

Abstract: Explore the spectrum of open peer review and assess its benefits and challenges to identify the most suitable approach for your publishing context.

Introduction

Open Peer Review is fundamentally about bringing transparency to how research is evaluated, by opening the review process rather than just making the results of that discussion accessible.

This course will guide you through the various aspects of peer review that can be opened and what is at stake. It provides the groundwork for future implementation decisions.

In this course, you will learn:

- The different aspects of peer review that can be opened – e.g. identities, reports, participation, etc.
- How each open peer review model creates specific opportunities and challenges for editors, reviewers, and authors.

- Key considerations to evaluate which open peer review approach best fits your specific needs.

Glossary

Open Science: Open science (OS) is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. Reference/derivation: [Unesco Recommendation on Open Science](#)

Open Peer Review (OPR): An umbrella term for creating a spectrum of openness tailored to different disciplines and publication models. It is fundamentally about bringing transparency to how research is evaluated by opening the review process rather than just making the results of that discussion accessible. It can involve opening various aspects of the process, including identities, reports, participation, interactions, and pre-review manuscripts.

Preprints: Preprints are often defined as complete and public drafts of scientific documents, not yet certified by peer review. However, some authors of preprints do not intend to publish them in a peer-reviewed publication. Additionally, a preprint can be large datasets with descriptions, protocols, (parts of) a thesis, presentations, reports of negative results, commentaries, videos, and more, which do not pass a standard peer review process. A preprint can also be peer-reviewed by a community, by a combination of artificial intelligence with human expert peer review, or by reviewers exclusively. Ambiguities and disagreements around the definition of preprints need to be addressed to offer more precise and less anachronistic terms in such an innovative area. The main purpose of preprints is to disseminate research results to the scientific community, establish ownership of results, and receive feedback from the professional community before submission to a journal. Preprints, “not filtered by their perceived quality or pertinence”, can reduce the competitive pressure imposed on researchers and reduce the negative consequences of filtering scholarly information.

Reference/derivation: Stojanovski, J., Marušić, A. (2024). Preprints Are Here to Stay: Is That Good for Science? In: Eaton, S.E. (eds) Second Handbook of Academic Integrity. Springer International Handbooks of Education. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_145

Training material 1: interactive course

Step 1. Introduction

Peer review is “a cornerstone of scientific publishing” (Ghosal et al, 2022), ensuring the quality and credibility of research. It serves as the foundation of scholarly communication, providing a seal of quality for research before it enters the academic record.

[D4.4 Training report]

In the traditional model, manuscripts submitted to journals are reviewed by a select group of experts, whose identities are typically kept confidential from the authors (single-blind review) or from both the authors and reviewers (double-blind peer review).

Such a review process itself is opaque, with limited or no interaction between authors and reviewers, and the review reports rarely being made public. This lack of transparency can lead to several issues and face increasing criticism – for a comprehensive overview of these issues, see Stojanovski's 2023 article on open peer review: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/2023/07/05/open-peer-review-an-overview/>.

Over the past two decades, research on peer review has expanded significantly, reflecting a growing awareness of its limitations.

As part of the broader Open Science movement, Open Peer Review presents a viable alternative to traditional models and is gaining acceptance within scholarly communication, indicating that it may soon become standard in academic publishing.

Step 2. Open peer review

Open Peer Review is fundamentally about bringing transparency to how research is evaluated, by opening the review process rather than just making the results of that discussion accessible.

This can involve opening various aspects of the process: identities, reports, participation, interactions, pre-review manuscripts...

Each of these practices can have a different impact on the author, reviewer, and reader experience. They can be combined in various ways, depending on the perspectives and contexts, and can take place on diverse platforms such as preprint servers, journals, or dedicated platforms.

Because of this wide range of interactions and adaptations, Open Peer Review is best understood not as a single practice with an unequivocal definition, but rather as an umbrella term for creating a spectrum of openness tailored to different disciplines and publication models.

Step 3. Pros and cons - Key features: opportunities and pitfalls

As open peer review encompasses such a diverse range of practices, there are various considerations for editors, reviewers and authors to take into account, each presenting new opportunities and challenges to navigate.

The following accordion provides an overview of the key characteristics, advantages, and potential drawbacks of different peer review models, helping you assess which one might best align with your journal(s) when transitioning toward more transparent evaluation processes.

1. **Single Anonymized Peer Review**

The identity of the reviewer is kept confidential, but the author's identity is known to the reviewer.

- No effort is required to anonymize the authors.
- Reviewers know who the authors are, which may help them assess potential conflicts of interest.

- Knowing the author's identity may influence the reviewer's feedback involving bias based on authors' identity, gender, age, affiliation, or career status.
- The review process is not transparent as the review reports are not publicly available.
- Reviewers do not receive public credit for their work.

2. Double Anonymized Peer Review

Both the identities of the reviewer and the author are kept confidential.

- Aims to reduce bias based on authors' identity, gender, age, affiliation, or career status.
- Extra effort is required to ensure that both the authors and reviewers remain anonymous.
- Ensuring authors' anonymity is not always possible.
- The review process is not transparent as the review reports are not publicly available.
- Reviewers do not receive public credit for their work.

3. Triple Anonymized Peer Review

Not only are the identities of the author and reviewer anonymous, but also the editor's identity is hidden from both the author and the reviewer.

- Aims to eliminate potential bias from the editor's relationship with either part.
- The process is administratively complex and requires additional steps to ensure all parties remain anonymous.
- Editors and reviewers do not receive public credit for their work.

4. Open Identities

Both the reviewers' and authors' identities are disclosed to each other.

- A stronger feeling of accountability among reviewers can lead to more constructive and professional feedback.
- Helps reduce conflicts of interest and encourages accountability.
- Can lead to more thorough reviews, but might discourage criticisms.
- Reviewers may be influenced by factors such as the author's identity, age, gender, affiliation, or career stage.
- Some journals may struggle to retain reviewers who prefer to remain anonymous.

5. Open Reports

The peer review reports are published alongside the article, allowing the public to see the feedback given by reviewers. Increases transparency of the review process.

- Readers can evaluate the quality of the reviews and how authors responded.
- Reviewers can get credit for their work and their review reports can be cited.

[D4.4 Training report]

- Reviewers may be influenced by factors such as the author's identity, age, gender, affiliation, or career stage.
- Both reviewers and authors may feel uneasy knowing that reviews will be openly accessible.

6. Open Participation

Anyone from the wider community can contribute to the peer review process, not just invited reviewers.

- Broadens the pool of reviewers, including early-career researchers.
- Can help address biases and elitism in reviewer selection.
- May lead to unstructured feedback and challenges in maintaining quality control.
- Adjusting the publishing platform to support open participation could involve technical challenges.

7. Open Interaction

Open interaction allows direct communication between authors and reviewers, creating a transparent dialogue during the review process.

- Encourages collaboration and constructive feedback.
- Can help authors better understand the reviewer's comments.
- The review process can be more efficient and less time consuming.
- Risks emotional reactions or confrontations.
- Some scholars may be unwilling to review under these conditions, reducing the pool of available reviewers.

8. Open Pre-review Manuscripts

Open pre-review manuscripts involve making a manuscript publicly available (e.g., on preprint servers) before the formal peer review process begins.

- Authors can receive feedback from the broader community, improving the manuscript before formal peer review.
- Risks unstructured or biased feedback.
- Public reviews may be influenced by the author's identity, leading to bias based on gender, affiliation, or reputation.

Step 4. Good practices

Diamond Open Access publishers can implement effective open peer review by following key practices that balance transparency with scholarly integrity while respecting the needs of their research communities.

Good Practices

1. Engage research communities to understand their needs and concerns.
2. Define clear objectives for implementing open peer review.
3. Take a pragmatic approach, balancing transparency with feasibility.

4. Plan for technological needs and associated costs.
5. Communicate effectively with all stakeholders to build trust.
6. Establish performance metrics to assess impact (Ross-Hellauer & Görögh, 2019).

Give authors and reviewers the choice

In your policies, you should provide reviewers with the possibility of:

- signing their reviews either with their identity only visible to the editor, author, and the other reviewers, or with their identity visible to all readers;
- publishing either review summaries or the full content of their review reports with identities visible or not, either alongside the published article or in an open preprint repository.

Such policies can also allow the corresponding author to opt for publishing either review summaries or the full content of review reports of their article or chapter.

Listen to research communities

Publishers should engage closely with their research communities to understand these perspectives and carefully consider their preferences when implementing OPR policies.

The shift towards OPR as a solution to traditional peer review limitations represents a significant evolution in scholarly communication. It challenges traditional notions of authority and expertise, fostering a more transparent and collaborative/participatory approach to research evaluation. (...)

Among the key elements of OPR, publishing review reports and disclosing reviewer identities have garnered the most attention from researchers. Open review reports are generally well-received, as they enhance scholarly dialogue and accountability. In contrast, identity disclosure has been met with greater scepticism, with concerns about potential bias, reputational risks, and uneven power dynamics.

Align with the NISO standard

The National Information Standards Organization (NISO) has developed comprehensive terminology and frameworks for peer review practices. Their [Standards on Peer Review Terminology](#) offers essential resources to help publishers implement consistent, clearly defined open peer review models that enhance transparency and accessibility across different disciplines and publications.

Beyond open peer review

The primary object of evaluation in open peer review remains, as with traditional peer review, the author's textual description of the research process, results, and findings, accompanied by tables, graphical representations and/or images.

However, open peer review can extend beyond the manuscript itself to include additional research outputs. These may include research data (which plays a crucial role in assessing the validity of research and interpreting results), code, methodological protocols, and preprints, allowing for a more comprehensive evaluation of the complete research process and enhancing reproducibility and transparency in scientific communication.

For more information, you can take a look at the following infographics:

- Open data
- Open protocols
- Open research software

And the course about preprints, repository deposits and self-archiving.

Step 5. Evaluation

Let's test your knowledge and reinforce your understanding of Open Peer Review

This evaluation uses flashcards: each card presents a question for you to consider before revealing the answer, helping solidify your understanding through active recall.

First, we'll cover the basics of open peer review. Then you'll explore and familiarise yourself with the implications of different OPR setups, through short scenarios.

[Key Concepts: A Quick Refresher](#)

What is Open peer review? How does it differ from traditional peer review?

Traditional peer review is typically confidential, while Open Peer Review is an umbrella term for practices that introduce transparency by opening various aspects of the publishing process.

Name the five key configurations of OPR

- Open Identities: Both the author and reviewer know each other's identity (i.e., non-blinded)
- Open Reports: Review reports are published alongside the article.
- Open Participation: The wider community can contribute to the review process.
- Open Interaction: There is direct reciprocal discussion between authors and reviewers, and/or between reviewers
- Open Pre-review Manuscripts: Manuscripts are made public before any formal peer review procedures, either internally as part of journal workflows, or externally via preprints servers.

Name a few ways Open Peer Review can improve traditional peer review

- More transparency and accountability
- More efficient publication process
- Less biases/elitism and conflicts of interest
- Improved error detection
- More consistent, constructive feedback
- Recognition and credit for reviewers
- More collaboration and knowledge sharing

What options should journals offer reviewers in open peer review ?

- Optional identity disclosure
- Choice to publish full/summary reports
- Option for reports to appear with article or in repository

Short scenarios

1. Recto: A journal wants to encourage **early-career researchers** to participate in the peer review process. Which Open Peer Review feature would help?

Open Participation allows anyone to contribute reviews, giving early-career researchers opportunities to gain experience. **Open Reports** can also be inspiring for them, offering insights into the review process.

2. Recto: A journal using **Open Identities** and **Open Reports** notices fewer reviewer acceptances. How can they address this?

Verso: Offer **flexible options**—allow reviewers to remain anonymous while still publishing their reports. This approach balances transparency with privacy, addressing concerns due to public exposure.

3. Recto: A journal is concerned about the **time investment** required for peer review. Which model might offer the quickest turnaround?

Verso: **Open Interaction**: direct communication between authors and reviewers can streamline the feedback process, potentially reducing revision cycles and overall time to publication.

4. Recto: A journal aims to maximise the **recognition given to reviewers** for their contributions. What approach best achieves this?

Verso: **Open Reports with Open Identities**: this combination provides the highest level of visibility for reviewers, allowing them to receive credit and build their reputation within the academic community.

5. Recto: A journal is worried about **authors' reactions to public criticism** with Open Reports. How can this be mitigated?

Verso: Offer it as an opt-in, emphasise constructive feedback, and provide author response options.

6. Recto: A journal using **Open Pre-review Manuscripts** is concerned about the quality of the feedback received. How can they address this?

Verso: Provide structured guidelines, moderate comments, and use a dedicated platform.

Training material 2: Opening the peer review process: a self-reflection tool

Step 1. Introduction

You are the editor of a journal that has traditionally used single or double-blind peer review. The journal is considering moving toward a more transparent peer review process. Your goal is to explore different models and decide which mode would be the best fit for your journal.

This interactive guide will introduce you to different models of open peer review, helping you understand their advantages, challenges, and potential strategies to address those challenges. For each model, you'll have the opportunity to reflect on how it might apply to your specific journal context. On the last page, you can download a blank version of this document to fill out, or download a completed version with your answers.

Step 2. Open identities without open reports

[D4.4 Training report]

The identities of both reviewers and authors are disclosed to each other but review reports are not publicly available.

Advantages

- Reviews are more likely to be thorough, as they are aware that their names are publicly linked to their assessments.
- Reviewers can gain public credit for their work and cite reviews in their academic record.
- Lower risk of undisclosed conflict of interest.

Challenges

- Revealing identities may discourage reviewers from making strong criticisms, especially if they are reviewing senior colleagues' works.
- Reviewers can be biased based on the author's identity, age, gender, affiliation, or career status.
- Journals may lose reviewers who are uncomfortable with revealing their identity.
- The unavailability of review reports can limit the community's ability to evaluate their quality.

Strategies to address challenges

- Provide clear guidelines encouraging reviewers to prioritize constructive criticism and academic integrity.
- Consider a hybrid approach where reviewers can choose to remain anonymous for particularly sensitive cases.
- Invite reviewers with different backgrounds to help reduce bias.

Could you apply this peer-review model in your journal? Does it help overcome the challenges inherent in the peer-review model you're currently using?

Do you face the same challenges? Are there any additional challenges specific to your context?

Would the proposed strategies to address challenges be feasible in your case?

Are there any other strategies that you could use?

[Text box]

Step 2. Open identities with open reports

Both the identities of reviewers and the reports they provide are made publicly available.

Advantages

- Published peer reviews help contextualize the research, offering a deeper understanding of the work.
- Readers can see the questions reviewers raised and how authors addressed them.
- Increased transparency allows the wider community to scrutinize the reviews.
- Reviewers are more likely to provide thorough feedback, knowing their identities and reviews will be published.
- Reviewers can gain academic credit for their work.

- Review reports can be cited.
- Making peer reviews publicly available creates a resource of examples for students to reference as they start engaging in peer review.

Challenges

- Reviewers may hesitate to provide their criticism if they're worried about negative reactions from colleagues or authors.
- Transparency may intensify emotional reactions of authors, especially when giving critical feedback.
- Reviewers can be biased based on the author's identity, age, gender, affiliation, or career status.
- Reviewers and authors may feel uncomfortable knowing their reviews will be publicly available.

Strategies to address challenges

- Recognize and reward reviewers for public reviews through a reviewer credit system.
- Find a suitable way to feature exemplary open reviews (e.g. in blog posts) to showcase the value of transparency.

Could you apply this peer-review model in your journal? Does it help overcome the challenges inherent in the peer-review model you're currently using?

Do you face the same challenges? Are there any additional challenges specific to your context?

Would the proposed strategies to address challenges be feasible in your case?

Are there any other strategies that you could use?

[Text box]

Step 3. Open reports without open identities

Advantages

- Keeping reviewers' identities confidential can help prevent backlash from authors or other reviewers.
- Transparency is maintained by making reports available.
- Making peer reviews publicly available creates a resource of examples for students to reference as they start engaging in peer review.

Challenges

- Readers may not fully appreciate the expertise behind the review if they cannot see the reviewer's identity.

Strategies to address challenges

- Include a brief description of the reviewer's qualifications or expertise at the end of each published review, without revealing their full identity.

[D4.4 Training report]

- Use structured templates for reviews, where reviewers can provide specific sections outlining their qualifications or experience related to the topic under review, without disclosing their full identity.

Could you apply this peer-review model in your journal? Does it help overcome the challenges inherent in the peer-review model you're currently using?

Do you face the same challenges? Are there any additional challenges specific to your context?

Would the proposed strategies to address challenges be feasible in your case?

Are there any other strategies that you could use?

[Text box]

Step 4. Open participation

Members of the wider community are able to contribute to the review process.

Advantages

- Open participation could address issues related to editorial selection of reviewers, such as biases, closed networks, and elitism. For early career researchers who haven't yet been invited to review, these open processes offer an opportunity to build their research reputation and develop their review skills.

Challenges

- The process could become more chaotic and less controlled, with a wide range of reviewers contributing varying levels of expertise.
- The lack of anonymity for reviewers in open identities review could undermine the process by discouraging criticisms, particularly against higher-status colleagues.
- There might be challenges in maintaining the quality and consistency of reviews.
- Technical challenges may be involved, e.g. adjusting the publishing platform to support open participation.

Strategies to address challenges

- Moderation (not displaying comments and reports before checking whether they meet a set of basic criteria).
- Instead of free-text reviews, require reviewers to follow structured criteria (e.g., methodology, clarity, contribution to the field) to maintain consistency.
- Introduce a system where community members or designated experts can upvote or flag reviews based on relevance and quality.

Could you apply this peer-review model in your journal? Does it help overcome the challenges inherent in the peer-review model you're currently using?

Do you face the same challenges? Are there any additional challenges specific to your context?

Would the proposed strategies to address challenges be feasible in your case?

Are there any other strategies that you could use?

[Text box]

Step 5. Open interaction

Transparent dialogue between reviewers and authors

Advantages

- Direct communication between authors and reviewers can lead to a more constructive exchange, clarifications, and improvements in the manuscript and potential collaborations in the future.
- The review process can be more efficient and less time consuming.

Challenges

- Reviewers might hesitate to provide critical feedback, particularly when assessing work from senior colleagues or influential figures.
- Some scholars may be unwilling to review under these conditions, reducing the pool of available reviewers.
- Without clear guidelines, direct communication between reviewers and authors might become confrontational or lead to misunderstanding.

Strategies to address challenges

- Set clear guidelines for constructive feedback.
- Allow optional anonymity in special cases. Consider permitting reviewers to remain anonymous if they feel uncomfortable revealing their identity due to power dynamics or other concerns.
- Use structured response templates to guide interactions and minimize conflicts.
- Collect feedback from authors and reviewers to assess the impact of open interaction on review quality and participation rates.
- Ensure a broad range of reviewers to mitigate bias related to identity, affiliation, and background.

Could you apply this peer-review model in your journal? Does it help overcome the challenges inherent in the peer-review model you're currently using?

Do you face the same challenges? Are there any additional challenges specific to your context?

Would the proposed strategies to address challenges be feasible in your case?

Are there any other strategies that you could use?

[Text box]

Step 6. Open pre-review manuscripts

Manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g. via preprint servers) in advance of formal peer review procedures. This allows the wider research community – not just invited reviewers – to read, comment on, and suggest improvements before the official review process starts.

Advantages

- Authors receive input from a broader audience before formal peer review. This can help them improve their submissions.

[D4.4 Training report]

- Editors and invited reviewers can use pre-review feedback to identify key strengths and weaknesses before formal evaluation.

Challenges

- Feedback may be unstructured and superficial.
- Public reviews may be influenced by the author's identity, leading to bias based on gender, affiliation, or reputation.

Strategies to address challenges

- Allow the submission of manuscripts that have already been publicly shared (e.g. via preprint servers)
- Allow authors to submit pre-review comments alongside formal journal submissions.

Could you apply this peer-review model in your journal? Does it help overcome the challenges inherent in the peer-review model you're currently using?

Do you face the same challenges? Are there any additional challenges specific to your context?

Would the proposed strategies to address challenges be feasible in your case?

Are there any other strategies that you could use?

[Text box]

Export page

Now that you have explored the advantages and challenges of each model of open peer review, reflect on which approach would best suit your journal and write down your reasoning.

7. Editorial quality and management

Details

Subtitle: Elevating standards through clear editorial workflows

Duration: Approximately 30 minutes

Keywords: Editorial, peer review, GDPR, transparency, preservation

Abstract: Learn how to manage the editorial quality of a Diamond Open Access journal by improving the peer-review process and effectively displaying editorial information.

Introduction

Evaluation procedures, often in the form of peer review, play an essential role in maintaining the quality, reliability, and validity of published content.

This course provides practical training to manage the editorial quality of a Diamond Open Access journal. You'll step into the role of a publisher working to improve a journal's peer review process and the editorial information on its website.

In this course, you will learn:

- How to improve a journal's peer review process.

- What main editorial information should be displayed on a journal's website

Glossary

Article Processing Charges (APCs): Fees paid by authors or their institutions to publishers to cover publication costs, allowing articles to be made freely available online without subscription barriers.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC is part of the data protection package adopted in May 2016 aiming at making Europe fit for the digital age. This Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data. (Reference/derivation: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>)

Preprints: Preprints are often defined as complete and public drafts of scientific documents, not yet certified by peer review. However, some authors of preprints do not intend to publish them in a peer-reviewed publication. Additionally, a preprint can be large datasets with descriptions, protocols, (parts of) a thesis, presentations, reports of negative results, commentaries, videos, and more, which do not pass a standard peer review process. A preprint can also be peer-reviewed by a community, by a combination of artificial intelligence with human expert peer review, or by reviewers exclusively. Ambiguities and disagreements around the definition of preprints need to be addressed to offer more precise and less anachronistic terms in such an innovative area. The main purpose of preprints is to disseminate research results to the scientific community, establish ownership of results, and receive feedback from the professional community before submission to a journal. Preprints, "not filtered by their perceived quality or pertinence", can reduce the competitive pressure imposed on researchers and reduce the negative consequences of filtering scholarly information. (Reference/derivation: Stojanovski, J., Marušić, A. (2024). Preprints Are Here to Stay: Is That Good for Science?. In: Eaton, S.E. (eds) Second Handbook of Academic Integrity. Springer International Handbooks of Education. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54144-5_145)

Voluntary Author Contributions (VACs): Optional financial donations made by authors to support open access journals, distinct from mandatory APCs, which help financially support publication while maintaining free submission and publication policies.

Training material 1: Editorial Quality - The peer review process

Evaluation procedures, often in the form of peer review, play an essential role in maintaining the quality, reliability, and validity of published contents.

In this activity, you'll step into the role of a publisher reviewing your journal's annual report, in order to improve its peer review process. You notice some interesting trends in the data - 3 in particular. For each one, choose the most appropriate interpretation and action.

Duration: 5 minutes (3 questions)

[D4.4 Training report]

1. More than half of the article submissions in the past year came from editorial board members.
 - A. It's a good thing! Board members produce high-quality work. No need to change anything.
 - B. It's not necessarily a problem, but it could be a sign of a declining journal reputation, a too-narrow journal scope, etc. You need to investigate further.
 - C. You consider limiting the number of articles from board members to keep authorship diverse and avoid potential bias.

Feedback: C. You're right to be cautious about a high proportion of submissions from board members. DIAMAS recommends limiting the proportion of published articles from editorial team members to 25% per issue to ensure diversity and minimise potential bias. Investigate if there are underlying reasons for the trend.

2. There's a high percentage of reviewers assigned to review manuscripts from their own institutions or by authors with whom they have ongoing collaborations.
 - A. This is likely unavoidable in specialised fields with limited pools of experts. As long as reviewers are subject matter experts, it's acceptable. No changes are needed.
 - B. While some overlap is inevitable, unconscious bias is a concern. You publish an article in your journal's newsletter reminding reviewers about disclosing conflicts of interest.
 - C. This high percentage suggests systemic issues requiring a more robust approach. You diversify your reviewer pool, formalise conflict-of-interest policies (including mandatory disclosures), and train editors on best practices.

Feedback: C. Impartiality and transparency in peer review are crucial for a journal's integrity. Editorial decisions should be made based on the scholarly merits of the submitted manuscript and should not be influenced by other factors such as the origin of the manuscript or business models. Therefore, a robust approach is required.

 - *The selection of peer reviewers should be carried out by the editorial team to ensure that reviewers are experts in the manuscript's subject area who do not have a conflict of interest with the author(s), and have the required expertise to validate research results and distinguish significant contributions.*
 - *All parties involved in the peer review process must declare any potential conflict of interest and avoid reviewing and handling manuscripts that are not suitable to make an objective and fair assessment.*
 - *The IP website should include a range of editorial policies that are easy to find and clearly describe how complaints and appeals regarding allegations of research misconduct will be handled and what the policy is for conflicts of interest.*

3. Many articles were refused because they didn't align with the journal's scope and standards.
 - A. The rejections simply reflect the journal's high standards. No action is needed.
 - B. The journal's standards might be too strict, or scope too narrow. You consider lowering the acceptance criteria and broadening the scope of the journal.

- C. The journal website and author guidelines might lack clarity regarding this information. A thorough review and revision of these resources are necessary to provide authors with clearer information.

Feedback: C. By providing clear and accessible information about the journal's scope and standards through revised author guidelines and a user-friendly website, the journal can reduce the number of misaligned submissions, leading to a lower rejection rate without compromising quality. This approach aligns with DIAMAS principles of transparency and accessibility.

Training material 2: Displaying editorial information

In order to improve how information is presented on your journal website, you compare three other websites with varying approaches.

For each website element, choose the one that you believe demonstrates the most effective approach for editorial quality. This activity focuses on learning through comparison rather than testing knowledge. The examples are designed to help you easily distinguish best practices from less effective approaches.

Duration: 10 minutes (9 questions)

Mission and Scope

A clear mission statement helps potential authors understand the journal's focus and helps readers find relevant research in their field. It's the foundation of your journal's identity.

1. "The journal publishes original research in the field of data science and its interdisciplinary applications."
2. "The journal publishes original research that fosters intellectual discourse across diverse fields of inquiry. We are committed to promoting innovative scholarship and advancing the boundaries of knowledge."
3. The International Journal of Multilingual Studies is a peer-reviewed, open-access journal that publishes research exploring the interplay of language, culture, and society in multilingual contexts. It is intended for researchers, educators, policymakers, and students interested in multilingualism and its implications. We encourage submissions exploring language policy, education, and sociolinguistics in diverse languages and learning contexts.

Correct. This journal clearly articulates its mission, target audience, and scope, providing specific examples of relevant research areas. Other journals provide statements that are either too brief or too vague.

Open Access Policy

A transparent open access policy informs authors about their rights and costs while demonstrating the journal's commitment to knowledge accessibility and broader research impact.

1. (No mention on main pages, but in author guidelines): "Authors retain copyright of their work. This journal is published under a Creative Commons Attribution licence."

[D4.4 Training report]

2. "The journal is committed to open dissemination of research."
3. "We are a diamond open access journal, committed to making research freely available to all. Authors are not charged any publication fees (APCs). The journal's operating costs are covered by the University of Aethelburg."

Correct. As a diamond open access journal, the IP should state explicitly that no mandatory fees are charged to authors. Some journals may choose to offer a Voluntary Author Contribution (VAC) whereby authors with access to institutional funding for open access publishing are given the opportunity to support the journal. It must be clear that there is no obligation to do so.

Author Guidelines

Comprehensive and well-structured author guidelines streamline the submission process, reduce formatting errors, and help ensure that articles meet the journal's standards before review.

1. A long, single-page document with no clear headings or formatting.
2. "Manuscripts should be formatted in a standard academic style. Please follow general scholarly conventions for citations and references."
3. The guideline is organised into clearly labelled sections: Submission Types, Formatting Requirements, References Style, Data Sharing, Ethical Guidelines, etc., with clear explanations and downloadable templates for different article types.

Correct. Author guidelines must be available giving details of the submission process, including the languages in which manuscripts can be submitted, article types accepted, and any formatting requirements, stylesheets or templates to be used. (maybe add Components of Author Guidelines?)

Evaluation Process

A transparent evaluation process builds confidence in the journal's quality standards and helps authors understand how decisions are made about their work.

1. "Manuscripts are reviewed before publication. The editor makes the final decision."
2. "Our publication follows a peer review process where authors and reviewers don't know each other in order to ensure the quality of submissions."
3. "We use a double-blind peer review process. After an initial editorial screening, manuscripts are sent to at least two experts in the field. The review process typically takes 6-8 weeks. Decisions are based on originality, rigour, and significance of the research."

Correct. IPs must provide information about the evaluation procedure undertaken by the publication, including the expected timeframe for the process, who is involved at what stage of the process, how decisions are made and by whom. All submitted articles should undergo a rigorous evaluation process that adheres to best practices in scholarly publishing, and any specific practices followed in the relevant discipline. Evaluation may take place before or after publication, depending on the review model adopted by the IP.

Editorial Policies

Clear editorial policies establish standards for ethical conduct, maintain research integrity, and provide guidance for handling disputes or misconduct, protecting all stakeholders in the publishing process.

1. Not found on the website.
2. A brief paragraph in the author guidelines: "Authors must adhere to ethical standards in research and publication."
3. A dedicated "Editorial Policies" page covering authorship criteria, contributor roles, conflicts of interest disclosure requirements, plagiarism detection processes, data fabrication policies, and complaint procedures, with links to COPE guidelines for further reference.

Correct. The IP website should include a range of editorial policies that are easy to find and clearly describe aspects such as authorship and contributorship, how complaints and appeals regarding allegations of research misconduct will be handled and what the policy is for conflicts of interest. Following industry-standard practices is recommended, such as those provided by COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics).

Data and Archiving

Comprehensive data and archiving policies support research reproducibility, enhance the value of published work, and ensure long-term access to scholarly content.

1. No information provided about data sharing or long-term content preservation.
2. "Authors agree to transfer copyright of their manuscript and all associated data to the journal upon acceptance. The publisher handles archiving."
3. "Authors are encouraged to deposit their research data in OpenData Repository with a permanent DOI. The journal is committed to long-term preservation of published articles through CLOCKSS and Portico digital archives. Authors may share their accepted manuscripts in institutional repositories after a 12-month embargo period."

Correct. The IP should feature policies on its website that address issues such as: text and data mining; whether or not authors can make the content available via open repositories and sharing services; and the archiving and presentation policy for published content.

Infrastructure and Security

Information about technical infrastructure demonstrates professionalism, reassures users about data security, and indicates the journal's commitment to reliable digital publishing practices.

1. No mention of technical infrastructure or security on the website.
2. "We use a reliable online platform for journal management and publication. Our system meets industry standards."
3. "Our publishing platform uses secure servers with SSL encryption, daily backups to multiple geographic locations, and regular security audits. The system complies with

[D4.4 Training report]

WCAG 2.1 accessibility standards and includes disaster recovery protocols to ensure continuous availability. Technical documentation is available for editorial staff."

Correct. IPs should clearly describe how any publishing infrastructure is maintained, backed up and protected from viruses and malware, as well as providing user instructions and documentation for editorial staff.

Accessibility and Clarity of Information

Clear, accessible information helps users understand your journal's policies and builds trust in your publication.

1. Important policies are buried within lengthy "About Us" text, lacking clear headings, formatting, or internal links to guide users.
2. Key details are scattered across various pages, often using inconsistent terminology and requiring users to piece together information from multiple locations.
3. Dedicated pages with clear titles (e.g., "Open Access Policy," "Author Guidelines") are prominently featured in the main navigation. Information is presented concisely, using straightforward language, with clear headings, bullet points, and internal links. A comprehensive site map further enhances discoverability.

Correct. Information should be written clearly and be jargon free. Details of all policies and procedures should be fully described and transparent. Information should be easy to find by including it in relevant menus and cross linking between sections. Getting external help reviewing a website can be useful and help identify areas where transparency could be improved.

Training material 3: Editorial quality - Visual guide

Editorial quality in Diamond Open Access publishing

Providing clear and transparent editorial information on a journal's website ensures the quality and trustworthiness of published research. Here are seven key elements a journal should display to demonstrate its commitment to rigorous evaluation, ethical standards, and publication quality, building trust among authors, readers, and other users:

Mission and scope

- Outline the publication's aims, scope, and target audience.
- State the frequency of publication and ensure publication dates reflect when content is available online.

Open Access Policy

- Declare that the journal is Diamond Open Access (no mandatory fees for authors).
- If Voluntary Author Contributions (VAC) is an option, it must be clear that there is no obligation to do so.

Author Guidelines

Provide clear guidelines on the submission process, including the languages in which manuscripts can be submitted, article types accepted, and any formatting requirements, stylesheets or templates to be used.

Evaluation processes

Describe the peer-review procedure, including: Timeframe and stages of review, who is involved at what stage of the process, and How decisions are made and by whom.

Editorial policies

Clearly outline policies on:

- Authorship and contributorship.
- Handling complaints, appeals, conflicts of interest.
- Allegations of research misconduct.
- Follow industry standards (e.g., COPE guidelines)

Additional policies

Address key issues like:

- Text and data mining permissions.
- Open repositories and content sharing.
- Archiving and preservation of published content.
- Explain how publishing infrastructure is maintained, backed up, and protected.

Tips

- Information should be written clearly and be jargon free.
- All policy and procedure details should be fully described and transparent.
- Information should be easy to find by including it in relevant menus and cross linking between sections.
- External website review can help identify areas for improved transparency.

Training material 4: Editorial management: visual guide

Editorial management in Diamond Open Access publishing

Efficient and ethical publishing in Diamond Open Access relies on well-defined management processes. Here are six key pieces of information a journal website should provide regarding its operational workflows, structural organisation, and administrative policies to ensure smooth functioning:

Clear aims and scope

- Journals need a clear definition of their objectives and subject coverage, and the reason for their existence.
- This guides the editorial team, informs potential contributors and readers, and enhances discoverability through search engines.
- It should be regularly reviewed and updated to ensure relevance

Publishing schedule

- Journals must adhere to a realistic publishing schedule, whether traditional issue-based or continuous.
- Indexing services may not consider a journal for inclusion if it is not publishing on time.

Editorial team

- Roles and responsibilities of editors, editorial board and staff should be clearly defined.
- Editor-in-Chief and editorial board are usually recognized experts who guide the journal's strategy and provide subject expertise.
- Consider including a diverse range of editors to act as ambassadors and reflect the journal's quality.
- Names and affiliations of editorial board members should be publicly available.

Clear author guidelines

- These guidelines should outline criteria for articles (types allowed, submission and layout instructions, any journal-specifics) as well as policies on open access licensing, copyright, author fees, and publication ethics (also applicable to book publishing).

Data protection

- Adhering to data protection regulations like GDPR is essential for both journals and book publishers.
- GDPR aims to ensure transparency and inform EU users, workers, team members, about how your organisation uses, stores, and processes their personal data.
- Privacy notice should outline how your organisation processes personal data.

Digital preservation plan

- A preservation strategy is strongly recommended to safeguard content against loss or disruptions.
- Affordable solutions are available to ensure long-term preservation of journal and book content.

Training material 5: GDPR privacy notice: visual guide

How to write a GDPR privacy notice in Diamond Open Access publishing

If you handle EU residents' data, GDPR applies to you. You need a clear privacy notice explaining how you process and protect their data.

#1 Make it easy to read and understand

Articles 12, 13, and 14 of the GDPR provide guidance on creating these notices, emphasizing clarity and accessibility. Privacy notices should be in plain language, delivered promptly, and provided free of charge.

- Avoid vague qualifiers: may, might, sometimes, often will, always.
- Provide clear, specific explanations: We will retain your personal details → We will retain your name, email address and institution name.
- Write in active tense with well-structured sentences.

- Use a spelling and grammar checker to keep sentences short and clear.

#2 Provide every information required

- The organisation's identity, contact details, and those of its data.
- Protection Officer, if there is one, or the individual responsible for monitoring and implementing the guidelines of the GDPR).
- Purpose and legal basis for data processing.
- Legitimate interests of the organisation or third party.
- Recipients or categories of recipients.
- Details of any data transfers to third countries.
- Retention period or criteria for determining it.
- Details of the data subject's rights.
- Right to withdraw consent.
- Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority.
- Automated decision-making systems, including profiling.
- If data is collected directly from individuals: Whether the provision of personal data is part of a statutory or contractual requirement or obligation and the possible consequences of failing to provide the personal data.
- If data is collected via another organisation or service: The categories of personal data obtained.

#3 Share it

- On your website under the title "Privacy Policy" with a direct link from each page.
- Orally upon request via the Data Protection Officer.

More info Best practices The EU website for GDPR offers a section on best practices for writing a compliant privacy notice, including a template.

8. Research integrity

Details

Subtitle: Fostering ethical practices and responsible publishing

Duration: 45 minutes

Keywords: research integrity, ethics, authorship, misconduct, transparency, responsible research.

Abstract: Uphold research integrity and responsible practices through policies, prevention and effective workflows for addressing misconduct concerns.

Introduction

Diamond Open Access publishing provides a unique opportunity to foster research integrity through transparent and community-driven practices.

This course equips publishers to uphold responsible research and ensure good and reliable publications.

In this course, you will learn:

- Key research integrity concepts and principles.
- How to develop and implement effective research integrity policies.
- Strategies for addressing and managing research integrity concerns.

Glossary

Questionable research practices: A range of activities that intentionally or unintentionally distort data in favour of a researcher's own hypotheses - or omissions in reporting such practices - including; selective inclusion of data, hypothesising after the results are known (HARKing), and p-hacking. Popularized by John et al. (2012). Reference/derivation: <https://forrt.org/glossary/vbeta/questionable-research-practices-or-/>

Research integrity: Research integrity (RI) encompasses a set of principles and practices that ensure researchers conduct their work ethically and with methodological rigour, fostering trust and confidence in the research process and its outcomes. Key elements include honesty, rigour, transparency, accountability, and respect for all participants. These principles should guide researchers at all stages of their work, from conceptualization to dissemination. Upholding research integrity is crucial for maintaining the credibility and reliability of scientific knowledge and fostering a relationship of trust between the research community and society. Various frameworks and guidelines, such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and institutional codes of conduct, provide guidance and standards for maintaining research integrity. Reference/derivation: <https://ukrio.org/research-integrity/>

Research misconduct: Scientific misconduct refers to the violation of standard codes of scholarly conduct and ethical behaviour in the publication of professional scientific research. It constitutes a breach of scientific integrity, encompassing violations of the scientific method and research ethics across the design, conduct, and reporting of research. Examples of scientific misconduct include fabrication (making up results), falsification (manipulating research materials or data), plagiarism (appropriating another person's ideas or words without proper credit), misrepresentation of data, failing to declare or appropriately manage conflicts of interest, and breaching legal, ethical and professional requirements needed for research. Motivations for scientific misconduct may include career pressure, ease of fabrication, and monetary gain. Reference/derivation: <https://ukrio.org/research-integrity/what-is-research-misconduct/>

Responsible research: Responsible Research (RR) is an approach aimed at anticipating and assessing the potential implications and societal expectations regarding research and innovation, with the goal of fostering the design of inclusive and sustainable practices. It involves engaging societal actors in collaborative processes throughout the entire research and innovation lifecycle, from agenda setting to implementation and evaluation, to align outcomes

with societal values and needs. RRI encompasses various dimensions such as governance, ethics, gender equality, open access, citizen participation, and scientific education. The overarching aim of RRI is to ensure that research and innovation are conducted ethically, sustainably, and in a socially desirable manner, thereby promoting creativity and opportunities that benefit society as a whole. Reference/derivation: <https://tetrris.eu/what-is-responsible-research-and-innovation-rri/#>

Training material 1: interactive course

Committing to research integrity in Diamond Open Access publishing

Step 1. Glossary

Research integrity: [as above]

Research misconduct: [as above]

Responsible research: [as above]

Step 2. Introduction

Research integrity involves conducting research ethically and to the highest professional standards, as defined by organisations like Science Europe (2015).

Recent misconduct cases have highlighted the need for a robust research integrity framework to ensure ethical research practices and maintain the credibility and trust in scientific knowledge.

Diamond Open Access publishers have a unique opportunity to shape research culture by actively promoting transparency, openness, and accountability through well-structured policies, educational efforts, and practice-oriented guidance.

This course provides foundational guidance for Diamond Open Access publishers to establish and implement research integrity policies and procedures. It focuses on understanding publishers' specific roles, responsibilities.

Step 3. Definitions - Understanding research integrity.

Let's dive into the basics of research integrity. This first part will explore what we mean by research integrity and responsible research, highlighting the core values that underpin trustworthy science. We'll also look at different types of research misconduct, from the most serious to those that fall into grey areas. You'll learn about these concepts through a series of activities.

Step 4. Activity

Fill in the blanks. Complete the paragraph below by filling in the blanks with the appropriate terms.

Research integrity refers to conducting research in ways that ensure its trustworthiness, validity, and reliability. Although specific standards might vary across disciplines, core principles universally underpin research integrity, including *reliability and rigor* in research performance, *honesty* in all aspects of research, and *transparency and openness* in reporting methods and findings. These principles should guide the

[D4.4 Training report]

responsible conduct of individuals involved in scientific research, including those who perform, finance, or evaluate it, as well as the institutions that publish and disseminate research.

In contrast, ***Responsible Research*** goes beyond simply avoiding misconduct by proactively anticipating the potential societal impacts of research and engaging multiple stakeholders throughout the entire research lifecycle. This approach ensures research aligns with societal values and contributes to addressing global challenges through dimensions such as governance, ethics, gender equality, open access, citizen participation, and scientific education.

While research integrity focuses on maintaining ***standards*** for individual conduct and institutional policies, responsible research emphasises creating ***systems*** that make science more inclusive, sustainable, and beneficial to society as a whole.

While ***Plagiarism*** involves using others' ideas without credit, ***Fabrication*** creates fictional data, and ***Falsification*** manipulates real data to distort results. These three serious violations are commonly abbreviated as FFP and constitute serious misconduct cases. The research community also recognises more subtle breaches known as ***Questionable Research Practices***, which includes various methodological shortcuts and transparency issues that may seem minor individually but collectively damage scientific progress.

Though ***FFP*** violations represent clear ***research misconduct***, ***QRPs*** often occur in ***grey areas*** where researchers might face competing incentives or pressures. Both categories, however, ultimately undermine the reproducibility and trustworthiness of scientific knowledge.

Step 5. Activity

Research integrity is built upon fundamental values that guide ethical research conduct. Try to fill in the blanks with the appropriate terms.

Drag the words. Research integrity is built upon fundamental values that guide ethical research conduct. Match each value with its correct description: [Values and descriptions listed below]

Accountability. Taking responsibility for one's research actions and decisions

Honesty. Being truthful in all aspects of research, from planning to reporting

Fairness. Treating collaborators, participants, and competitors with respect and without bias

Transparency. Being open about methods, data, and findings to enable verification

Step 6. Activity

Which type of research misconduct is it? For each statement, select the appropriate category.

MCQs: Which of these practices are examples of fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, and QRPs?

[correct answers marked with an asterisk]

Making up experimental data that was never actually collected.

*Fabrication

Falsification

Plagiarism

Questionable research practices

Inventing research results to support a hypothesis.

*Fabrication

Falsification

Plagiarism

Questionable research practices

Creating fictional research participants or data points.

*Fabrication

Falsification

Plagiarism

Questionable research practices

Manipulating research images or data to make results look more significant.

*Falsification

Fabrication

Plagiarism

Questionable research practices

Selectively omitting data points that don't support the hypothesis.

*Falsification

Fabrication

Plagiarism

Questionable research practices

Altering research equipment or process records.

*Falsification

Fabrication

Plagiarism

Questionable research practices

Changing raw data to fit a preferred narrative.

*Falsification

Fabrication

Plagiarism

Questionable research practices

Copying text from another source without citation.

*Plagiarism

Falsification

Fabrication

Questionable research practices

Using someone else's ideas or research without acknowledgment.

- *Plagiarism
- Falsification
- Fabrication
- Questionable research practices

Presenting another researcher's work as one's own.

- *Plagiarism
- Falsification
- Fabrication
- Questionable research practices

Translating text from another language without proper attribution.

- *Plagiarism
- Falsification
- Fabrication
- Questionable research practices

P-hacking (repeatedly running statistical tests until finding a significant result).

- *Questionable research practices
- Fabrication
- Falsification
- Plagiarism

HARKing (Hypothesizing After Results are Known).

- *Questionable research practices
- Fabrication
- Falsification
- Plagiarism

Selective reporting of research findings.

- *Questionable research practices
- Fabrication
- Falsification
- Plagiarism

Adding unnecessary authors to a publication.

- *Questionable research practices
- Fabrication
- Falsification
- Plagiarism

Trying different statistical methods to get desired results.

- *Questionable research practices

Fabrication
Falsification
Plagiarism

Not disclosing the use of AI or writing assistance tools.

*Questionable research practices
Fabrication
Falsification
Plagiarism

Misuse of statistical techniques or reporting.

*Questionable research practices
Fabrication
Falsification
Plagiarism

Step 7. Activity

Summary. Select all accurate statements to create a comprehensive overview of what you've learned. [Correct answers marked with an asterisk]

1. * Research integrity refers to conducting research in ways that ensure its trustworthiness, validity, and reliability.
2. Research misconduct only happens because of malicious intent. / Research misconduct requires intentional deception.
3. * Research misconduct consists of fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism (FFP)
4. Peer review alone is sufficient to detect all research misconduct.
5. * Questionable Research Practices (QRPs) are methodological shortcuts and transparency issues that damage scientific progress.
6. Only researchers commit research misconduct and questionable research practices.
7. * Intentional misconduct (FFP) is generally considered more serious than questionable research practices.
8. Research misconduct and questionable research practices are illegal practices.
9. * The same practice may be considered acceptable in one discipline but questionable in another.
10. Responsible research involves following legal regulations more thoroughly than research integrity.
11. * Responsible Research goes beyond avoiding misconduct by anticipating potential societal impacts of research.
12. Research integrity violations only occur in high-profile or high-stakes research.
13. * While research integrity focuses on individual conduct, responsible research emphasises creating inclusive and sustainable systems.
14. Citation counts are reliable indicators of research quality and integrity.
15. * Research integrity involves upholding values across the entire research lifecycle, from planning to publication.

16. Research integrity is the responsibility of researchers only, while responsible research engages everybody.
17. * Research misconduct often stems from systemic pressures, inadequate training, career incentives, and institutional cultures – not just malicious intent.

Learn more about **Questionable research practices** :

<https://ukrio.org/wp-content/uploads/Simon-Kolstoe-Guidance-QRPs-2023.pdf>

Step 8. Research Integrity in Diamond Open Access publishing

Explore the 3 main advantages of Diamond Open Access for promoting research integrity. Flip each card to reveal its description.

Recto: Financial and editorial independence. **Verso:** Editorial independence is a critical aspect of research integrity. Without commercial pressure, publishing decisions can focus on quality and knowledge advancement rather than profit. This reduces the "publish or perish" culture that often drives questionable research practices, as decisions are based solely on scientific merit.

Recto: Community oversight. **Verso:** Research communities typically oversee Diamond OA journals, incorporating diverse perspectives and disciplinary standards. This collective governance ensures integrity standards reflect the needs and values of specific disciplines.

Recto: Transparent editorial processes. **Verso:** Transparent editorial workflows help identify potential integrity issues and build trust in published research. The open nature of these processes reinforces accountability throughout the research communication cycle.

Step 9. The distinct position of publishers

1. Receivers, not originators

Publishers operate at the dissemination phase, while the primary responsibility for research integrity rests with researchers and their institutions. Publishers receive finished research works and must ensure these submissions meet clearly established integrity standards before dissemination.

2. Gatekeepers

While publishers cannot directly control research methods, data collection, or institutional ethics, they significantly influence research integrity practices through clear expectations, verification processes, and transparent decision-making procedures.

3. Promoters of responsible research practices

Encouraging adherence to best practices in data management, authorship, and communication builds a foundation of integrity and strengthens the reliability of published research.

Step 10. Key areas requiring publisher oversight

MCQ: Which of these aspects do you think should be part of a research integrity framework? (Select all that apply)

Authorship and Contributorship

Correct. Publishers should verify proper attribution of meaningful contributions and confirm that listed authors meet qualification criteria.

Website Design and User Interface

Incorrect. While important for accessibility, website design is not directly related to research integrity frameworks.

Research Ethics

Correct. Publishers should ensure compliance with discipline-specific ethical standards, particularly for human and animal research.

Data Integrity

Correct. Publishers should establish clear expectations for data handling, sharing, and verification to promote reproducibility.

Marketing and Promotion Strategies

Incorrect. Marketing strategies are important for journal visibility but not directly related to research integrity.

AI and Technology Use

Correct. Publishers should provide guidance on appropriate use of AI tools and require disclosure of technological assistance.

Conflict of Interest

Correct. Publishers should implement disclosure requirements and mitigation processes regarding relationships that could influence research.

Misconduct Prevention and Response

Correct. Publishers should develop clear procedures for addressing integrity concerns, including investigation protocols.

Social Media Engagement

Incorrect. While important for dissemination, social media strategies are not directly related to research integrity frameworks.

Corrections and Retractions

Correct. Publishers should maintain transparent processes for addressing post-publication issues with clear documentation.

Step 11.- Good practices

While addressing research misconduct is essential, publishers can make their most significant impact through preventive measures that foster transparency, accountability, and quality. The most effective practices are often embedded in everyday publishing workflows, with many aligning closely with Diamond Open Access principles that prioritise open knowledge sharing, community governance, and equitable participation in scholarly communication. This chapter explores some of these aspects.

Practice transparency in journal policies and practices

Openness is fundamental to scholarly communication and directly translates into best publishing practices. Publishers should focus on:

- Maintaining up-to-date author instructions and ethical policies
- Promptly communicating retractions, corrections, and reasons for them

[D4.4 Training report]

- Providing for post-publication review and commentary
- Disclosing funding sources and any potential conflicts of interest to maintain transparency and trust.

Require openness from authors and reviewers through open science practices.

Journals are in a powerful position to encourage researchers to :

- Share datasets, code, and methodological protocols openly. Cf Course.
- Publish preprints and preregistration of studies where relevant. Cf Course.
- Report negative or null findings transparently. Cf Course.
- Consider opening different aspects of the peer review process

By linking Open Science explicitly to research integrity, publishers enhance transparency, accountability, and trust in published research.

Provide education and guidance to researchers/authors, editor staff (?) and reviewers

Many questionable research practices come from a lack of information and guidance on responsible research practices. Some writers, reviewers, and editors may lack the necessary training to play their roles effectively. This can be addressed through training and guidance :

- Ensure editors are well informed about responsible publishing practices, requirements that need to be communicated to authors and reviewers, and what to do if problems arise.
- Ensure that authors, reviewers and editor staff have the necessary training to play their roles effectively, including aspects such as responsible writing, reviewing, and editing.

Collaborate with other publishers

While maintaining your editorial independence to create policies suited to your own situation, consider engaging in collaborative initiatives with other publishers.

Journals benefit from working with other journals to develop common approaches and tools to foster research integrity. This could involve sharing best practices and developing shared resources and tools for addressing integrity issues. It could also be very useful to pool training resources, as journals vary widely in their capacity to develop and implement educational programs.

Such collaboration can contribute to improving research integrity standards and practices in Diamond Open Access publishing.

Article

To delve deeper into this topic, we encourage you to explore the National Library of Medicine's article, '[Identifying and Promoting Best Practices for Research Integrity](#)', which offers insights into fostering integrity within the research landscape. The article frames best practices and discusses the roles of various stakeholders in upholding research integrity – researchers, research institutions, journals and other scholarly communicators, research sponsors and users of research results, societies.

Step 12. Research integrity policies.

A foundational research integrity policy should address the following key areas:

Research and Publication Ethics

Guarantee that the journals adhere to international standards and codes of ethics – such as COPE Code of Conduct, Declaration of Helsinki (human research), ARRIVE guidelines (animal research) – or have their own publicly accessible code of ethics. Outline expectations for ethical data handling, including confidentiality and security.

Conflict of Interest

Ensure consistent workflows requiring authors, editors, and reviewers to disclose both general and financial conflicts of interest, or explicitly state the absence thereof in a Conflict-of-Interest statement.

Clearly define what constitutes a conflict of interest.

Require all authors, reviewers, and editors to disclose potential conflicts. You can include standardised conflict of interest declaration forms in submission processes.

To manage conflicts of interest, researchers and author should :

- Disclosure: Always disclose any personal, financial, or professional conflicts that could influence your research
- Editorial Policies: Adhere to the editorial policies of journals regarding conflicts of interest
- Recusal: From the review process or decision-making in cases where a conflict exists
- Transparency: Ensure all conflicts are transparently communicated in publications and peer review processes

Outline procedures for managing conflicts during peer review and editorial decision-making, and explain how declared conflicts are evaluated and managed by the editorial team.

Misconduct

Establish a comprehensive policy addressing research misconduct.

Define research misconduct (fabrication, falsification, plagiarism) and questionable research practices (QRPs).

Provide clear instructions for reporting potential misconduct confidentially. Anyone who might detect misconduct should report it when:

- There is evidence: Credible evidence of misconduct such as fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism
- Following Institutional Guidelines: Follow the procedures outlined by the host institution or publisher. Typically, this involves reporting to a designated research integrity officer or committee.

Establish clear criteria and procedures to report, investigate, and resolve allegations

Clarify roles and responsibilities within the editorial team and external parties.

[D4.4 Training report]

Define circumstances under which retractions or corrections should occur (e.g., significant errors impacting conclusions, proven misconduct). You can provide templates for public correction or retraction notices to maintain consistency.

Step 13. Guidelines for Authorship and Contributorship

Many issues such as plagiarism, honorary authorship, unacknowledged ghost authorship, and authorship disputes represent serious challenges to research integrity. Clear attribution establishes both credit and responsibility, which becomes increasingly important with collaborative research.

Provide authorship and contributorship guidance that respects the norms of relevant research disciplines and/or recognised standards (e.g., CRediT Taxonomy).

Ensure your guidelines clearly define who qualifies as an author and what constitutes a contribution. Inform authors that contributions deserving authorship include not only the writing but also activities related to the conceptualisation and execution of the research, collection and production of research data/materials, and analysis and interpretation of results.

Encourage researchers to reach an agreement on how these diverse contributions will be acknowledged before manuscript submission, ideally early in the research process. As a publisher, you play a vital role in supporting good communication among all parties involved in the research to prevent or resolve possible disputes and authorship manipulation.

Ideally, reinforce the value of transparency by publishing the specific contributions of each researcher and collaborator within the journal article itself.

For more information, see the course about copyright, authors' rights and licences ([url](#)).

Step 14. Guidelines for Artificial Intelligence

Publishers are encouraged to develop guidelines on generative AI tools that respect changes in the research process in a technology-enhanced environment. These guidelines should inform and educate researchers/authors, reviewers, and editors about the responsible use of generative AI tools.

Principles

Effective research integrity policies should be:

- Written in clear, understandable language
- Linked to recognised international standards – providing credibility and consistency.
- Clearly displayed on the publisher's website and consistently applied across all journals published
- Actionable and enforceable with clear expectations, procedures, and consequences.

Policy templates [here](#).

Step 15. - Editorial decision workflow

Ensure accountability and documentation: They should also be careful to document all steps taken throughout the process. Maintain clear and auditable records of editorial decisions, misconduct investigations, and corrective actions taken. This ensures accountability, consistency, and defensibility of your integrity practices.

Step-by-step instructions

1. Report

The process begins when a concern about research integrity is raised:

- Concerns may be reported by readers, reviewers, editors, authors, or whistleblowers
- Reports should be directed to a designated individual (e.g., editor-in-chief or research integrity officer)
- Initial documentation should include the nature of the concern, the article in question, and any supporting evidence
- Maintain confidentiality of the reporter's identity when appropriate
- Acknowledge receipt of the report promptly

2. Initial Investigation

Upon receiving a report, publishers should conduct a preliminary assessment to determine if it warrants formal investigation.

Positive direction:

- Concern appears to be a misunderstanding rather than misconduct
- Issue can be resolved through minor corrections or clarifications
- Limited scope of potential impact
- No evidence of intentional deception

Negative direction:

- Evidence suggests potential fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism
- Concern involves multiple publications or extensive portions of work
- Pattern of questionable practices is identified
- Initial evidence suggests intentional misconduct

Based on this assessment, determine whether to:

- Dismiss the concern as unfounded
- Address the issue through minor corrections
- Proceed with a more thorough investigation
- Refer the matter to the authors' institution if serious misconduct is suspected

3. Gather Evidence

If further investigation is warranted:

- Gather and review preliminary evidence before taking any formal action (e.g., source data, lab notebooks, previous publications)
- Request additional information from authors when needed
- Consider seeking input from subject matter experts not involved in the original peer review/Consult with subject matter experts when specialised knowledge is required

[D4.4 Training report]

- For technical issues (e.g., image manipulation), use appropriate analytical tools
- Document all findings systematically
- Maintain objectivity and fairness throughout the evidence-gathering process

4. Communication Protocol

Clear communication is essential throughout the process:

- Inform authors about the concern in a neutral, non-accusatory manner
- Provide authors with specific details about the issues identified
- Allow reasonable time for authors to respond and provide explanations
- Maintain professionalism and respect in all communications
- Keep records of all correspondence
- For serious concerns, consider informing relevant institutions or funding bodies
- Ensure communications follow a consistent format and tone

5. Feedback Loop

Establish a structured review of the evidence and responses:

- Convene a panel of appropriate editors and experts to review all materials
- Evaluate author responses against the evidence gathered
- Consider whether additional information or clarification is needed
- Return to previous steps if necessary to obtain more information
- Document the decision-making process and rationale
- Ensure decisions are consistent with established policies and precedents
- Consider whether additional publications by the same authors should be examined

6. Resolution

Conclude the process with clear outcomes:

- **No further action:** If investigation determines the concern was unfounded
- **Correction:** For minor errors that don't affect the validity of findings
- **Expression of concern:** When investigation is ongoing but readers should be alerted
- **Retraction:** For serious cases of misconduct or irreparable errors
- **Referral:** Forward to institutional authorities or funding bodies for further investigation

For any resolution involving published content:

- Provide clear reasons for the action taken
- Place notices prominently in the position of the original article
- Include notices in tables of contents
- Ensure metadata is properly updated to reflect the article's status
- Maintain transparency about the nature of the problem and resolution

7. Follow-up Procedures

After resolution:

- Document lessons learned from the case
- Consider whether policies or procedures need to be updated
- Implement preventive measures to reduce similar occurrences
- Provide education or guidance to editorial staff based on the case
- Review similar articles if a pattern of issues has been identified

Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)

As you implement research integrity workflows, the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) provides valuable materials to support ethical publishing practices at <https://publicationethics.org/>, including:

- A mandatory code of conduct for journal editors
- An aspirational set of best practices
- Numerous guidelines and monographs addressing specific research integrity issues

We recommend exploring these COPE flowcharts that align with the editorial decision process discussed in this chapter:

1. Plagiarism in Submitted Manuscripts : <https://publicationethics.org/guidance/flowchart/plagiarism-submitted-manuscript>
2. Inappropriate Image Manipulation : <https://publicationethics.org/guidance/Flowchart/inappropriate-image-manipulation-published-article>
3. Concurrent Submissions : <https://publicationethics.org/guidance/Flowchart/concurrent-submissions-manuscript-multiple-journals>

Step 16. Activity

Now, test your understanding by completing this drag-and-drop exercise. The flowchart below shows how to handle concerns about scientific rigour in datasets prior to publication. These concerns might involve errors, incomplete information, or potential data manipulation. Arrange the steps in their appropriate sequence in the flowchart.

For the complete guideline and detailed flowchart, visit:

<https://publicationethics.org/guidance/flowchart/scientific-rigour-unpublished-data-dealing-concerns>

Step 17. Conclusion

Congratulations on completing this course. You now understand the basics of research integrity and how to apply them in Diamond Open Access publishing.

Research integrity is achieved not solely through individual researchers' integrity but through the integrity of the entire system, including researchers, institutions, funding agencies, journals,

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societies, and other participants whose practices and incentives interact to either support or undermine integrity.

For Diamond Open Access publishers, three key practices guide everything: transparent policies, active promotion of open science, and ongoing education.

To start implementing what you've learned, you can begin with one policy or practice, then build from there.

The frameworks, policies, and procedures outlined in this course provide a solid foundation, but research integrity is an evolving field. Stay engaged with organisations like COPE, continue learning about emerging challenges such as AI in research, and collaborate with other publishers to strengthen integrity standards across the scholarly publishing ecosystem.

9. Choosing a software

Details

Subtitle: Finding the right publishing platform for your needs

Duration: Approximately 45 minutes

Keywords: Platform, software, SaaS, interoperability.

Abstract: Learn how to evaluate and select publishing platforms for Diamond OA journals by comparing software options, hosting models, and key features aligned with the DOAS.

Introduction

In Diamond Open Access Publishing, choosing a publishing platform requires careful evaluation of multiple factors.

Whether you're a publisher, service provider, journal editor, or you're involved in supporting publishing infrastructure, this course is designed to help you make decisions towards choosing the right option for a platform compliant with the DOAS. This course is also useful for librarians and trainers supporting publishing activities.

In this course, you will learn:

- How to assess your publishing needs and workflows.
- What to look for in platform features and hosting models.
- How to align your platform choice with Diamond OA values and standards.

Self-reflection guide: This document guides you through a structured evaluation of your current workflow and helps you assess various platform options, whether self-hosted or SaaS. Use it to analyse your current setup, explore potential solutions, and choose a platform that optimizes your publishing process.

Glossary

File format: A file format is a standard way of encoding information so that it can be stored in a computer file. It defines the structure and type of data that the file contains: how information is

organised, encoded, and represented. Thanks to this, the data stored in files can be consistently interpreted, accessed, and processed by software applications. File formats widely used in the context of scholarly publishing include:

- PDF (Portable Document Format)
- EPUB (Electronic Publication)
- HTML (Hypertext Markup Language)
- XML JATS (Journal Article Tag Suite)
- DOCX (Microsoft Word Open XML Document)
- LaTeX (Document Preparation System)
- CSV (Comma-Separated Values)

Reference/derivation: <https://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/appendices/file-formats/>

Free and open-source software: Free and open-source software (FOSS) is software available under a licence that grants the right to use, modify, and distribute the software, modified or not, to everyone free of charge, as opposed to proprietary software, where the restrictive copyright or licensing is used and the source code is not available to users. Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Free_and_open-source_software

Interoperability: Interoperability is the ability of different systems, devices, or software to communicate, exchange data, interact and work together smoothly and efficiently. It involves the establishment of common standards, protocols, and interfaces to facilitate smooth communication among systems.

Metadata: Metadata provides information about data. Specifically, it is machine-readable data that describes content, context and structure of resources and their management over time. In the context of scholarly publishing, metadata are pieces of information that describe published outputs (articles, books, journals, etc.).

Training material 1: Interactive course

Step 1. Choosing a publishing platform

A journal publishing platform is a digital service that allows publishers to manage the publication process from manuscript submission to content publication and distribution on the web. In Diamond Open Access Publishing, choosing a publishing platform requires careful evaluation of multiple factors.

Whether you're a publisher, service provider, journal editor, or involved in supporting publishing infrastructure and training, this course is designed to help you make decisions towards choosing the right option for a Diamond Open Access (DOAS) compliant platform.

To help you put this knowledge into action, we've prepared a checklist alongside this course to guide you through assessing your current publishing setup and evaluating potential new platforms.

Step 2. Essential features of a publishing platform

The effectiveness of an OA publishing platform hinges on multiple factors, including back-end workflow management, front-end user experience, and robust technical solutions. Understanding these elements is essential for making an informed choice.

The back-end (or back office) of a platform is where the behind-the-scenes management happens. Not publicly visible and accessed via a login form, it's where different versions of the submitted manuscripts, review reports, and correspondence are saved, and where metadata is created.

The following screenshot illustrates the platform's back-end interface. Note how it facilitates workflow management for different user roles (e.g., Journal Manager, Author, Reviewer).

[image]

The front-end is the public-facing website that human readers and machines interact with. It focuses on content presentation, discoverability and user experience.

The following screenshot shows a journal's frontend. Focus on the navigation structure, the presentation of the table of contents, the search functionality, and the overall design. These elements directly impact user experience and discoverability.

[image]

Step 3. Key considerations when choosing a publishing platform

Selecting the right publishing platform involves evaluating several crucial aspects. A robust platform effectively balances back-end efficiency, front-end usability, security, and machine-readable metadata. Let's explore these key areas.

Management of publishing workflow

An effective publishing platform should enable efficient management of the entire publication process, including:

- Streamlined content submission and tracking
- Easy communication between editors, authors, reviewers and the community
- Coordinated production operations (copyediting, typesetting, metadata production, etc.)

If you already have a platform, how does it handle the publication workflow, from submission to publication? You can refer to the first question of the course checklist to start evaluating your own situation.

User friendly website

The website should provide seamless access to published content through a user-friendly interface. That is:

- Easy to navigate: Straightforward and easy navigation within articles, as well as between articles and journals is enabled via a table of contents, menus, links and a search functionality.
- Responsive: The interface is designed to adjust automatically to the browser space, ensuring consistent content display across all devices, and suitable for various bandwidths.

- Informative: All relevant information is clearly displayed and easy to find. The platform should publicly display information about the publisher and the journals it hosts. The metadata describing each article is displayed on a dedicated page (article landing page) that can also contain the full text in the HTML format and/or a link to the full text in other formats (e.g. PDF, ePub, etc.).
- Accessible: The interface should be designed and coded to ensure that everyone, including people with disabilities, can access and understand its content either independently or with the help of assistive technologies.

Machine-readable metadata

Machine-readable metadata is essential for making your publications easily discoverable through search engines and aggregators such as Google, Google Scholar, OpenAIRE, CORE, BASE, etc. This is why your platform should offer robust metadata capabilities.

Metadata should be accessible via standard protocols for metadata exchange : Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH), REST API, HTTPS, etc.

It should be possible to export it in standard content description formats. Widely adopted metadata schemas include: Dublin Core, DataCite, Crossref, JATS XML, etc. Most journal management systems support these features. Make sure with your IT support and/or service providers that they are set up correctly.

For a deeper dive into metadata in Diamond Open Access publishing, consider exploring our dedicated course.

Security

Beyond workflow and user interface, your platform should be secure, regularly updated, and protected against data breaches.

When choosing a platform, make sure that standard security and backup procedures are included in any IT support agreements and/or service provision agreements, and that all these security features are addressed:

A secure server environment: it runs on a regularly updated server with firewall protection and intrusion detection/prevention systems to block unauthorized access. Ensure your IT support agreement covers regular security updates and patching of the server environment.

A secure files directory: it protects private files like unpublished submissions from unauthorized access through strict permissions and encryption.

A secure email communication: it uses a dedicated SMTP server with correctly configured SPF and DMARC records to prevent spoofing, and it requires validation of the email addresses for all new user accounts.

Encrypted web traffic: it used a SSL certificate to protect all data transmitted between users' browsers and the platform, safeguarding against eavesdropping and data breaches.

Step 4. Options for your publishing platform

In order to make the right decision, you should consider the pros and cons of these options:

- a. Platforms based on specialised free and open-source software (FOSS)
 - Software is free to download and installed on a server.

[D4.4 Training report]

- Developed by dedicated non-profit organisations and supported by a wide community of users and developers.
- Customisable open-source code.
- Out-of-the-box functionalities supporting the management of all processes from submission to publication. Yet, some features may be missing.
- Free plugins.
- Installation and maintenance support is needed.
- Lock-in risk (see glossary) for journal management data (e.g. correspondence).

Examples: [Open Journal Systems](#), [Janeway](#), [Kotahi](#)

b. **Platforms based on proprietary software aligned with accepted standards**

- Ready-to-use solutions with necessary features.
- Limited customisation (possible at a fee).
- Metadata and management process data (including peer review correspondence) are not available for export.

c. **Small-scale custom builds**

- Tailored solutions
- The risk of non-compliance with standards
- Poor interoperability.
- Maintenance risks.
- Vendor lock-in risk (see glossary)

d. **Adjustments of commonly used Content Management Systems (CMS)**

Limited functionalities and interoperability: major customisation needed for full workflow support (beyond content display) and metadata handling.

Examples: WordPress, Joomla, Drupal

To guide your evaluation, refer to the first question of the provided checklist, which addresses these platform options in detail.

Step 5. The most popular FOSS solutions.

Diamond OA publishers and service providers should strive to build the infrastructure on free and open-source software, with publicly accessible code. This approach promotes interoperability, knowledge sharing, and collaboration among publishers, while also enabling them to maintain technical independence and flexibility, avoid vendor lock-in, and adapt development to their specific needs. Here are some notable examples of FOSS journal management software.

a. **Open Journal Systems (OJS)**

Open Journal Systems (OJS) is a free and open-source platform designed to support open-access, peer-reviewed academic publishing by providing infrastructure for editorial management workflows (submission, peer review, and indexing) and article display. OJS supports different user roles (e.g. journal manager, editor, reviewer, author, and reader). It has

a plugin architecture, allowing integration of new features (e.g. indexing in Google Scholar, usage statistics, and archiving via LOCKSS) without altering its core.

Software provider: Public Knowledge Project (PKP)

Website: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs>

Programming language: PHP

Licence: GNU General Public License

Documentation and training materials: <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/>

Demo: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/software/ojs/demo/>

Notable examples: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/software/ojs/usage-data/>

b. Kotahi

Kotahi is a flexible and customizable platform created to support the requirements of Publish-Review-Curate (publishing a preprint, community review, validation) workflows and emerging scholar-led publishing models. XML JATS production is seamlessly integrated into the publishing workflow

Software provider: Coko Foundation

Website: <https://kotahi.community/>

Programming language: JavaScript

Licence: MIT licence

Documentation: <https://gitlab.coko.foundation/kotahi/kotahi>

c. Lodel

Lodel is a Content Management System (CMS) created in to support complex, structured editorial workflows, especially in humanities and social sciences. It is used on the OpenEdition Journals and Books platforms.

Software provider: OpenEdition

Website: <https://lodel.hypotheses.org/>

Programming language: PHP

Licence: [GNU General Public License, version 2](#)

Documentation (mostly in French): <https://lodel.hypotheses.org/documentation>

Notable examples: <https://lodel.hypotheses.org/ils-se-servent-de-lodel-hors-openedition>

d. Janeway

Janeway is a free, open-source publishing platform offering tools for journal and preprint management. It supports editorial management workflows (submission, peer review, and indexing). Customization is possible through plugins.

Software provider: Centre for Technology and Publishing at Birkbeck, University of London

Website: <https://janeway.systems/>

Programming language: Python (Django)

Licence: AGPL

Documentation: https://janeway.systems/support_and_docs

Notable examples: Open Library of Humanities

To guide your evaluation, refer to questions 4 and 5 of the provided checklist, which address this subject in detail.

Step 6. Hosting options

Choosing the right hosting option is crucial for accessibility and long-term sustainability. Consider the pros and cons of independent journal platforms and Software as a Service (SaaS) solution.

Independent Journal platform

Independent journal platforms offer full control and customisation, but it requires technical expertise and ongoing management and maintenance.

Choosing this type of software requires careful consideration of several key factors:

- Evaluate your technical and financial capacities.
- Determine availability and costs of technical support.
- Ensure capability for regular updates and backups.
- Confirm ability to manage editorial processes adequately.

Software as a Service (SaaS)

SaaS platforms require minimal technical skills with managed security and regular updates, but customization is limited, and data migration can be a concern.

Choosing this type of software requires careful consideration of several key factors:

- Features: Does it cover all publishing needs?
- Digital preservation: Does the provider ensure sustainable digital preservation?
- Documentation and support: Are comprehensive guides available?
- Customisation options: Is it possible to customise the SaaS platform? Under what conditions (e.g. you can do it yourself or the provider can do this for a fee)?
- Vendor lock-in risk: Can you change the platform providers without data loss or having to pay a high fee?

To guide your evaluation, refer to questions 4 and 5 of the provided checklist, which address this subject in detail.

Step 7. Embrace openness and collaboration.

Diamond open access publishers are part of a dynamic ecosystem where openness extends beyond making scholarly content freely available.

We encourage you to actively contribute to the sustainability of free and open-source software. Your participation in community initiatives can also help strengthen the broader community and foster a more resilient and interconnected publishing landscape.

Software: Publishers should strive to use free and open-source software as much as possible in their editorial and publishing workflows. To support Diamond OA publishing, in some countries shared infrastructures based on free and open-source software are maintained at the national level and offered to institutional publishers on the software-as-a-service basis free of charge (e.g. HRČAK in Croatia, ePublishing EKT in Greece, Openjournals.nl in the Netherlands, PubIN in Portugal, Recyt in Spain, Online Scholarly Journals in Finland etc.). Many universities around the world offer similar platforms to their journals.

Collaboration. Institutional publishers and service providers should contribute to the community efforts whenever possible, by sharing the code of any new plugins they may have developed. Some FOSS solutions are designed and maintained by non-profit organisations and communities who seek to provide sufficient documentation and support knowledge exchange through forum discussions. Engage in the development community by contributing bugs detected, translations into local languages, documentation, bug fixing or developments to promote collective growth.

Metadata sharing. Metadata sharing policies should include distribution of all metadata under the CC0 licence and permission for text and data mining. For a deeper dive into metadata in Diamond Open Access publishing, consider exploring [our dedicated course](#).

Step 8. Knowledge check

This short quiz contains 8 questions. Take your time, and don't hesitate to try different options where you have doubts. Each option will provide feedback explaining why it's correct or incorrect, giving you another chance to understand the topic.

1. [What part of a publishing platform is accessed through a login form and manages tasks like manuscript submission, review reports, and correspondence?](#)
 - a) Front end: **Incorrect.** The front end is the public-facing part of the website.
 - b) Home page: **Incorrect.** The home page is part of the front end and doesn't require a login.
 - c) Back end (or back office): **Correct.** The back end is the administrative area accessed through a login.
 - d) Article landing page: **Incorrect.** This is a public page displaying a specific article.

Correct Answer: c. Back end (or back office)
2. [Which key feature ensures consistent content display across various devices and screen sizes?](#)
 - a. Metadata schemas
 - b. Interoperability protocols
 - c. Responsive interface
 - d. Security updates

Correct Answer: c. Responsive interface

[D4.4 Training report]

A responsive interface is crucial for a publishing platform because it:

- a) Ensures content displays correctly on various devices.: Correct. Responsiveness adapts the display for optimal viewing.
- b) Improves the platform's search engine optimization.: Incorrect. While related, responsiveness is primarily about display, not SEO.
- c) Protects against unauthorized access.: Incorrect. Security is a separate concern from responsive design.
- d) Ensures consistent application of metadata schemas.: Incorrect. Metadata schemas are for content description and organization, not display formatting. Responsive design focuses on how content adapts to different screen sizes, not how it's described.

3. Why should publishing platforms support widely adopted metadata schemas and metadata exchange protocols?

- a. To prevent unauthorised access to articles
- b. To enable seamless integration with aggregators and search engines and ensure better visibility of the published content
- c. To reduce the size of published articles
- d. To enhance visual design

Correct Answer: b. To enable seamless integration with aggregators and search engines and ensure better visibility of the published content

3. Supporting widely adopted metadata schemas and exchange protocols is important for publishing platforms to:

- a) Enhance data security.: **Incorrect.** Metadata describes data; security measures protect it.
- b) Improve discoverability by search engines and aggregators.: **Correct.** Standard metadata enables seamless integration with aggregators and search engines and ensure better visibility of the published content.
- c) Reduce file sizes of publications.: **Incorrect.** Metadata adds information, increasing file size, although often negligibly.
- d) Create a visually appealing website.: **Incorrect.** Visual design is separate from metadata functionality. Metadata helps organize and describe content, not how it looks.

4. Which statement correctly describes a key feature of free and open-source publishing software?

- a) It is owned by commercial publishers: **Incorrect.** Open-source software is typically community-owned and developed.
- b) Its code is open and can be freely used and customized: **Correct.** This is the defining characteristic of open-source software.
- c) It requires paid subscriptions for installation: **Incorrect.** Open-source software is free to install, though support might be paid.
- d) It can be used free of charge but customizations are not allowed: **Incorrect.** Customization is a key benefit of open source.

5. What is a potential disadvantage of using proprietary software for journal publishing?

- a) No technical support is provided: **Incorrect**. Proprietary software often comes with vendor support, though it may be paid.
- b) The vendor lock-in risk is involved: **Correct**. Switching from proprietary systems can be difficult and costly. Provide the definition of "Vendor lock-in risk" in the feedback + as a clue
- c) It is usually incompatible with common metadata standards: **Incorrect**. While possible, most proprietary software aims for compatibility.
- d) It lacks any ready-to-use functionalities: **Incorrect**. Proprietary software typically provides a suite of features.
6. Which requirements should a good scholarly publishing platform meet? (Select all that apply)
- The platform offers the necessary features and supports the full publishing workflow: **Correct**. Essential for efficient operation.
- The software is regularly updated and well-documented: **Correct**. Ensures security, functionality, and ease of use.
- Demos, tutorials, or guides are available: **Correct**. Important for training and user adoption.
- The platform is provided by a major commercial publisher: **Incorrect**. Not a requirement; open-source and smaller vendors are viable.
- There are no maintenance costs after the initial set-up: **Incorrect**. All platforms require ongoing maintenance and updates.
- Integration with key infrastructures (e.g., ORCID, Crossref) is supported: **Correct**. Essential for discoverability and interoperability.
- The platform supports automated content preservation and allows for easy migration: **Correct**. Crucial for long-term access and flexibility.
7. How can you reduce the risk of vendor lock-in when selecting a publishing platform? (Select all that apply)
- Use the services of a well-known commercial service provider.: **Incorrect**. Large vendors can sometimes increase lock-in.
- Verify that the platform does not use incompatible and proprietary data formats.: **Correct**. Ensures data portability.
- Confirm the platform supports seamless data migration.: **Correct**. Makes switching providers easier.
- Ensure that there are no high fees or complex processes for migrating data.: **Correct**. Reduces the cost and difficulty of switching.
- Make sure that you have stable funding to continue using the platform.: **Incorrect**. Funding is important, but doesn't prevent lock-in.
8. Which of the following statements accurately describe the Software as a Service (SaaS) model in the context of scholarly publishing? Select all that apply.
- SaaS platforms allow users to download and install software on their own servers.: **Incorrect**. SaaS is accessed online, not locally installed.

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- Although users usually pay for access to the software through a subscription model, some SaaS platforms are available free of charge.: **Correct**. While often subscription-based, free/open-source SaaS options exist.
- SaaS solutions often include ongoing maintenance and updates managed by the service provider.: **Incorrect**
- SaaS platforms can be customized without any limitations or additional costs.: **Incorrect**. Customization options and costs vary by provider.
- Users are responsible for all technical support and troubleshooting without assistance from the provider.: **Incorrect**. SaaS providers typically offer support.

Correct: Although users usually pay for access to the software through a subscription model, some SaaS platforms are available free of charge and SaaS solutions often include ongoing maintenance and updates managed by the service provider.

Step 9. Conclusion

This concludes the course on choosing a publishing platform.

You now have a solid foundation for evaluating different platforms and making informed decisions aligned with Diamond Open Access principles.

To help you put this knowledge into action, you can use the [checklist](#) to guide you through assessing your current publishing setup and evaluating potential new platforms. This checklist is available as separate resources alongside this course. You can edit it and use it whenever you need.

The Documentation section of the toolsuite article provides valuable resources for further insights into technical infrastructure, platform selection, and software evaluation.

If you're interested in delving deeper into metadata, we recommend to follow [the related course](#), as it covers important aspects of metadata management relevant to choosing appropriate journal software.

We also recommend exploring [the infographic](#) on Digital Preservation for a visual overview of key archiving strategies, which is crucial for evaluating software platforms based on their preservation capabilities.

Training material 2: visual guide

Checklist - Choosing a journal publishing platform

This checklist guides you through a structured evaluation of your current workflow and helps you assess various platform options, whether self-hosted or SaaS. Use it to analyse your current setup, explore potential solutions, and choose a platform that optimises your publishing process.

1. [How my platform handles the publication workflow, from submission to publication:](#)
 - It supports the management of all processes from submission to publication. Great! You're ready to handle the publishing process efficiently.

- It could support the management of all processes from submission to publication but we don't use these options. Managing the entire publishing process with a journal management system would make it easier for you to handle documentation – manuscripts, reviews and correspondence – and to archive what needs to be preserved, preventing data and documentation loss.
- It can only display content. Consider changing or upgrading the publication platform.
- We don't have an independent website. Journal volumes are uploaded to the publisher's website. Consider using an online publishing infrastructure supporting workflows from manuscript submission, through peer review, to content display. That will enable more efficient journal management and ensure better discoverability.

2 · My publishing platform is:

- A shared platform based on free and open-source software managed by a university / national body / non-profit organisation.
- Based on free and open-source software managed by our publishing team.
- Based on free and open-source software managed by a commercial service provider.
- Based on a widely used CMS content management systems like Wordpress, Joomla or Drupal.
- Based on proprietary software and offered by a commercial service provider.
- A custom-made platform developed by an IT expert.
- We don't have a publishing platform.
- I don't know.

3 · I already have a platform, and

- The platform offers all the features I need. It supports the entire scholarly publishing workflow from submission to publication. If not, consider other options.
- The software is regularly updated. If not, consider other options.
- Demos, video tutorials, and guides are available to help me familiarize myself with the platform. If not, try to get more information from the software provider.
- The software is properly documented. If not, try to get more information from the software provider.
- There are known use cases, success stories, or lessons learned from failures with this software.
- The software is backed by a large, active community of users and developers.
- Integration with key infrastructures (e.g., Crossref, DataCite, ORCID) is supported. If not, consider other options.
- The platform supports automated preservation of published content.

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- The journal can be migrated to another platform without significant difficulty if needed. If not, consider other options.

4 · Is this independent platform right for us?

- I have sufficient technical resources (hardware, software) to support the publishing platform.
If not, consider other options such as shared platforms or Software-as-a-Service solutions. Some countries (e.g., Croatia, Greece, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain) offer national infrastructures based on free open-source software for OA publishers. Universities often host publishing platforms for their journals, or you can partner with other publishers to establish shared platforms. For SaaS, you can check service providers in the IPSP Registry.
- IT support for software installation is available. If not, consider outsourcing IT support.
- It will be possible to ensure ongoing maintenance and updates for the platform. If not, this probably means that you don't have sufficient resources to run your own platform.
- There are additional costs for IT support or software upgrades (included in the budget, funding sources identified). If yes, include those costs in the budget and try to find funding sources
- I have the financial resources allocated for ongoing maintenance, security, backups, and updates. If yes, include those costs in the budget and try to find funding sources.
- It will be possible to repair and replace hardware if needed. If not, consider outsourcing hosting.
- My hosting provider guarantees hardware and software integrity. If not, find a different provider.
- There is a clear agreement on the service level expectations from the hosting provider. If yes, make sure to conclude a written agreement with the hosting provider detailing service level expectations.
- There are enough trained personnel to manage the platform effectively. If not, consider outsourcing support or upskilling the existing staff.
- I have documentation detailing technical setup and workflows for transitions in case of staff changes.

5 · Is this SaaS platform right for us?

5.1. Feature scope: Does it cover all publishing needs?

- The platform covers all the essential publishing needs, such as manuscript submission, peer review, and content distribution.
- All features required are offered by this platform.
- Those features are vital for your work. If these vital features aren't covered by the platform, consider finding a different solution.
- There are features offered in the service package that are not used.

These features aren't used because reasons for not using the features include:

- We don't know how to use them.
- Additional staff would be required.
- We don't really need those features.
- It is possible to exclude unused features from the package to reduce the cost.
- It is possible to exclude those features from the package to reduce the cost.

5.2. Long-term preservation: Does the provider ensure sustainable long-term preservation?

- Digital preservation is included in the service package.
- The service provider collaborates with a trusted preservation service (e.g., LOCKSS, CLOCKSS, PKP Preservation Network, etc.).

If the platform doesn't meet these criteria, make sure to take care about preservation yourself. Learn more with our visual guide to digital preservation in the dedicated course.

5.3. Documentation and support: Are comprehensive guides available?

- Comprehensive user guides, manuals, or tutorials are available to help with platform usage.
- Technical support is provided.

If the platform doesn't meet these criteria, consider changing the service provider.

- Technical support involves additional costs, and these costs are clearly indicated in the service agreement. If not, make sure that details about technical support are included in the service agreement.

5.4. Customization options: Is it possible to customise the SaaS platform? Under what conditions (e.g. you can do it yourself or the provider can do this for a fee)?

- The platform can be customized to fit specific needs.
- Responsibility for customisation (e.g., self-service or provider-managed) is clearly defined.
- There is no cost involved.
- The conditions for customisation are clear. If not, make sure that conditions for potential customisation are discussed before signing the service agreement.

5.5. Vendor lock-in risk: Can you change the platform provider without data loss or having to pay a high fee?

- The service provider has committed to keeping the platform up-to-date with relevant technological developments.
- It is possible to switch to another platform without data loss or a significant amount of manual work.
- There are high fees or complex processes associated with migrating your data.

If the platform doesn't meet these criteria, consider changing the service provider.

10. Metadata

Details

Subtitle: How to structure metadata for indexing and discovery

Duration: Approximately 45 minutes

Keywords: Metadata, indexing, discovery, interoperability, preservation

Abstract: Learn how to manage and structure metadata to improve discoverability, support interoperability, and ensure your journal content meets Diamond OA standards.

Introduction

Metadata plays a key role in making scholarly content visible, accessible, and reusable. Applying clear and consistent metadata standards is essential to ensure journal content is properly indexed and reaches the right audience. This course offers practical guidance on how to structure and display metadata in your online journal to improve its discoverability and reach.

In this course, you will learn:

- Why proper metadata is essential for indexing and long-term accessibility
- How to apply best practices for curating and displaying metadata
- What metadata elements and standards support discoverability and interoperability

Please note: This course provides general guidance. For implementation on a specific publishing platform, refer to that platform's technical documentation.

Glossary

File format: A file format is a standard way of encoding information so that it can be stored in a computer file. It defines the structure and type of data that the file contains: how information is organised, encoded, and represented. Thanks to this, the data stored in files can be consistently interpreted, accessed, and processed by software applications. File formats widely used in the context of scholarly publishing include:

- PDF (Portable Document Format)
- EPUB (Electronic Publication)

- HTML (Hypertext Markup Language)
- XML JATS (Journal Article Tag Suite)
- DOCX (Microsoft Word Open XML Document)
- LaTeX (Document Preparation System)
- CSV (Comma-Separated Values)

Reference/derivation: <https://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/appendices/file-formats/>

Interoperability: Interoperability is the ability of different systems, devices, or software to communicate, exchange data, interact and work together smoothly and efficiently. It involves the establishment of common standards, protocols, and interfaces to facilitate smooth communication among systems.

Metadata: Metadata provides information about data. Specifically, it is machine-readable data that describes content, context and structure of resources and their management over time. In the context of scholarly publishing, metadata are pieces of information that describe published outputs (articles, books, journals, etc.).

Metadata standard: Metadata standard is a set of rules and guidelines that define the structure and format of metadata. It ensures that resources are described consistently and that descriptions are understandable and usable across different platforms.

A specific implementation of a metadata standard tailored to a particular context or use case is called metadata schema. It details how the elements defined in a standard should be used and it often includes additional rules and guidelines.

Widely used metadata standards include:

- [Dublin Core](#)
- [MARC](#) (Machine-Readable Cataloguing)
- [MODS](#) (Metadata Object Description Schema)
- [TEI](#) (Text Encoding Initiative)
- [PREMIS](#) (Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies)

Reference/derivation: RDA Metadata Standards Catalogue: <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

Metadata exchange protocol: A metadata exchange protocol is a set of rules and standards that governs the transfer of metadata between systems, applications, or services. These protocols facilitate the sharing, discovery, and use of metadata and ensure interoperability, and consistent interpretation of metadata across various systems and platforms. Commonly used metadata exchange protocols:

1. [OAI-PMH](#) (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting)
2. [OAI-ORE](#) (Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange)
3. [RESTful APIs](#) (Representational State Transfer APIs)
4. [SWORD](#) (Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit)
5. [SOAP](#) (Simple Object Access Protocol)
6. [SPARQL](#) (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language)
7. [Z39.50](#)

Software-as-a-Service (SaaS): Software-as-a-Service is a software delivery model where applications are hosted and maintained by a provider and made accessible to users via a web

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browser. This model eliminates the need for managing infrastructure, updates, or hardware on the user side and can involve subscriptions for using the service. In the context of scholarly publishing, SaaS refers to cloud-based publishing platforms provided by non-profit or commercial providers, allowing publishers to manage the entire publishing workflow without having to host software locally.

TDM (Text and Data Mining): Automated computational analysis of text and data. Often involves downloading, extracting, and indexing full texts and metadata for research purposes.

Vendor lock-in: Vendor lock-in is a situation where a customer becomes dependent on a specific vendor's products, services, or technologies because it is difficult and/or expensive to switch to another provider. Such a situation can arise due to high switching costs, proprietary formats, or incompatible systems that limit interoperability. In the context of scholarly publishing software and services, vendor lock-in may happen if:

- The platform uses proprietary data formats that are incompatible with other platforms
- Migration to a different platform would require significant time, effort, technical expertise and funds.
- Service agreements impose high fees for data extraction.
- Support, updates, or customizations are exclusively controlled by the vendor.

Training material 1 - Interactive course

Step 1. Metadata

Metadata include digital pieces of information that describe published outputs like journal articles, books, a chapter, or even the journal itself. This course will help you understand the importance of metadata for the effective dissemination of scholarly content.

We'll explore how to display metadata in your online journal and how to leverage best practice to ensure optimal discoverability of your journal.

Please note that this course offers generic guidance. In order to be able to implement metadata on a specific publishing platform, you will have to consult the relevant technical guidelines.

Step 2. Human-readable metadata on article landing pages

In the digital age, content discovery hinges on metadata exchange. That is why published content should be described with detailed metadata.

Let's explore the key metadata elements that contribute to effective scholarly communication. The following illustration is a good example of the structural layout of an article's landing page. Take a close look at the information displayed across the five categories below.

A [PDF version](#) of this presentation is available for accessibility purposes and download.

To make this work effectively, here are some best practices to keep in mind:

Unique landing pages: Every published item needs its own landing page with a unique URL. This provides a stable and permanent web address for readers, search engines, and indexing services to reliably access the article's full metadata and content.

Multilingual metadata: Where relevant, provide metadata in at least two languages. In this case, dedicated article landing pages should be created for each language.

Clear author identification: Define author name conventions in author guidelines and use ORCIDiDs to ensure accurate identification of authors.

Leverage journal management systems: If the journal uses one, the metadata entered into the system in the publishing process should be automatically displayed on article landing pages.

Activity

Choose an article landing page from your journal's website and analyse the metadata elements displayed.

Is all the key information present? Is it accurate and clearly presented?

This practical exercise can reveal valuable insights and potential areas for improvement in your own publishing workflows.

Step 3. Machine-readable metadata on article landing pages

Well-designed article landing pages with comprehensive metadata alone are not sufficient to guarantee that search engines and aggregators will capture and index the information. The metadata should also be shown in a way that allows machines to easily interpret and process it.

Meta tags: The most common way of exposing machine-readable metadata in online journals is through HTML meta tags, which contain metadata structured according to standard metadata schemas. e.g. Dublin Core, Schema.org, etc. These schemas define consistent metadata formats that search engines, databases, and indexing services can easily interpret, enabling reliable retrieval and indexing of journal articles and enhancing their discoverability.

Configuration: If the journal uses an online journal management system, the metadata entered into the system in the publishing process will be automatically embedded in html tags. Some free and open-source journal management systems, including Open Journal Systems and Janeway, also support the Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH), which allows them to deliver structured metadata in XML format.

Checking: Collaborate with your IT support to make sure that meta tags and metadata exchange protocols are properly configured. Make sure that OAI-PMH protocol is enabled (e.g. in Settings > Distribution > Access in Open Journal Systems). If you are struggling to enable this, reach out to the community for support, e.g. via the European Digital Capacity Hub.

To check by yourself, you can:

- Use the "View Page Source" option in your web browser to inspect meta tags.
- Test metadata capture using a reference management application, such as Zotero.

Below is an example of metadata presented via HTML meta tags : [embedded_metadata.jpg](#)

Step 4. Persistent identifiers for articles and the underlying metadata

Persistent identifiers (DOI, ARK, Handle, URN) are permanent, unique digital links assigned to articles and registered in curated registries. They provide a consistent way to locate and access a specific article online, even if its location changes.

In order to obtain a persistent identifier (PID) for an article, the publisher usually deposits the article's metadata into a registry, linking the PID to the article's digital location. Due to this, various services (reference managers, APIs, search engines, aggregators, etc.) can retrieve metadata from PIDs.

Image: [PIDs](#) [The image shows what kind of information can be retrieved from a persistent identifier if rich metadata are deposited when registering a PID]

[DOI \(Digital Object Identifier\)](#) is a unique alphanumeric code assigned to a digital object, such as a journal article, book, or dataset, providing a permanent link to its online location. It is managed by the International DOI Foundation. DOIs are the most widely used PIDs for journal articles. In order to be able to assign DOIs to journal articles, you should make an arrangement with a DOI registration agency or a DOI service provider (organisation authorised to register DOIs), which usually involves a membership fee and a fee charged for each DOI. Learn more: [Existing Registration Agencies](#) Some free and open-source journal management systems (e.g. Open Journal Systems, Janeway) simplify DOI registration by automating the metadata deposit and DOI assignment steps.

[Handle](#) is a type of persistent identifier maintained by the Corporation for National Research Initiatives (CNRI). Handles can be applied to a wide range of digital materials. Some journals use handles instead of DOIs as a more affordable option.

[ARK \(Archival Resource Key\)](#) is a type of persistent identifier managed by the California Digital Library (CDL). ARKs can be assigned to digital, physical, or abstract entities. The adoption and use of ARKs for persistent identification of digital and physical resources is supported by the ARK Alliance. Some journals use ARKs instead of DOIs as a more affordable option.

[URN \(Uniform Resource Name\)](#) is a persistent identifier system managed by the IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force) and widely used by major national libraries in Europe. URNs cannot be used to directly locate an item and are not necessarily resolvable. Although there are no licence costs involved in assigning URNs, an URN registration agency needs to establish appropriate infrastructure. URNs can be used for journal articles, but this practice is not very common.

[ORCID \(Open Researcher and Contributor ID\)](#) is a unique, persistent digital identifier usually assigned to researchers and scholars, helping distinguish researchers with similar names and ensuring proper attribution of their publications and other academic contributions. Require authors to provide their ORCIDs when submitting a manuscript. It is free for authors to use ORCID.

ROR ([Research Organization Registry](#)) is a persistent identifier for research institutions, organisations, and funders. ROR provides a unique, machine-readable ID to accurately identify and link research organisations and ensure proper attribution of research outputs. Require authors to provide RORs for their institutions, if available, when submitting a manuscript. RORs are free for institutions.

Step 5. Make your metadata open

In the digital environment, metadata is exchanged across systems, making research outputs widely accessible and interconnected. Search engines, aggregators and academic services use various methods to capture metadata automatically and, in some cases, publishers have to provide metadata in a particular format. To maximise the reach and impact of your metadata, consider the following practices:

When setting up the platform

Make sure that

- features supporting metadata creation and display are properly installed and configured,
- relevant metadata exchange protocols are properly configured,
- metadata export is enabled and configured.

Release the metadata into the public domain using the CC0 licence, e.g. by including the following statement in the journal policies: “The journal metadata are freely accessible to all, and freely reusable by all, under the terms of the Creative Commons [Universal \(CC0 1.0\) Public Domain Dedication licence](#).” This enables various aggregators to harvest and disseminate your metadata without having to ask permission or deal with complicated licensing issues. Public-domain metadata foster wider access to information, promote collaboration, allow for the development of new tools and services based on this data and play the key role in building non-commercial discovery platforms (e.g. [OpenAIRE Explore](#), [OpenAlex](#), [OpenCitations](#)) and citation indexes.

At manuscript submission

- Make sure that authors submit accurate and detailed metadata, including funding information, ORCIDs for authors and RORs for their organizations.
- Require authors to use a citation style that includes DOIs displayed as full URLs.

During content production

- Add date, article number, volume and issue
- Enrich the metadata provided by authors if needed (e.g. by adding additional keywords, PIDs, etc.)
- Consider providing metadata in multiple languages
- Assign PIDs for articles (e.g. DOI)

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- Deposit complete metadata about publications, including bibliographic references and abstracts, when registering persistent identifiers for articles in line with the recommendations of the [Initiative for Open Citations \(I4OC\)](#) and [Initiative for Open Abstracts \(I4OA\)](#). Provide PIDs for authors, organisations and related research outputs (e.g. research data), as well as metadata in multiple languages, if available.

To go further, you can explore essential indexing strategies in the course [Visibility, communication, marketing and impact](#) (chapter 3 of the resource "Visibility and Discoverability").

Step 6. Considerations for the full text

Some search engines like Google Scholar build their indexes by processing full-text content. Consider the following to make it easier for search engines to capture metadata from the full text :

Structured full text: Structure the full text, ideally in JATS XML, which allows for flexible conversion to multiple formats (like PDF, HTML, and ePub) and ensures consistent metadata embedding. Avoid outdated file formats like DOC, RTF, WPD, etc.

Rich metadata embedding: Embed detailed metadata, including CRediT information, copyright and licence information, and conflict of interest statements in the full text. Learn more: Resources: JATS XML

PDF/A compliance: Ensure that the PDF version is PDF/A compliant. Most typesetting tools allow for the creation of PDF/A files.

Open fonts: Use open-source, Unicode-supporting fonts for broader compatibility and accessibility. Learn more: [Open-Source Unicode Typefaces](#). (Wikipedia)

Unrestricted access: Do not restrict access to the full text (e.g. by preventing text copying or converting text in PDFs to outlines).

Active links: Ensure key elements in the full text are linked and accessible: Display all PIDs (e.g., DOIs, ORCIDs) as full URLs and interactive links within the PDF. Present license information as interactive links for easy access.

Citations: Cite references consistently. Inconsistent citation styles and missing identifiers make it hard for indexing services to capture citations. Use a citation style that includes DOIs displayed as full URLs.

Step 7. Conclusion

Publishers play a pivotal role in ensuring the discoverability, accessibility, and impact of scholarly content. This course has highlighted the importance of metadata in achieving these goals, offering a comprehensive overview of best practices and actionable strategies for optimising metadata at every stage of the publishing process.

To summarise the key takeaways, you can explore the flashcards below. Each card presents the main concepts; you need to flip them to reveal detailed explanations and examples.

Recto: Human-readable metadata

Verso: Each article should have a dedicated landing page with a unique URL. Display detailed metadata on the landing page

Use persistent identifiers for authors, organisations, published content (e.g. in cited references).

If the publishing platform is multilingual, create separate landing pages for different languages.

Recto: Machine readable metadata

Verso: Use HTML meta tags to display structured metadata. Make sure that metadata exchange protocols (e.g. OAI-PMH) are enabled and configured.

Deposit rich metadata when registering PIDs for articles (e.g., references, keywords, abstracts).

Recto: PIDs

Verso:

- DOI, ARK, Handle, or URN for articles
- ORCID for authors
- ROR for institutions
- Display PIDs in the recommended format, e.g. <https://doi.org/10.xxxx/xxxxx>.
- Deposit rich metadata when registering PIDs (e.g., references, keywords, abstracts)

Recto: Licensing and Copyright

Verso: Indicate copyright holders on article landing pages and in the full text.

Clearly display licensing information on article landing pages and in the full text, in all file formats (HTML, XML, PDF).

Provide the licence name, logo and a link to the licence deed. . CC BY 4.0 license

Recto: Open Metadata

Verso: Release metadata under the CC0 license to allow reuse without restrictions.

Deposit rich metadata when registering PIDs for articles (e.g., references, keywords, abstracts).

Include metadata in multiple languages where applicable.

Recto: Metadata in the full text

Verso: Structure the full text, ideally in JATS XML. Embed detailed metadata in the full text

Display all PIDs in the PDF as full URLs and interactive links.

Use a citation style that includes DOIs displayed as full URLs.

Additional resources

The following supplementary resources offer a deeper dive into key metadata concepts and practical implementation strategies to enhance your publishing practices.

General

'Metadata'. 2024. European Diamond Capacity Hub. 2024.

<https://toolsuite.diamas.org/metadata>.

Avanço, Karla. 2023a. 'What Is Metadata for Publication and How Is It Used? Part 1: Introduction to Metadata'. Billet. The Road to FAIR (blog). 19 January 2023.

<https://roadtofair.hypotheses.org/499>.

Avanço, Karla. 2023b. 'What Is Metadata for Publication and How Is It Used? Part 2: Metadata Standards'. Billet. The Road to FAIR (blog). 3 February 2023.

<https://roadtofair.hypotheses.org/696>.

How to get a PID

Registering content with Crossref: <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/register-maintain-records/choose-content-registration-method/>

Create DataCite DOIs: <https://doi.datacite.org/>

Janeway: Identifiers:

<https://janeway.readthedocs.io/en/v1.4.2/manager/identifiers/index.html>

Handles: https://www.pidconsortium.net/?page_id=1060

Assigning ARKs: <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/ARKs/ARK+Identifiers+FAQ>

Displaying PIDs

'DataCite DOI Display Guidelines'. DataCite Support.

<https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-doi-display-guidelines>.

Hendricks, Ginny. n.d. 'DOI Display Guidelines'. Website. Crossref.

<https://www.crossref.org/display-guidelines/>

'User Experience Display Guidelines'. n.d. ORCID. Accessed 28 April

2024. <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-guide/user-experience-display-guidelines>

Registry (ROR), Research Organization. 2021. 'ROR Display Guidelines', April.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4702038>

Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT)

'CRediT'. 2022. CRediT. 2 August 2022. <https://credit.niso.org/>.

'CRediT Taxonomy'. 2022. JATS4R. 9 May 2022. <https://jats4r.org/credit-taxonomy/>.

'Implementing CRediT'. 2020. CRediT (blog). 14 April 2020. <https://credit.niso.org/implementing-credit/>.

JATS XML

'JATS XML Converter Service'. n.d. Accessed 5 December 2024. <https://jats.srce.hr/>.

'JATS4R – Optimise Reusability and Exchange of Content Tagged in JATS XML'. n.d. Accessed 5 December 2024. <https://jats4r.niso.org/>.

'Journal Article Tag Suite'. n.d. Accessed 5 December 2024. <https://jats.nlm.nih.gov/>.

Training material 2: visual guide

Article Information

1. Article Title: The title of the research article.
2. Journal title, volume, issue, publication year, and article number (or pagination).
3. Abstract: A concise summary that highlights the study's objectives, methods, key findings, and conclusions.
4. Keywords: Specific terms or phrases that capture the main topics of the study. It is a good idea to enrich author-provided keywords with terms from relevant controlled vocabularies.
5. Persistent Identifier (DOI, ARK, Handle, URN): DOI should always be displayed as a full URL link in the form <https://doi.org/10.xxxx/xxxxx>. Learn more: <https://www.crossref.org/display-guidelines/>
6. Publication timeline: Dates of article submission, review, acceptance and publication.
7. Funding information: A statement disclosing financial support received for the research or project. This section typically includes details about grants, sponsorships, institutional support, or other financial resources that contributed to the study. It often specifies the funding organisations or agencies (using funders' persistent identifiers, e.g. RORs, is recommended), grant numbers, and any relevant funding acknowledgements

Author information

1. Full names of authors: See Author contributions for more details
2. ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID): Unique identifiers for each author.
3. Institutional affiliations: Authors' institutions, including full names and addresses, e.g. University, Faculty/Institute, City, Country
4. ROR (Research Organization Registry ID): Institutional persistent identifier
5. Author Contributions: Contributions for deserving authorship include not only writing but also the activities related to the conceptualisation and execution of the research, collection and production of the research data/materials, analysis and interpretation. Use the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) to describe the key types of contributions

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made to the article. See Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) below for more information.

Journal and publisher information

1. Journal title: it should be the same as registered in the ISSN International Registry. Don't use any unofficial translated or abbreviated forms.
2. Publisher's name. Display the publisher's name prominently on the journal website. Use the official name, as registered in the ISSN International Registry.
3. ISSN and eISSN. ISSN(International Standard Serial Number)and eISSN(electronic ISSN) are unique identifiers assigned to print and electronic versions of a serial publication, respectively. Display these numbers prominently on a journal website to make it easy for users to locate and verify this information.

Rights and access Information

1. Open access icon: indicates the open access status of the article.
2. Copyright information: Specifies who has the legal rights to the article. Diamond OA journals should allow authors to retain copyright.
3. Licence information: Outlines the terms under which the article can be used, shared, and adapted by others. The Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) licence is recommended, as it allows unrestricted distribution and adaptation of the work, provided the original authors are credited. Use the latest version of the CC licence: 4.0 version, which is more user-friendly and more internationally robust. Always provide a link to the licence deed. Learn more: <https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/policies/displaying-licensing-information>

Referencing

1. References. A list of sources cited throughout the text that provide supporting information, prior research, or context for the study, acknowledging the work of other researchers and enabling readers to locate original sources for further study. Use standardised citation styles (e.g., APA, MLA, Chicago) to ensure consistency and facilitate accurate identification of sources. When deciding which citation style to use in your journal(s), you should give preference to those that include DOI or URL in reference list entries (e.g. APA, Chicago) and always display DOIs and URLs as links.
2. Supporting information: Providing links to related research outputs (e.g. research data deposited in repositories, preprints, and registered studies, etc.) in the metadata of a journal article enhances the transparency, reproducibility, and discoverability of research. Use persistent identifiers to establish links with the related content.
3. How to cite

11. Digital preservation

Details

Subtitle: Preparing content for long-term access

Duration: 5 minutes

Keywords: Preservation, archive, storage, accessibility, metadata, indexing/indexation

Abstract: Learn how to preserve Diamond OA publications using open formats, rich metadata, and reliable archiving solutions to ensure long-term accessibility.

Introduction

Diamond Open Access publishers often work with limited resources, making it challenging to keep content safe and accessible over time. Without proper preservation, articles can be lost due to platform failures or outdated formats.

Presented in a clear infographic format, this course offers key strategies to help you protect your journal's content for the long term.

In this course, you will learn:

- How to prepare your content for archiving using recommended formats and metadata.
- What tools and services can help preserve your journal, even with a small budget.
- How to make your content accessible and discoverable over time.

Training material 1 : visual guide

Digital Preservation in Diamond Open Access publishing

In the digital age, publications are vulnerable to technology failures, platform changes, and format obsolescence, while Diamond Open Access publishers face significant challenges. Learn key strategies to ensure the long-term preservation, interoperability, and accessibility of published articles.

Archive Your Publications

- Dark Archives:** Services like LOCKSS, CLOCKSS, and Portico are robust, distributed archiving systems that safeguard your content and provide continued access if your primary platform fails or is discontinued.
- Community Guidance:** Diamond Open Access publishers can face significant resource challenges in digital preservation, but you can get support from community initiatives like the PKP Preservation Network for Open Journal Systems users, and Project JASPER for Diamond OA Journals indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ).

Prepare for Archiving

c. Content

- Fonts: Unicode-compliant, open-source.
- Images: high-resolution with descriptive captions.
- Tables: easy to interpret, well-structured, annotated.
- Consistent file naming: follow best practices.
- Metadata: machine-readable in widely used formats, e.g., XML, CSV, JSON.

d. Formats

- Open and widely used file formats like PDF, HTML, and EPUB.
- PDF is not optimal for small screens or text and data mining.
- Tag full-text in XML JATS or equivalent (e.g., TEI).
- Use multiple formats.

12. Visibility, discoverability and impact

Details

Subtitle: Making a journal visible, valued, and widely read

Duration: 70 minutes

Keywords: Visibility, indexing, communication, marketing, impact, metadata, **metrics**

Abstract: Learn how to promote a Diamond Open Access journal and measure its reach through effective indexing strategies, targeted communication approaches, and responsible metrics.

Introduction

The full potential of Open Access is achieved when content is disseminated as widely as possible to academia and society at large. However, operating without charging authors or readers often comes with limited resources for marketing and dissemination.

This course provides you with different strategies to ensure that the journal and the work it publishes reaches the largest, most relevant audience possible and has a significant impact.

In this course, you will learn to:

- Ensure a journal and its content are easily discoverable online through transparent policies, indexing strategies and technical considerations
- Develop targeted communication strategies and a strong visual identity to engage your scholarly community effectively.
- Apply various metrics and analytical tools to track usage, measure effectiveness, and responsibly evaluate publication impact.

Glossary

Metadata: Metadata provides information about data. Specifically, it is machine readable data that describes content, context and structure of resources and their management over time. In

the context of scholarly publishing, metadata are pieces of information that describe published outputs (articles, books, journals, etc.).

Metrics: Metrics are quantitative indicators used to measure various aspects of scholarly publishing performance and impact. In the context of Diamond Open Access publishing, metrics can track usage (views, downloads), engagement (comments, shares), citation impact, editorial workflow efficiency, and geographic reach. These measurements provide insights that can inform strategic decisions and demonstrate value to stakeholders

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): A persistent identifier (PID) is a long-lasting reference to a digital object, person, organisation, or other entity. It is unique to an entity and remains stable over time, i.e. it resolves even if the location of the entity changes. PIDs widely used in scholarly publishing:

- DOI (Digital Object Identifier)
- Handle Archival Resource Key (ARK)
- URN (Uniform Resource Name)
- ISBN (International Standard Book Number)
- ISSN (International Standard Serial Number)
- ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)
- ROR (Research Organization Registry)
- ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)

Reference/derivation: PID Services Registry: <https://pidservices.org/>

Repositories: Repositories are digital platforms that hold research output and provide free, immediate and permanent access to research results for anyone to use, download and share. Repository (open access repository), OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit).

Search Engine Optimization (SEO): SEO refers to the practice of optimising digital content to improve its visibility in search engine results. In scholarly publishing, SEO involves techniques that make journal websites and published content more discoverable by search engines. This includes optimising HTML tags, website structure, keywords in titles and abstracts, and ensuring accessibility of content to search engine crawlers.

Training material 1: Visibility and discoverability

Step 1. Transparent policies

Readers, authors, libraries, search engines indexing services and aggregators are more likely to engage with journals and their content when they can easily find relevant information such as open access status, licensing terms, editorial practices, and data availability. Clearly communicating this type of information is essential for making research accessible, reusable, and discoverable.

Reflecting these principles, the following section provides a series of key questions to help you assess and improve your transparency practices.

Open Access status and licensing

Do you have a clear Open Access statement prominently displayed on your publishing platform? This assures users that the content is freely available.

Are the licensing terms for your content clearly stated? Specify the licence governing the reuse and distribution of your content (e.g., Creative Commons licences like CC BY). This ensures users understand their rights and obligations regarding the use of your publications. Provide a link to the full licence text for easy reference.

Have you considered dedicating your metadata to the public domain? Whenever possible, use the CC0 license for metadata provided via exchange protocols (e.g., OAI-PMH). This maximises interoperability and allows for broader reuse and distribution of your metadata, further increasing the discoverability of your publications. Clearly state the metadata licensing policy to avoid ambiguity.

For comprehensive information on Open Access status and licensing, we recommend our "Copyright and Licenses" course.

Journal policies and guidelines

Are your mission, vision, and scope statements clearly defined and publicly available? This helps readers, authors, libraries, search engines indexing services and aggregators quickly determine if the content aligns with their interests. Such a targeted visibility increases engagement.

Do you have comprehensive author and reviewers guidelines? Clear and publicly available guidelines encourage high-quality submissions and facilitate thorough peer reviews. This enhances the credibility of the published work.

Are your editorial policies readily available? These policies should encompass research ethics, publishing ethics, and peer review processes. Transparency in these areas builds trust and demonstrates your commitment to rigorous and ethical practices. Make these policies easily accessible on your website.

Our course 'Editorial Policy and Quality' covers this topic in more details.

Open Science practices

The availability of data, protocols and other materials underlying a scholarly publication significantly improves its value and impact and can foster further discoveries and broader application of the published research.

Are datasets underlying research articles publicly available? Publicly available datasets are harvested by aggregators and captured by search engines. Due to this, researchers looking for data can also track down associated publications. This broader exposure can significantly increase citations and overall impact.

Are supplementary materials being shared? Sharing supplementary materials such as software, protocols, and methodologies, can attract researchers seeking specific tools or methods. When these resources are readily available, researchers are more likely to find and cite associated publications. This increased accessibility also fosters collaboration and promotes the wider adoption of research outputs.

To learn more, take a look at this infographic: [link]

Step 2. Technical strategies

The discoverability of online scholarly content depends on a number of technical factors, such as descriptive information about the publication (metadata), unique persistent identifiers for articles and other content, and optimising the website for search engines. Collaborate with your IT support to make sure that the following strategies are implemented.

Metadata quality

High-quality and well-crafted metadata ensures your content is easily found by researchers, readers, and indexing services, significantly increasing its impact and reach. Here's what you need to check:

Does your metadata adhere to established standards? Following globally accepted metadata standards ensures your metadata is compatible with various systems and platforms, enabling broader dissemination and discoverability of your publications. This interoperability allows your content to be easily incorporated into databases and search indexes worldwide.

Have you included all key descriptive elements in your metadata? Comprehensive metadata provides a rich and detailed description of your work, enabling search engines and databases to accurately index and display your publications. Include essential information such as titles, authors, abstracts, keywords, publication dates, licensing details, and related identifiers to ensure your content is easily discoverable.

Is your metadata readily available to both humans and machines? Metadata should be clearly displayed on article landing pages for human readers and embedded within the HTML source code for search engine crawlers. This ensures that both human users and automated systems can easily capture and use your metadata.

Do you use protocols like OAI-PMH? Employing protocols like OAI-PMH allows metadata harvesting by indexing services and databases, further expanding the reach of your publications.

Do you offer easy to export or copy citations? Providing easy-to-use citation options in various formats promotes proper attribution and increases the visibility of your work within scholarly communities.

For a deeper dive into metadata best practices, follow this course: [link]

Persistent identifiers (PIDs)

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are fundamental for ensuring the long-term access and proper attribution of your publications. For PIDs to be truly effective, consider these essential practices.

Have you obtained PIDs for all articles from a recognized registration agency (e.g., Crossref, DataCite for DOIs)? PIDs for articles (e.g. DOIs, ARKs, Handles, URNs) are crucial for persistent access and accurate citation tracking, ensuring your content remains findable and citable over time.

Are all relevant PIDs (DOIs, ORCIDs, ISNIs, RORs) included in the metadata you submit when registering PIDs for articles? This maximises interlinking and discoverability, connecting your publications with authors, institutions, and other related research outputs.

Are all relevant PIDs clearly displayed on article landing pages? Displaying PIDs on article landing pages in line with relevant recommendations ensures easy access for users, facilitating proper citation and linking practices.

Are PIDs embedded within the HTML <head> tag? Embedding PIDs in the HTML code enhances machine readability, enabling search engines and other automated systems to accurately index and link your publications.

Search engine optimisation (SEO)

The discoverability and ranking of your online content in search engines is crucial for attracting readers and researchers to your publications. Follow these Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) best practices to achieve this:

Are you using relevant and specific keywords throughout your website? Include relevant keywords in the HTML <head> tag not only for published articles but also for all other journal pages (home page, Aims and Scope, journal policies, author guidelines, etc.). Avoid keyword stuffing in <head> tags, as this can negatively impact your ranking in search engines. For articles, enrich the author-provided keywords by integrating additional terms from subject-specific controlled vocabularies to cover essential aspects not explicitly included by the authors. Include relevant keywords in image alt text.

Have you optimised your HTML title tags and meta descriptions? These tags provide concise summaries of your content to search engines and users. Make sure meta descriptions for article landing pages include article abstracts. Craft compelling and informative meta descriptions for all other journal pages (home page, Aims and Scope, journal policies, author guidelines, etc.) that accurately reflect the content of each page and encourage clicks from search results.

Is your website architecture well-structured and easy to navigate? A logical hierarchy of pages, clear navigation menus, and descriptive internal links are essential for both user experience and

search engine crawlers. Ensure your sitemap is accurate and up-to-date, allowing search engines to easily index all your content.

Do you regularly update your website with new content and refresh existing material? Regularly publishing new articles, blog posts, and other relevant content signals to search engines that your website is active. Keeping existing content current and accurate also improves user experience and search ranking.

Have you created and submitted an XML sitemap to search engines? Sitemaps help search engines discover and index all the pages on your website, ensuring that your content is easily findable. Keep your sitemap up-to-date as you add or remove pages.

Is your website responsive, adapting seamlessly to different screen sizes? A responsive design is crucial for providing a positive user experience across all devices (desktops, tablets, and smartphones). Search engines prioritize mobile-friendly websites, so responsiveness is a key factor in search engine ranking.

Is your website fast and secure? Page load speed significantly impacts user experience and can affect ranking in search engines. Optimise images, minimise HTTP requests, and leverage browser caching to improve loading times. Ensure your website uses HTTPS to provide a secure browsing experience for your users. Regularly monitor your website's performance using tools like Google Search Console to identify and address any technical issues.

Are you using structured data markup to provide context to search engines? Structured data (e.g. Dublin Core, schema.org, etc.) helps search engines capture the content on your pages, leading to richer search results and improved visibility.

Activity

How would you solve these problems? Consider the technical issues described on the front of each card. Then, formulate potential solutions. Flip the card to check your reasoning against recommended best practices.

Recto: Articles rarely appear in search engine results, even with specific keywords. **Verso:** Improve SEO: keyword research, website structure, HTML tags, sitemaps, and fresh content.

Recto: Broken or outdated links to articles in search engines and indexing databases. **Verso:** Implement persistent identifiers (DOIs) for all articles, ensuring links remain stable regardless of website changes.

Recto: Journal content is not discoverable in indexing databases and search engines. **Verso:** Standardise metadata using established schemas, meet indexing criteria and apply for indexing with relevant databases and services.

[D4.4 Training report]

Recto: Readers can't easily use citation information for articles. **Verso:** Provide human readable metadata on article pages, machine readable metadata in HTML using meta tags, and pre-formatted citations in various styles

Recto: Search engines, aggregators and indexing databases have trouble connecting articles with other relevant research outputs (e.g. datasets, protocols). **Verso:** Embed PIDs of related outputs within the HTML `<head>` tag in the article landing page. Include the PIDs of related outputs in the article metadata when registering the article PID. Add the article PID to the metadata of related outputs.

Recto: The website is difficult to use on smartphones and tablets. **Verso:** Implement a responsive web design. This ensures the website adapts to different screen sizes and provides a good user experience on all devices.

Recto: The citation information captured by reference managers and indexing services from article landing pages is inaccurate and incomplete. **Verso:** Ensure that article landing pages include machine-readable structured metadata (e.g. Dublin Core, JSON) and that detailed metadata are provided when registering PIDs.

Step 3. Indexation

Wider dissemination of metadata through various channels significantly expands a publication's reach. Indexing services, libraries, aggregators, and repositories all help to connect your content with a larger audience. By ensuring your content is present on these platforms, you increase its visibility and discoverability.

Disciplinary databases and indexes

Identify and target disciplinary databases and indexes to reach specific research communities. This focused approach ensures that your journal is discoverable by researchers actively working in the relevant field, leading to more targeted readership and potential authors.

Multidisciplinary and subject indexes

Submit the journal to prominent multidisciplinary indexing services and other relevant subject-specific indexes, having first ensured that the journal meets all relevant inclusion criteria. This broadens the journal's visibility within the wider academic community and within specialised research areas, increasing the likelihood of discovery by researchers using these services. Inclusion in reputable indexes also enhances the journal's prestige and perceived quality.

Library catalogues and discovery systems

Collaborate with libraries for inclusion in their catalogues and discovery systems. This makes your content accessible to a vast network of researchers and institutions subscribed to these library services.

Aggregators and archives

Engage with aggregators and archives that distribute content to libraries and other users. Aggregators and archives compile content from multiple sources, making it easier for libraries and researchers to access a wider range of materials through a single platform. This increases the discoverability and usage of your journal's content.

Open repositories and OAI-PMH

Make your scholarly content available in institutional or other open repositories that support the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). OAI-PMH allows metadata about your journal's content to be harvested by various search engines, databases, and other discovery services. This automated metadata sharing significantly expands the reach and discoverability of your publications beyond your immediate platform. It also promotes interoperability and allows for broader data analysis and research on scholarly communication patterns

Step 4. Indexation in practice

This last section provides information about some open access indexing services and aggregators that can help you disseminate your outputs and improve your visibility and outreach.

Before applying to any indexing service, carefully review and address the following:

- Check indexing status: Search for your journal to confirm whether it is indexed.
- Evaluate content coverage: Check whether all relevant content is properly indexed and discoverable.
- Review inclusion requirements: If your journal is not indexed, familiarise yourself with inclusion criteria and guidelines.
- Assess compliance: Review your journal to ensure it meets inclusion requirements.
- Apply for Indexing: If your journal is eligible, apply for indexing by following the application process.

DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals)

DOAJ is a community-curated online directory of peer-reviewed open access journals from all over the world, across all disciplines and languages. Managed by the Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA), it promotes visibility, accessibility, and best practices for open access publishing. It enables:

- Centralised discovery: DOAJ provides a trusted platform for researchers to discover quality OA content.

[D4.4 Training report]

- Increased visibility: Inclusion in DOAJ increases a journal's visibility to a global audience, attracting more readers and potential authors.
- Quality assurance: DOAJ's stringent inclusion criteria ensure that indexed journals meet high standards of quality and transparency, enhancing their credibility.
- Metadata distribution: DOAJ disseminates metadata to various search engines, databases, and other discovery services, further amplifying a journal's reach.

For more details on applying to DOAJ, refer to their detailed guide: <https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>

You can submit your journal to other indexing services:

- BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine) is a global multidisciplinary [search engine that harvests](#) OAI metadata from [institutional repositories, OA journals](#) and academic [digital libraries](#). Become a content provider: <https://www.base-search.net/about/en/suggest.php>
- CORE (Connecting Repositories) is a global aggregation service that harvests and indexes OA research outputs from repositories and journals. It is operated by the Knowledge Media Institute based at the Open University, United Kingdom. How to join <https://core.ac.uk/benefits#join-core>
- [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#), maintained by [OpenAIRE](#), is a comprehensive scholarly knowledge graph aggregating metadata for publications and other research outputs, projects, and organizations from global data sources. It underpins [OpenAIRE Explore](#), a discovery tool for researchers and funders. To submit a journal or publishing platform as a data source, use the [OpenAIRE Provide](#) service: <https://www.openaire.eu/validator-registration-guide>
- [OpenAlex](#) is an open access bibliographic database of scholarly publications, authors and institutions, named after the Library of Alexandria. It started operating in January 2022 as a successor of the terminated Microsoft Academic Graph and is managed by the non-profit organization OurResearch. OpenAlex automatically indexes new journals but if a journal is not indexed a request can be sent: <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/24740885744535-Can-you-index-my-journal>

Learning material 2: Usage and metrics

Step 1. Types of metrics

Diamond Open Access journals can use a whole range of quantitative indicators – called metrics – to track performance, usage and outreach and to inform strategic decisions. These metrics help assess the efficiency of editorial workflows and identify trends in readership, geographic reach, and engagement, content usage and impact. There are various types of metrics, you can explore the most commonly used below.

Citation counts

The number of times an article is cited by other scholarly publications. Citation counts are typically incomplete because citation tracking services have limited coverage, focusing only on publications with DOIs or a subset of selected journals. Despite these limitations, citation data remains highly appreciated by both authors and readers.

[Caption: Cited 45 times by other scholarly publications.]

Usage metrics

These metrics show how often articles and journals are accessed online. They include:

- Visits/Views: The number of times an article or journal page is viewed.
- Downloads: The number of times an article's full text is downloaded.
- Geographic Distribution: The locations of users accessing the content.

The most popular free and open-source publishing platforms have plugins that can capture and display this information.

[Caption: 12,000 views; 3,500 full-text downloads; Geographic Distribution]

Altmetrics

Altmetrics capture the broader online engagement and impact of research beyond traditional citations. They track:

- Social media: Mentions or shares on platforms like X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, and Facebook.
- Media Mentions: Appearances in blogs, news articles, and other media outlets.
- Saves/Bookmarks: The number of times an article is saved or bookmarked in reference managers like Mendeley.
- Online Discussions: Engagement through comments and discussions on publisher websites and academic networks.

This information can help identify which platforms and content types generate the highest engagement and resonate most with audiences, enabling publishers to tailor their marketing efforts. Please note that these metrics are typically generated by third-party services with limited coverage.

[Caption:

Social Media Mentions: X (formerly Twitter): 150 mentions | LinkedIn: 50 shares | Facebook: 30 shares | Media Mentions: Featured in 5 news articles; Discussed in 3 academic blogs; 200 saves in Mendeley; 10 comments on publisher website; Active threads in 2 academic networks]

Information about the editorial workflow

These metrics track the efficiency and effectiveness of the editorial process. Examples include the interval from submission to the first decision and the interval between acceptance and publication.

This information is important for authors when making decisions where to publish their research.

c Time from submission to first decision: 4 weeks. Time from acceptance to publication: 3 weeks.]

Journal-level metrics

These metrics provide insights into the overall performance of a journal. E.g. the average number of citations received by articles published in a journal over a specific period.

Some of these metrics, like JIF or SJR, are generated by third-party services and rely on proprietary datasets with limited coverage.

[Caption: Journal Impact Factor (JIF): 5.2; Average citations per article: 20; Add SCImago Journal Rank (SJR): 6.2]

Step 2. How used and useful

Different stakeholders have different needs when it comes to metrics. As a publisher, the metrics you choose to collect and display should reflect the perceived relevance to authors, readers, and funding agencies. Explore how various scenarios call for different types of metrics with the following activity.

Activity

Select the most appropriate type of metrics for each scenario.

1. You want to understand the geographic distribution of your readership. What types of metrics can help?

Answer: Usage metrics with location data.

*Usage metrics. Usage metrics, especially with location data, show you where your readers are located. This information can inform targeted marketing campaigns, help you encourage submissions from specific regions, and provide valuable insights into the global reach of your publications.

Citation counts. Citation counts tell you how many times your content is cited in other publications, without providing disaggregated geographic information, and won't help you understand your readership's distribution.

2. An author needs to choose the most appropriate journal for submitting their research. What types of metrics can help?

Answer: information about submission, acceptance and publication dates.

*Information about submission, acceptance, and publication dates. While many factors influence journal selection, understanding the typical timelines for submission, peer review, acceptance, and publication is crucial. This information helps authors align their publication strategy with career milestones, grant deadlines, or other time-sensitive goals. It also sets realistic expectations about the publication process.

Altmetrics. Altmetrics, which measure the broader societal outreach of research (like social media mentions and news coverage), are valuable for assessing engagement. However, they don't directly inform the key aspects of journal selection, such as scope, audience, quality, or publication timelines.

3. An author wants to assess the societal attention of its articles beyond the academic community. What types of metrics can help?

Answer: Altmetrics.

*Altmetrics. Altmetrics provide a valuable measure of an article's reach and influence beyond the academic community. They capture engagement on social media, mentions in news outlets and blogs, and discussions in online communities, giving authors a broader picture of their work's impact.

Citation counts. Citation counts show how many times an article has been referenced in scholarly publications, but they don't reflect the broader societal attention you're looking for.

4. A library wants to identify trends and popular topics in their field. What types of metrics can help?

Answer: Citations counts and Altmetrics.

*Citation counts and Altmetrics. By combining citation counts (what is cited in academic publications) and Altmetrics (what people are discussing online), libraries can gain an understanding of current and emerging research trends and societal interests.

Editorial workflow metrics. Editorial workflow metrics are important for publishers to manage their processes, but they don't provide insights into broader research trends or reader interests.

5. You want to track the effectiveness of your latest marketing campaign for a new journal. Which types of metrics are most helpful?

Answer: usage metrics and Altmetrics

*Usage metrics and Altmetrics. Usage metrics, such as website visits, downloads, and Altmetrics such as mentions in news outlets and social media engagement, provide direct feedback on the effectiveness of your marketing campaign. They allow you to track reach and engagement in real-time.

[D4.4 Training report]

Citation counts. Citation dynamics are different across research areas, whereas citation data processing workflows are too slow to provide timely feedback on the success of a marketing campaign.

6. A publisher wants to optimise publication timelines. Which metrics are most relevant? Which types of metrics are most relevant?

Answer: Editorial workflow metrics.

*Altmetrics. Altmetrics measure the broader outreach of research but don't provide insights into the internal publication process.

Editorial workflow metrics. Editorial workflow metrics provide granular data on each stage of the publication process, from submission to publication. This allows publishers to identify bottlenecks, streamline workflows, and ultimately optimise publications timelines.

7. A reader is interested in finding the most discussed research topics on social media. What types of metrics can help?

Answer: Altmetrics.

Altmetrics are specifically designed to track online engagement and discussions around research, including social media activity. This makes them the ideal tool for readers looking to discover trending topics and join the conversation.

Usage metrics can show what articles are popular, but they don't specifically highlight what's being actively discussed on social media platforms.

[Feedback]

Having considered these scenarios, you can see that metrics offer valuable insights into how a publication is discovered, used, and disseminated:

Tracking them can help publishers design marketing strategies, optimise their policies and workflows and attract new submissions.

Metrics are also valuable for authors, readers and libraries. For example, information about submission, acceptance and publication dates can be helpful to authors when making decisions where to publish.

Metrics can help readers and libraries identify popular and relevant research, as well as current trends and discussions in social media.

Step 3. Analytical tools

Having identified the key metrics relevant to your publishing goals, the next step involves selecting and using the right analytical tools. These tools are essential for collecting, analysing, and reporting on your chosen metrics, transforming raw data into actionable insights.

The following tools, categorised by their primary function, can help you analyse different aspects of your publications' performance and integrate these insights into your workflow.

Usage and engagement / online engagement tools

The following free services can help you understand how readers interact the content on the journal website:

- **Matomo** is a free and open-source web analytics tool, providing detailed insights into visitor behaviour, content engagement, and conversion tracking. It requires installation on the publisher's server.
- **Google Analytics** is a free web-based service that tracks website traffic, user behaviour, and engagement. It provides detailed reports on page views, bounce rates, and traffic sources. However,
- **Google Search Console** is a free web-based service that monitors website performance in Google search, tracking search queries, impressions, and clicks. It helps improve SEO and ensures journal content is discoverable in search engines.

Commonly used free and open-source publishing platforms often offer usage statistics through native features (Janeway) or plugins (Open Journal Systems).

The following commercial services track how users engage with journal content beyond the journal's website:

- **Altmetric Explorer:** A web-based platform that monitors online activity related to research, capturing mentions across social media, news outlets, blogs, policy documents, and more. Managed by Digital Science, it primarily offers subscription-based services, but free tools like the Altmetric Bookmarklet and institutional repository badges are available for researchers and institutions. .
- **PlumX Metrics :** offers a range of metrics on usage and captures (export/saves, readers, bookmarks, favourites) alongside citation and mentions/reactions on social media. It is a paid service offered by Elsevier, but some features are available free of charge for non-profit journals.

Bibliometric and citation databases

OpenCitations Index is an open-access citation index built on bibliographic metadata from sources like Crossref, DataCite, and OpenAIRE. Citation data is available in various formats through SPARQL endpoints, REST APIs, data dumps, or search interfaces like OSCAR and LUCINDA.

OpenAlex is a free, open database of scholarly works, journals, authors, institutions, and research topics. It provides citation counts and subject coverage for journals. Data can be accessed through its web interface, API, or can be downloaded as data dumps for in-depth analysis.

Google Scholar is a free search engine for scholarly content. Although it does not provide analytical data on the journal level, it helps identify highly cited articles from the journal.

When measuring the influence and reach of publications within the academic community, national and institutional research assessment systems often rely on bibliometric data provided by commercial databases. Due to this, authors take into consideration bibliometric data and the ranking of journals in bibliometric databases when choosing where to publish their research. That is why this information is important for Diamond OA publishers. However, a subscription is required to access these services.

- **Web of Science (WoS)** is a multidisciplinary subscription-based platform offering bibliometric data via multiple databases. Its Core Collection includes six databases, four of which cover records from journals. WoS does not provide journal-level analytical data but offers detailed insights into citation data and metrics for individual articles.
- **Journal Citation Reports (JCR)** is a subscription-based service integrated with the Web of Science. It provides bibliometric data for academic journals, such as impact factors, subject categories, citation data, immediacy index, etc.
- **Scopus** is a subscription-based multidisciplinary platform that provides bibliometric data. While it does not offer journal-level analytical data, it delivers detailed insights into citation metrics and data for individual articles.
- **SCImago Journal & Country Rank** is a free service providing bibliometric indicators for journals and countries based on proprietary data from Scopus. Journals can be analysed by subject area, category, or country.

Complex Research Analytics Platforms

A number of commercial platforms offer a broader perspective on research impact by integrating various data sources; However, these platforms typically require substantial financial resources to access the full range of features and data.

- **Dimensions:** is a research analytics platform that integrates different data sources to provide metrics on publications, citations, grants, patents, clinical trials, and policy documents. Dimensions is owned by Digital Science and operates on a freemium business model
- **SciVal (Elsevier)** is a research analytics platform that offers tools to assess the impact of research, track key metrics, and benchmark institutions, researchers, or journals. SciVal is owned by Elsevier and operates on a subscription-based business model.
- **Essential Science Indicators (ESI)**, is a paid analytical tool owned by Clarivate, ranking authors, institutions, countries, and journals based on the publication and citation performance from the Web of Science Core Collection.

To better understand the capabilities of these tools, we encourage you to explore free and simple options firsthand. These suggestions offer a quick initial insight:

- **OpenAlex** : check how a particular journal is represented on this platform.
 1. Go to <https://openalex.org/sources>
 2. Search for your journal
 3. Access and explore analytical data

- **SCIMAGO** : check the ranking of journals from a particular field of research or a country.
 - a. Visit <https://www.scimagojr.com/>
 - b. Search for your journal
 - c. Access and explore journal-level analytical data
 - d. Follow links under Subject Area and Category to see how your journal performs compared to other journals.

Or Go to “Journal rankings” and check relevant subject categories to see how your journal performs compared to other journals.

Step 4. Displaying metrics

The selection and display of metrics depend not only on the perceived relevance to various stakeholders but also on the technical capabilities of the platforms used. Some metrics may require different levels of effort, technical expertise, and support, or they may involve financial resources. This section explores how to effectively present your chosen metrics, considering both audience needs and technical constraints.

Journal-level metrics

Usage and workflow statistics:

- Overall page views and unique visitors to the journal's website
- The average time between manuscript submission and first decision or acceptance
- Submission statistics

Commonly used free and open-source publishing platforms offer usage statistics through native features or plugins. Explore software documentation to learn how to set it up.

- **SJR (SCImago Journal Rank)** is a metric generated by the Scimago Journal & Country Rank service based on Scopus data. Journals can use a free widget to display this information on their websites: <https://www.scimagojr.com/help.php#embeddings>
- **Journal Impact Factor** is a metric generated by Clarivate Analytics through the Journal Citation Reports (JCR). It measures the frequency with which the average article in a journal has been cited in a particular year.

Article-level metrics:

- At least the dates of manuscript submission and acceptance should be publicly displayed both on the landing pages and in the full text.
- **Citation counts** are provided by various services external to the publishing platform, which sometimes offer tools that make it possible to display citation counts on the publishing platform using widgets. This requires different levels of technical expertise and sometimes also financial resources. In most cases, PIDs are crucial for tracking citation counts. If you

[D4.4 Training report]

want to integrate citation counts provided by some of these services, explore the guidelines provided in the Resources section.

- **Altmetric data:** Similarly to citation counts, the information is displayed using widgets. Major providers of this type of information are proprietary and setting up such widgets usually requires financial resources. If you want to integrate Altmetric data in a journal website, explore the guidelines provided in the Resources section.

Step 5. Responsible use of metrics

As Diamond Open Access publishers, evaluating the quality and impact of your publications requires a responsible approach to metrics. Moving beyond traditional impact factors, responsible metrics emphasise a balanced, transparent, and inclusive evaluation of research.

- **Diverse Metrics:** To support diversity and inclusivity in measuring the impact, it is recommended to avoid using Journal Impact Factor (JIF) as a single measure of journal quality and impact of the published content. Instead, Diamond OA publishers and journals should use a variety of quantitative and qualitative indicators to capture a broader spectrum of research impact, including citation metrics, Altmetrics, peer reviews, and societal impact measures. There is also a need to recognise that different disciplines have different norms and impact measures. Besides, complementing quantitative metrics with qualitative evidence, such as peer review comments, case studies, and expert opinions, to provide context for the numbers can ensure narrative context.
- **Transparency and Openness:** It is recommended that the methodologies and tools behind metrics be transparent and understandable so that researchers know how their work is evaluated. Selected metrics should use open datasets whenever possible to allow verification and further analysis by the academic community.
- **Regular updates:** The metrics used should be regularly reviewed and updated to reflect changes in the research environment and technological advancements. These metrics can indicate impact (which can be based on citations or alternative metrics), usage, or efficiency of editorial workflow and decisions (like submission, acceptance and publication dates or rejection rates). The granularity of these metrics can also vary, as they may relate to specific content items like articles or the entire publication.
- **Data privacy:** Diamond OA publishers and service providers must ensure that all data collection and processing activities comply with relevant data protection regulations, such as the [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR) in Europe. It is necessary to implement measures to protect the privacy of users whose data is being collected. This includes anonymizing data where applicable and ensuring secure data storage.

Step 6. Conclusion

Let's recap the key takeaways. Use the flashcards below to review the main concepts. Flip each card to reveal detailed explanations and examples.

Diversity: Go beyond the Impact Factor. Use a variety of metrics (citations, altmetrics, usage data).

Stakeholder needs: Consider the needs of authors, readers, libraries, and funders when selecting and displaying metrics.

Open Tools: Explore free and open tools like OpenCitations and OpenAlex to gather and analyze data.

Privacy: Comply with data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR) and protect user privacy.

Transparency: Be open about your data collection and analysis methods. Use open datasets whenever possible.

Resources

General

“Usage and Metrics.” 2024. European Diamond Capacity Hub. 2024. <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/usage-and-metrics>.

“Visibility, Indexation, Communication, Marketing and Impact.” 2024. European Diamond Capacity Hub. 2024. <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/visibility-indexation-communication-marketing-and-impact>.

Patterson, W., Byers, A.. (2023). Open Access Journals Toolkit: Journal and article-level metrics. <https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/indexing/journal-and-article-level-metrics>

Setting up web analytics tools

Matomo: <https://matomo.org/guide/getting-started/getting-started/>

Google Analytics: <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/9304153?hl=en>

Google Search Console: <https://support.google.com/webmasters/answer/10267942?hl=en>

Displaying citation counts on journal websites and publishing platforms

Crossref Cited-by: Crossref makes it possible to retrieve citation counts through a public API: <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/cited-by/> Journals using Open Journal Systems can install a plugin to display citations in Crossref: <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/crossref-ojs-manual/en/citationsplugin>

Open Citations offers an open API that can be used to retrieve citation counts: <https://opencitations.net/api/v1#/citation-count/{doi}>

Dimensions offers citations badges that are free for non-commercial use: <https://www.dimensions.ai/products/all-products/dimensions-badges/>

[D4.4 Training report]

Scopus offers a free API that can be used to retrieve citation counts: https://dev.elsevier.com/cited_by_scopus.html Journals using Open Journal Systems can install a plugin to display citations in Scopus: <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/crossref-ojs-manual/en/citationsplugin>

Displaying altmetric data on journal websites and publishing platforms

Altmetric com badges: <https://www.altmetric.com/solutions/altmetric-badges/>

PlumX Metrics offers a free widget to non-profit OA journals: <https://www.elsevier.com/insights/metrics/plumx/integrate>

Training material 3 : General communication strategies - Visual guide

General communication strategies in Diamond Open Access publishing

Multimedia: Engage a wider audience by presenting research in accessible and engaging formats. Develop video abstracts, podcasts, infographics that summarise key findings and attract readers beyond traditional academic circles.

Webinars: Foster deeper understanding and engagement by hosting live or recorded webinars featuring authors discussing their work. This provides a platform for direct interaction with the audience and encourages broader dissemination of research insights.

Academic events: Organise and participate in academic events to raise publications' profile within the relevant academic communities.

Cross-journal promotion: Expand your readership and influence by cross-promoting articles in related journals. Collaborate on joint special issues or thematic series to reach a wider audience across different disciplines and foster interdisciplinary dialogue.

Interactions with readers: Cultivate a strong relationship with your readership through interactive content such as surveys and feedback forms. Understanding their interests and needs allows you to tailor the journal's content and improve its overall quality and relevance.

Training material 4 : Planning your communication strategies · self reflection guide.

Introduction

This self-reflection tool is a starting point for a structured communication and marketing plan.

It is designed to help you evaluate your current practices, identify areas for improvement, and explore new opportunities in areas like audience segmentation, marketing activities, social media, press outreach, collaborations, and author support.

Using the questions as a guide, you can reflect on what works well, what can be improved and how to refine your approach.

On the last page, you can download a blank version of this document to fill out, or download a completed version with your answers.

Communication strategy {Questions with text boxes}

- Do you have a communication and marketing strategy and plan? If not, why?
- Who is involved in strategy/plan development?
- What types of information do you rely on when developing your communication plan or strategy?

Marketing activities {Questions with text boxes}

- What are the goals of your marketing activities?
- What channels (email, social media, conferences) do you currently use for marketing?
- What are the main segments of your audience (e.g. authors, reviewers, libraries, funders, etc.)? Do you tailor our messages to different audiences?
- Do you track feedback from your audience(s)? How?
- Do you measure the effectiveness of your marketing activities? How?
- What are the main challenges in reaching your target audience(s)?

Press releases {Questions with text boxes}

- Do you issue press releases (e.g. for platform improvements, groundbreaking articles, etc.)? If not, why?
- Do you collaborate with the media directly to ensure wider media coverage? If not, why?
- Do you track the impact of press releases in terms of readership and engagement? If yes, how?

Social media presence {Questions with text boxes}

- Which social media platforms do you actively use? How do you decide which platforms to use?
- Do you adapt your content to social media and non-academic audiences? For example : impact statements and summaries, infographics, short videos, (simple language), etc.
- How regularly do you post?
- Do you interact with our audience (comments, shares, discussions), or is it mostly one-way communication?
- Do you track engagement? If yes, what type of content gets the most engagement?

Blog/Website {Questions with text boxes}

- Do you have a dedicated blog or website section for news and announcements?
- What type of content do you publish there (editorials, interviews, news, etc)?
- Do you provide impact statements, translations or summaries of publications that could be of interest beyond the research community?

[D4.4 Training report]

- How often do you update it, and how do you promote these updates?
- Do you receive any feedback on your blog/news content? Do you receive any feedback on your blog/news content?

Newsletters {Questions with text boxes}

- Do you send newsletters regularly? If so, how often?
- What content do you include, and how do you determine its relevance?
- How do you track engagement?

Presentations at conferences and workshops {Questions with text boxes}

- Do you promote your journal(s) at conferences/workshops? If yes, what strategies and resources do you use?
- How do you follow up with interested individuals after the event?

Collaborations {Questions with text boxes}

- Do you collaborate with universities, research institutions, or scholarly societies to promote your journal(s)? If yes, what strategies do you use?
- Do you collaborate with other publishers to actively promote your journal(s) and/or published articles? If yes, what strategies do you use?
- What benefits have you observed from these collaborations?

Offering support to authors for promoting their work {Questions with text boxes}

- Do you provide authors with guidelines and resources for promoting their work? Guidelines could include sharing on social media, depositing in repositories, creating impact statements or simple summaries in multiple languages, etc. Resources could include social media kits, promotional videos, or infographics.
- Have you received feedback from authors on the usefulness of these resources?
- Have you analysed the impact of these promotional tools?

Encouraging reviewers to engage beyond reviewing {Questions with text boxes}

- How do you engage reviewers beyond just reviewing (e.g. discussions, events)?
- Do you encourage reviewers to share their reports publicly, if possible? If yes, do you gather feedback from them?

Export the results {Questions with text boxes}

- Download the document in .docx format – whether you've completed the answers or not. If you haven't answered any questions, the exported file will contain just the questions, allowing you to fill them out later or in another tool.
- If you've provided answers, the document will include both the questions and your responses, fully editable for further refinement.

Training material 5: Visual identity – Visual guide

VISUAL IDENTITY in Diamond Open Access publishing

Visual elements like logo, colours, typography, imagery, shape how readers perceive a publisher and its journals. A strong visual identity communicates professionalism and quality at a glance. Here are key strategies to enhance the visibility and perception you need to stand out and attract readership.

#1 - Thematic alignment: be relevant

- Visuals reflect the journal's subject matter. e.g. earth tones for environmental journals.
- Logo embodies its core mission and values.

#2 - High quality: be appealing

- High-quality images and logos.
- Eye-catching graphics on social media.
- A well-designed website with easy navigation and clear content presentation.
- Professional design expertise - if resources allow.

#3 - Consistency: be recognizable

- Unified branded visual identity across all media, such as websites, email communications, social media, print publications and any marketing material (banners, brochures, presentations) for conferences and events.
- A comprehensive style guide outlining the use of logos, colors, typography and other visual elements, for all publications and marketing materials.

13. Equity, diversity, inclusion

Details

Subtitle: Creating fair and inclusive publishing environments

Duration: 60 minutes

Keywords: Equity, diversity, inclusion, belonging, accessibility, gender, language, fair

Abstract: Learn how to enhance publishing quality, fairness and impact through EDIB strategies, focusing on gender diversity, multilingualism and accessibility.

Introduction

There is growing recognition that some established practices in scholarly publishing have contributed to discrimination and exclusion – harming individuals, research, and society more broadly. Addressing these inequities is essential for building fair, responsible, and inclusive publishing systems.

[D4.4 Training report]

This course provides a practical introduction to Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB) in Diamond Open Access publishing. It includes a short presentation to explain the key ideas and examples, as well as tools to help you reflect on your current practices and plan improvements.

In this course, you will learn:

- How discrimination and exclusion can occur in scholarly publishing
- What EDIB means and why it matters
- How to implement EDIB practices in your organisation, focusing on gender diversity, multilingualism, accessibility, and inclusive language

Glossary

Accessibility: The design of products, devices, services, vehicles, or environments so as to be usable by people with disabilities. The concept of accessible design and practice of accessible development ensures both “direct access” (i.e. unassisted) and “indirect access” meaning compatibility with a person’s assistive technology (for example, computer screen readers). Reference/derivation: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accessibility>

• **Accessibility policy:** Formal rules your organisation puts in place to achieve its accessibility requirements: The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) are part of a series of web accessibility guidelines published by the Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) of the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), the main international standards organisation for the Internet. Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Web_Content_Accessibility_Guidelines

• **Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB):** Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) or Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) is a conceptual framework that claims to promote the fair treatment and full participation of all people, especially in the workplace, including populations who have historically been under-represented or subject to discrimination because of their background, identity, disability, etc. Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Diversity,_equity,_and_inclusion

• **Gender diversity:** Equitable or fair representation of people of different genders. It most commonly refers to an equitable ratio of men and women, but also includes people of other genders (e.g. intersex, nonbinary, trans). Reference/derivation: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gender_diversity

• **Multilingualism:** In scholarly publishing, the presence and use of more than one language to disseminate research rather than relying on a single language for scholarly communication. This could include translating individual publications into more than one language, but it also entails a publishing ecosystem where publishing takes place in a variety of languages even when the works published are not translations of one another (e.g. one journal article may be published in Finnish, another in Polish, and another in French). Reference/derivation: Inspired by the Helsinki Initiative (<https://www.helsinki-initiative.org/>)

Training material 1: Introduction to EDIB - interactive course

Step 1. EDIB in Scholarly Publishing

There is a growing recognition that some established practices in scholarly publishing have led to discrimination, harming individuals, research, and society more broadly.

As a Diamond OA publisher or service provider, developing a robust EDIB strategy is key to addressing these issues.

Step 2. Introduction

The first step towards positive change is recognising how discrimination manifests in publishing practices.

Let's explore some real-world examples to see how seemingly neutral practices can reinforce multiple types of inequities at different stages of the publishing process.

In the following slide we'll explore 9 scenarios. Your task is to identify which ones illustrate potential biases and discrimination, and which ones showcase good practices designed to avoid them.

For each publishing scenario that appears, think: 'Is this discrimination or a good practice? What is it about?' then flip the card to check your answer and go to the next scenario.

Step 3. Cards

A journal selects a reviewer with a visual impairment to review a manuscript that is only available as an untagged PDF.

Potential bias – Accessibility

The format might be inaccessible for the reviewer because screen readers rely on tags to navigate and understand the document's layout and content.

A researcher submits a groundbreaking manuscript on transgender health to a prestigious journal. Despite the study's rigour and originality, the reviewers dismiss the findings as "niche" and "lacking broad applicability". They also criticise the author's use of inclusive pronouns (e.g. "they/them") for some participants, deeming it grammatically incorrect and confusing.

Potential bias – Gender

Dismissing the research focus and inclusive language suggests bias against transgender individuals.

Editors use diverse methods for identifying potential reviewers, such as searching databases, attending conferences, and seeking recommendations from a wider range of colleagues, to expand their pool beyond personal networks.

Good Practice – Multiple forms

[D4.4 Training report]

Broadening the reviewer pool helps reduce potential biases that can stem from limited networks.

A review criticises a manuscript for lacking citations from established scholars in the field. However, the manuscript primarily cites relevant research from scholars based in the Global South, which the reviewers seem unfamiliar with.

Potential bias – Geographic Location

Dismissing relevant research from the Global South suggests a potential devaluation of non-Western perspectives.

A researcher with dyslexia submits a paper to a journal. The journal requests revisions and offers comprehensive support services, including both translation assistance and reviews focused on inclusive language.

Good Practice – Accessibility

Providing writing support removes barriers for researchers who struggle with the writing process.

A prestigious international conference (about a global issue or non western subject) stopped mandating English as the sole language for presentations and discussions. It now encourages presentations in other languages, offers simultaneous translation services and provides materials in multiple languages.

Good practice – Language

Promoting multilingual access facilitates participation from researchers around the world.

A female researcher's study faced repeated rejections from top journals, resulting in a less prestigious publication. Meanwhile, a male colleague's similar research, using a sample overwhelmingly composed of men, was swiftly accepted by a prestigious journal and widely cited.

Potential bias – Gender

This disparity suggests a possible bias favoring male researchers and male-focused studies, while undervaluing research conducted by women.

The journal's/publisher's website details a clear procedure for name changes on published works, outlining steps for updating metadata across platforms (website, databases, indexing services), ORCID, and other identifiers.

Good practice – Gender

Simplifying the name change process supports gender transitions and accurate attribution of authorship.

A research team from a non-Western country submits a manuscript using terminology common in their cultural context. The reviewers, unfamiliar with these terms, criticise the language as "unclear" and "imprecise," leading to the paper's rejection.

Potential bias – Cultural and Linguistic

The rejection based on unfamiliar terminology reveals a Western-centric bias in the review process, potentially marginalizing valuable research from other cultural contexts.

Step 4. Scenarios

These scenarios highlight the importance of recognising subtle forms of discrimination that affect individuals from diverse marginalised groups.

Institutional affiliation	Language	Gender
High-status institutions / Less prestigious institutions	Dominant language speakers / Non-speakers and non-native speakers	Men / Women, transgender & non- binary individuals
Race and Ethnicity	Ability	Other
Dominant / Marginalised racial/ethnic groups	Able-bodied individuals / Individuals with disabilities	Religion, socio-economic status, geographic location, sexual orientation...

Step 5.

It's difficult to fully grasp how significant and widespread disparities are in scholarly publishing. Multiple, intersecting factors contribute to a complex and evolving landscape of inequality.

Disciplinary and geographic variations: diversity fluctuates significantly across academic fields and locations.

Intersectionality: people can face multiple layers of disadvantage due to the combined effects of their race, gender, economic status, and other identities.

Data gaps: limited data collection and privacy concerns lead to insufficient information about certain groups and the discriminations they experience.

Encouraging trends: while some disciplines show progress in closing gaps, setbacks and emerging challenges persist.

Step 6

Such discrimination has multiple and far-reaching consequences.

Individuals

Marginalised scholars often face career setbacks, reduced visibility and limited opportunities.

- Publication rates: marginalised groups may face higher manuscript rejection rates.
- Professional opportunities: they get fewer invitations for prestigious roles, such as peer reviewers or editors.
- Access: they may face barriers to accessing scholarly resources and publishing opportunities.
- Research: they are often underrepresented in research topics and study samples, and their needs and contributions are overlooked.
- Indexing and visibility: their work is less likely to be indexed in prestigious databases.

Research

A lack of diversity leads to homogeneous perspectives, overlooking crucial subjects and limiting the scope and impact of findings.

- Publication rates: marginalised groups may face higher manuscript rejection rates.
- Professional opportunities: they get fewer invitations for prestigious roles, such as peer reviewers or editors.
- Access: they may face barriers to accessing scholarly resources and publishing opportunities.
- Research: they are often underrepresented in research topics and study samples, and their needs and contributions are overlooked.
- Indexing and visibility: their work is less likely to be indexed in prestigious databases.

Society

Unequal representation in knowledge creation perpetuates existing inequalities and results in uneven societal benefits.

- A lack of research on accessibility needs results in inaccessible environments, further marginalising people with disabilities.
- A lack of research on the specific healthcare needs of transgender individuals can lead to inadequate or discriminatory medical care, negatively impacting their health and well-being.
- Underrepresentation of women in STEM research reinforces the male dominance of these fields, perpetuating a discriminatory environment and discouraging women from pursuing STEM careers.

Step 7.

Awareness is the first step, because habit is the first obstacle. Discrimination often stems from deeply rooted mechanisms that permeate the field.

Consider the following scenario:

An editorial board, composed primarily of senior researchers from prominent European institutions, is tasked with selecting peer reviewers for new submissions.

Their current process relies on personal networks and databases, but the board recognises the potential for bias in this approach.

Which concerns might they reasonably have? Click below to answer the question, and close the panel to continue. Feel free to close the panel to reread the scenario – your answers are retained.

- **Familiarity and/or Homogeneity Bias** : The board might lean towards reviewers they know personally or by reputation, and/or from similar backgrounds and viewpoints.
- **Prestige and Geographic Bias**: Reviewers from less prestigious institutions or located outside of Europe might be overlooked, even if their expertise is highly relevant.
- **Citation Metrics Bias**: Over-reliance on citation metrics can disadvantage researchers who face systemic barriers to publishing and gaining citations.
- **Homogenous Editorial Board**: The lack of diversity within the editorial board itself can perpetuate a cycle of exclusion, as their networks are likely to reflect similar demographics and perspectives.

Step 8

This exercise highlights a crucial point: bias can operate on multiple levels.

Individual

Our personal experiences and societal conditioning can lead us to favour certain groups. We tend to favor what is similar or familiar to us, and overestimate prestige while underestimating the lack of it. This kind of bias can influence publishing practices, such as choosing reviewers or evaluating manuscripts.

Structural

Systems and processes themselves can be biased. Relying on citation metrics disadvantages researchers facing systemic barriers to publication, while a homogenous editorial board is likely to perpetuate existing inequalities due to the limitations of its network, reinforcing power dynamics

Step 9

Addressing these issues in scholarly publishing is about creating an environment where everyone has equal opportunities and representation, which benefits individuals, research, and society as a whole.

This is what EDIB stands for : Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, Belonging.

Let's delve into the meaning of these principles with this activity. Drag the words in the right definition.

Diversity : Ensuring that people of different sexes, genders, abilities, career stages, races, ethnicities, geographic and institutional locations, and linguistic and cultural backgrounds are represented in the community.

[D4.4 Training report]

Belonging: Treating everyone as a full member of the community and helping them to thrive so they feel a valued, accepted and able to engage fully.

Inclusion: Ensuring that all individuals are welcomed, visible, heard and considered.

Equity: Removing systemic barriers and biases and providing the necessary support to enable everyone to have fair access to opportunities and resources regardless of background or location.

Step 10

EDIB cannot be the responsibility of any one individual. It requires a collective effort. Different actors in the scholarly publishing ecosystem, including authors, peer reviewers, editors, editorial board members, librarians, and Diamond OA publishers, can play a role to address various facets of EDIB such as:

Gender diversity

Gender diversity in scholarly publishing aims to counteract historical biases and the underrepresentation and marginalisation of women, non-binary individuals, and other gender minorities.

Diamond OA publishers can help to break the cycle by implementing inclusive policies, diversifying editorial teams and reviewer pools, mitigating bias in peer review, and promoting equitable research practices.

Accessibility

Accessibility addresses the exclusion of individuals with disabilities from fully participating in scholarly discourse.

You can design products or services for both direct (unassisted) and indirect (assistive technology compatible) access to content, metadata, and digital functionality. Key elements include clear fonts, appropriate line spacing, descriptive image alt text, captions, and plain language summaries.

Multilingualism

Multilingualism challenges the dominance of English in academic publishing, which has historically marginalized non-Anglophone researchers and knowledge.

You can promote linguistic diversity by supporting translations, offering language services, and ensuring metadata is accessible across languages, thus expanding the global reach and impact of research while reducing language-based inequities.

Inclusive language

Inclusive language challenges our tendency to adopt default perspectives, which may implicitly favour certain groups and marginalize others.

You can foster inclusivity by consciously choosing language that recognizes diversity, promotes equal opportunities and ensures everyone feels visible, heard and considered.

Step 11

Publishers are particularly well-placed to drive improvements. You can set goals and design policies that bring about meaningful change.

To support your efforts, here are 3 downloadable checklists for best practices :

Gender diversity [[downloadable file](#)]

Accessibility and inclusion [[Downloadable file](#)]

Multilingualism [[Downloadable file](#)]

These checklists will help you assess your current practices, identify areas for improvement, and track your progress toward a more equitable and inclusive publishing environment.

We encourage you to use these tools to advance EDIB within your organisation.

Training material 2. Gender Diversity self-reflection guide (interactive course)

Introduction

This tool is designed to guide you through advancing gender diversity in your publishing workflows. Whether you're looking to conduct a thorough review, plan strategic interventions, or gain insights into your organisation's commitment to inclusivity, it provides a flexible framework to support your efforts.

The tool outlines 12 good practices, strategically grouped into three categories:

- **Easy:** Practices that are simple, require minimal resources, and can be implemented quickly.
- **Moderate:** Practices that need more effort or resources but are achievable with modest costs.
- **Long-term:** Practices requiring additional planning, resources, or a longer timeframe to implement.

For each practice, use the blank space to reflect on:

- What is your current status of implementation?
- What specific steps are you already taking?
- Where do you see potential for improvement?
- What actionable next steps can you identify?
- What barriers or challenges might you encounter?

By the end of the assessment, you'll have created a comprehensive view of your current gender diversity efforts. This approach allows you to identify areas for improvement and understand the steps you've already taken. You can also generate a tracking sheet to organise your goals, assign tasks, set deadlines, and monitor the implementation of your action plan.

Easy

Awareness of unconscious bias is raised, and information and/or basic training on how to avoid it is provided to authors, peer reviewers, editors, editorial board members, and employees.

[D4.4 Training report]

Why: This is a crucial first step towards fostering critical self-reflection and organisational change. It encourages individuals and the organisation as a whole to identify and address biases within editorial processes. How: Introduce training about unconscious bias. Resources should be made readily available to staff and bias awareness should be incorporated into regular editorial meetings.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Inclusive language and images are encouraged in manuscript preparation

Why: Encouraging use of inclusive language and images helps to avoid perpetuating harmful stereotypes and gender disparities. How: Update author guidelines with clear expectations for inclusive language and image selection. Provide examples of best practices and resources like inclusive stock image libraries. Consider a pre-submission checklist for authors to self-assess their manuscript.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Gender-neutral or gender-inclusive language is encouraged for peer review and editorial feedback.

Why: Respectful, inclusive feedback avoids potential misgendering and ensures feedback focuses solely on the merits of the work, rather than the author's perceived identity. How: Share a concise guide on gender-neutral language with editors and reviewers. Emphasise using "they/them" pronouns when unsure, avoiding gendered salutations, and focusing on constructive criticism of the work itself.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

An EDIB statement addressing gender diversity is crafted and shared to signal to authors and readers that the IPSP/journal values and seeks a range of perspectives.

Why: Publicly advocating for gender diversity distinguishes your journal as inclusive, attracts individuals who share your values, and holds your journal accountable for achieving its stated goals. How: Develop a statement that clearly states your journal or organisation's approach to gender diversity, using available resources to ensure key areas are covered. Share the statement prominently on your website and ensure it is referred to in author and editor-facing processes, policies and communications.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Moderate**An appropriately gender-diverse pool of authors, reviewers, editors, and board members is sought. Progress is tracked, and an action plan is developed and implemented. Once established, reviews are solicited from the various genders in appropriate proportions.**

Why: A diverse pool enriches research quality through varied perspectives, mitigates bias, and fosters a truly inclusive scholarly environment. How: Set diversity targets, actively recruit from underrepresented groups. Encourage feedback to help reflect on and improve processes. Make sure progress is recorded and shared with all those involved.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Authors and peer reviewers are offered the option to self-report their gender (including non-binary options). Progress towards meeting diversity goals is monitored and tracked. Author privacy is respected in cases where they choose not to self-report.

Why: Gathering demographic data (while respecting privacy) is crucial for tracking progress, informing outreach, and assessing effectiveness of diversity initiatives. How: Offer a secure, confidential self-reporting option with inclusive gender categories. Honor choices not to disclose. Encourage feedback to help reflect on and improve processes. Make sure progress is recorded and shared with all those involved.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

A policy requiring authors to submit a citation diversity statement is implemented.

Why: Broadening cited works amplifies marginalised voices, reduces systemic citation bias, and enriches the overall scholarly conversation. How: Add to your author information and submission guidelines to include a requirement for a citation diversity statement, including examples of the key points that should be covered in the statement. Share the statement prominently on your website and ensure it is referred to in author and editor-facing processes, policies and communications.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

A policy ensuring appropriate representation and reporting of sex/gender in research subjects/study populations is implemented.

Why: Accurate and appropriate sex/gender reporting minimises bias, enhances research utility (especially in fields like health, where not reporting on gender could reduce the usefulness of the findings for some populations), and promotes inclusivity. How: Implement clear reporting guidelines while respecting participant privacy rights and offering appropriate options for self-identification. Note that some study participants may not wish to report their gender, and their right to privacy must be respected.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Double-anonymous review (author and reviewer are unknown to one another) is implemented to reduce reviewer gender bias.

Why: Concealing author identities minimises potential reviewer bias based on demographics, promoting fairer evaluation of research. How: Implement a system where both author and reviewer identities are hidden throughout the review process.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Long-term

Author diversity audits are conducted regularly.

Why: Regular audits provide essential data on representation trends, enabling data-driven decisions to improve diversity and inclusion efforts. How: Conduct surveys or analyse publication data to assess author demographics. Use findings to inform targeted interventions and track progress.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Implementation of open review is considered, with an assessment of its impact on marginalised authors.

Why: While open review can promote inclusion and foster broader community engagement and transparency, it's crucial to consider the potential disadvantages of this openness for some authors (e.g. those from disadvantaged gender minorities). How: Carefully weigh the potential benefits and risks of open review, considering its impact on all authors.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Gender-diverse employees (including those in senior positions) are hired and retained, to encourage diversity in attitudes and practices.

Why: Diverse teams foster diverse perspectives, challenge biases, and create a more inclusive and equitable organisational culture. How: Implement proactive recruitment strategies targeting underrepresented groups, create inclusive hiring processes, and foster a supportive environment for retention.

[Text boxes for users to answer questions]

Training material 3. Multilingualism self-reflection guide (interactive course)

Introduction

This tool is designed to guide you through advancing multilingualism in your publishing workflows. Whether you're looking to conduct a thorough review, plan strategic interventions, or gain insights into your organisation's commitment to inclusivity, it provides a flexible framework to support your efforts.

The tool outlines good practices, strategically grouped into three categories:

- **Easy:** Practices that are simple, require minimal resources, and can be implemented quickly.
- **Moderate:** Practices that need more effort or resources but are achievable with modest costs.
- **Long-term:** Practices requiring additional planning, resources, or a longer timeframe to implement.

For each practice, use the blank space to reflect on:

- What is your current status of implementation?
- What specific steps are you already taking?
- Where do you see potential for improvement?
- What actionable next steps can you identify?

- What barriers or challenges might you encounter?

By the end of the assessment, you'll have created a comprehensive view of your current multilingualism efforts. This approach allows you to identify areas for improvement and understand the steps you've already taken. You can also generate a tracking sheet to organise your goals, assign tasks, set deadlines, and monitor the implementation of your action plan.

Easy

There's a policy stating that submissions are accepted and content decisions are made without regard to the author's language background.

Why: It ensures a fair and inclusive process that prioritises research merit. It broadens the scope of published work and enriches the scholarly conversation. How: Formalise a statement in your submission guidelines explicitly mentioning that submissions will be evaluated based on their scholarly merit and relevance, not the author's native language. Ensure that all editors and staff are aware of this policy and trained to implement it consistently. Actively promote this policy to encourage submissions from authors with diverse linguistic backgrounds.

Peer review feedback forms include a statement that linguistic quality alone is not a sufficient reason for rejecting a submission.

Why: It encourages submissions from non-native speakers and recognises that language can be improved during the editorial process. How: Modify your peer review feedback forms to include a clear statement that reviewers should focus on the scientific quality, methodology, and significance of the research, and not solely on the language. Provide reviewers with guidelines on offering constructive feedback on language issues, focusing on clarity and comprehensibility rather than grammatical perfection.

Authors are required to report the language sensitivity of their research data.

Why: It ensures transparency about the potential impact of language on research findings, particularly in qualitative studies or research involving language as a variable. How: Include a section in the submission guidelines requiring authors to describe the role of language in their data collection and analysis. Provide examples of how to address language sensitivity (e.g., translation processes, interpretation issues, cultural nuances in language). Offer guidance on how to transparently report any limitations in the research due to language factors.

Authors are provided with contact details for affordable, reputable editing and translation services with whom our organisation can work effectively.

Why: It lowers the barrier to publication for authors who may not have access to or afford professional language support. How: Compile a list of recommended language editing and translation services, ensuring they have expertise in the relevant subject areas. Negotiate

[D4.4 Training report]

potential partnerships with these services to offer discounted rates for authors. Make this list readily available to authors on the journal website and during the submission process.

Awareness about unconscious linguistic bias is raised and resources are provided to authors, reviewers, editors, and staff to minimise their own.

Why: It educates authors, reviewers, and editors about potential biases related to language, promoting fairer evaluation and a more inclusive environment. How: Offer workshops, webinars, or online resources on linguistic bias. Include information on unconscious bias in reviewer and editor training materials, emphasising the importance of focusing on the content rather than surface-level language errors. Encourage self-reflection and discussion among editors and reviewers about their own potential biases.

Clear writing and translation-friendly style are promoted, and resources for developing such content are provided to authors for abstracts and articles.

Why: It facilitates easier understanding for a wider audience, including those who may rely on machine translation. It also simplifies the translation process for human translators. How: Provide authors with clear guidelines and resources on writing in plain language, avoiding jargon, idioms, and complex sentence structures. Offer examples of best practices for writing abstracts and articles that are concise, clear, and easily translatable.

Guidelines, policies, and other informational texts are written in a translation-friendly style. Communications also follow this style.

Why: It makes information accessible to a wider audience and demonstrates a commitment to multilingualism. How: Review all website content, guidelines, policies, and communications to ensure they are written in a clear and concise style that is easy to translate. Use plain language and avoid idioms or complex sentence structures.

Linguistic citation diversity (i.e., citing work in other languages) is promoted, and guidelines are provided to authors.

Why: It broadens the scope of scholarly discourse, recognises valuable research published in languages other than English, and reduces systemic bias in citation practices. How: Authors must submit a linguistic citation diversity statement with their manuscript. Include in author guidelines a clear encouragement to cite relevant work in multiple languages. Provide examples of how to include and reference non-English language sources correctly. Explain the importance of linguistic diversity in citations for a comprehensive literature review.

Linguistic citation diversity is evaluated during peer review.

Why: It broadens the scope of scholarly discourse, recognises valuable research published in languages other than English, and reduces systemic bias in citation practices. How: Instruct reviewers to consider the breadth of linguistic diversity in the cited works. Provide them with guidance on how to assess the appropriateness and relevance of non-English citations.

An automatic translation tool is provided, with clear disclaimers regarding its limitations.

Why: It provides immediate access to content in multiple languages, expanding reach and accessibility. How: If the translation widget on the website is machine-based, clearly state that machine translation is not perfect and should be used with caution. Offer the option to view the original language version.

Moderate**Plain language and translation-friendly summaries are requested and published alongside abstracts, both online and/or in articles.**

Why: It makes research findings accessible to a wider audience, including those who may not be specialists in the field or native English speakers. How: Provide clear guidelines on writing effective summaries, emphasising conciseness and avoidance of technical jargon. Offer examples of good plain language summaries. Make these summaries available in all languages where the abstract is available.

Abstracts are published in at least two languages.

Why: It increases the visibility and discoverability of research for non-English speaking audiences. How: Request authors to provide translations of their abstracts, or offer translation services. If offering translation services, ensure they are high-quality and accurate. Establish a workflow for managing and publishing multilingual abstracts.

Clear, accessible, and permissive guidelines are provided to publish the same or similar works in other languages (with due acknowledgement).

Why: It facilitates the dissemination of research to a wider audience and allows authors to reach readers in their native language. How: Develop clear guidelines for authors who wish to publish their work in other languages, including procedures for acknowledging the original publication.

Goals for diverse linguistic representation among the editorial board and peer reviewers are set and monitored.

Why: It brings diverse perspectives to the editorial process and ensures fair evaluation of submissions from different linguistic backgrounds. How: Collect data on the linguistic backgrounds of editorial board members and peer reviewers (e.g., native languages, language proficiencies). Set targets for increasing representation from diverse linguistic groups. Implement strategies to recruit editors and reviewers with varied linguistic expertise. Regularly monitor progress towards these goals and report on the findings.

Translator contributions are explicitly recognised.

Why: It values the important work of translators and gives them appropriate credit. How: Include a by-line field under the author's name, or offer a certificate similar to those provided to peer

reviewers. Acknowledge translators in the article metadata. Establish clear guidelines on how and when translators should be credited.

Peer review training and guidelines are offered in multiple languages.

Why: It makes training accessible to reviewers from diverse linguistic backgrounds. How: Translate peer review training materials and guidelines into the languages most relevant to your reviewer pool. Ensure that language versions are equivalent in content and quality.

Long-term

Abstracts and full texts are published in two or more languages, in the same or separate documents, if the authors provide the translations.

Why: It maximises accessibility and reach of research. How: Establish a clear workflow and guidelines for publishing multilingual abstracts and full texts. Provide authors with support and resources for preparing translations.

The number/proportion of multilingual abstracts and full texts is tracked and publicly shared.

Why: It demonstrates commitment to multilingualism and provides valuable data for assessing progress. How: Develop a system for tracking the language diversity of published content. Regularly report on the proportion of abstracts and full texts available in multiple languages. Make this data publicly available on the journal website or in annual reports.

Content is published in machine-translation-friendly formats.

Why: It facilitates machine translation, making content more accessible to a wider audience. How: Publish articles in HTML format in addition to PDF. Use semantic HTML markup to improve the structure and clarity of the content for machine translation. Avoid using images to convey text, as this hinders machine translation.

Policies, guidelines, informational texts and calls for papers are available in at least two languages.

Why: It ensures that all key information is accessible to a global audience. How: Ensure consistent information across all versions. Establish a process for translating and updating website content regularly. Prioritise the translation of essential pages, such as submission guidelines, editorial policies, and contact information.

English metadata is provided for non-English content.

Why: It improves discoverability of non-English content through search engines and databases. How: Provide English translations of titles, abstracts, keywords, and other metadata for articles published in other languages. Use standardised metadata formats that support multiple languages. Ensure that multilingual metadata is properly processed and displayed.

Professional translation and language-check services for authors are subsidised or fully supported.

Why: It removes significant barriers for authors who wish to publish in multiple languages. How: Explore funding opportunities to support translation and language-check services. Partner with translation agencies to offer discounted rates or subsidies to authors. Establish a system for authors to access and use these services.

Training material 4. Accessibility self-reflection guide (interactive course)

Introduction

This tool is designed to guide you through improving the accessibility of your publishing workflows. Whether you're looking to conduct a thorough review, plan strategic interventions, or gain insights into your organisation's commitment to inclusivity, it provides a flexible framework to support your efforts.

The tool outlines good practices, grouped into 6 categories:

- Compliance
- Policy & commitment
- Expertise and support
- Accessible content
- Alternative formats
- Inclusive language and imagery

For each practice, use the blank space to reflect on:

- What is your current status of implementation?
- What specific steps are you already taking?
- Where do you see potential for improvement?
- What actionable next steps can you identify?
- What barriers or challenges might you encounter?

By the end of the tool, you'll have created a comprehensive view of your current accessibility efforts. This approach allows you to identify areas for improvement and understand the steps you've already taken. You can also generate a tracking sheet to organise your goals, assign tasks, set deadlines, and monitor the implementation of your action plan.

Compliance

International accessibility standards (e.g., WCAG 2.2) are understood and followed consistently.

[D4.4 Training report]

Why: It demonstrates a commitment to inclusivity and ensures content is usable by people with a wide range of disabilities. How: familiarise yourself with WCAG 2.2 guidelines and integrate them into your content creation and publishing workflows. Regularly review and update practices to align with the latest standards.

Regional accessibility legislation and guidelines are actively monitored and implemented.

Why: It allows you to meet legal requirements and demonstrate your commitment to serving your local community. This builds trust and reinforces your reputation as a responsible member of the publishing ecosystem. How: Ensure that your policies and practices comply with all applicable legal requirements. Establish a process for monitoring updates to legislation and recommendations.

Policy & commitment

Accessibility is a strategic and operational priority and not treated as an afterthought or a one-off activity.

Why: It fosters a culture of inclusivity and leads to more effective and sustainable accessibility solutions. How: Include accessibility as a core principle in your organisation's mission and values. Integrate accessibility considerations into all stages of the publishing workflow. Allocate resources and assign responsibilities for accessibility.

An accessibility statement is available. It outlines the commitments and practices in place, and encourages authors, peer reviewers, and editors to adopt similar approaches.

Why: It demonstrates transparency and accountability, and fosters a shared responsibility for inclusive publishing. How: The statement can outline your commitment to accessibility, the standards you follow (e.g., WCAG), the features and services you provide to ensure accessibility, how to provide feedback or request alternative formats, and an encouragement for authors, reviewers, and editors to consider accessibility in their contributions. Publish the statement prominently on your website.

Expertise and support

We have staff with appropriate expertise.

Why: It ensures that you have the knowledge and skills to implement effective accessibility practices. This internal capacity strengthens your commitment to inclusivity and allows for proactive problem-solving. How: Invest in training and development for your staff on accessibility best practices. Recruit individuals with specialised knowledge in accessibility. Designate an accessibility officer or team to oversee implementation and provide support.

Resources and guidance on creating accessible and inclusive content for authors and reviewers are provided.

Why: It empowers contributors to create content that is usable by everyone. How: Develop guidelines and tutorials on accessible content creation. Offer workshops or training sessions on accessibility for authors and reviewers. Provide templates or tools to facilitate the creation of accessible documents.

Accessible content

Content is presented in a logical reading order and uses clear language.

Why: It enhances comprehension and makes the content more accessible to a wider audience, particularly people using assistive technologies. How: Implement structured content creation processes. Use headings and subheadings to organise content. Write in plain language, avoiding jargon and complex sentences.

Publications include page numbers.

Why: It provides essential navigational cues for all readers, particularly those using assistive technologies or referencing specific sections of the text.: author guidelines ?

Fonts, colour, size, and line spacing are adjustable.

Why: It empowers your readers to customize their reading experience with adjustable display settings according to their individual needs and preferences. This enhances readability and accessibility for users with visual impairments or other reading difficulties. How: Use web technologies and design practices that allow these adjustments. Ensure sufficient colour contrast between text and background. Avoid relying solely on colour to convey information.

Presentation and content are separated.

Why: It ensures that content can be adapted to different formats and devices without losing its meaning or structure. This is crucial for accessibility and allows content to be accessed by users with a variety of assistive technologies. How: Use structured markup (e.g., HTML) to define content elements. Employ CSS for styling and presentation. Avoid using tables for layout.

Alternative formats

Alternative text descriptions for all images in our publications are provided.

Why: It allows screen readers to convey the meaning and context of visual content to users who are blind or visually impaired.

How: Provide guidelines, training and/or tools for authors and editors on writing effective alt text. Ensure all images have accurate and concise alternative text.

Captions or transcripts for videos are provided.

[D4.4 Training report]

Why: It makes multimedia content accessible to individuals who are deaf or hard of hearing, as well as those who prefer to read text.

How: Establish a workflow for captioning or transcribing videos. Provide guidelines and tools for authors on creating captions/transcripts. Ensure captions/transcripts are accurate and synchronised.

Plain language summary is provided alongside journal articles/the traditional scientific abstract.

Why: It makes complex research findings more accessible to non-specialist audiences, readers with lower literacy levels, and those using a non-dominant language. How: Provide author guidelines on creating plain language summaries. Offer examples of effective plain language summaries.

Inclusive language and imagery**We use respectful language that reflects human diversity, promotes equal opportunities, and avoids defaulting to the point of view of traditionally dominant groups (e.g., Western, male, White, able-bodied).**

Why: It avoids perpetuating harmful stereotypes and creates a welcoming and inclusive environment for all your readers. How: Provide guidelines, tools and/or training for editors and authors.

Images reflect human diversity and avoid stereotypes.

Why: It avoids perpetuating harmful stereotypes and creates a welcoming and inclusive environment for all your readers. How: Provide guidelines on selecting inclusive images, access to image libraries with diverse and inclusive visuals. Review images for representational bias.

Data visualisations are designed to avoid biased representations.

Why: It ensures that data is presented accurately and objectively, preventing the perpetuation of harmful stereotypes or misinterpretations. How: Provide guidance on creating accessible and unbiased data visualisations. Use clear labels and avoid misleading scales or chart types. Consider the needs of users with colour vision deficiencies.

Annex 3 - Feedback questionnaire

1. How relevant is this topic to your work on current or future projects?

Highly relevant
Relevant
Interesting but not applicable
No answer

2. What was your level of familiarity with this topic before starting the course?

No prior experience.
Have implemented some aspects.
Have actively worked with it occasionally.
Have actively and regularly worked with it.
No answer

3. Which learning outcomes/ goals do you think you achieved? (Select all that apply)

I can identify appropriate funding sources for Diamond open access journals and those that should be avoided or handled with caution.
I recognise the main funding challenges of Diamond open access publishing, such as long-term sustainability, diverse contexts, and editorial independence.
I can identify common strategies to address these challenges, such as diversifying funding sources and in-kind contributions.
I can apply what I learned to a few simple scenarios – such as maintaining financial sustainability without mandatory fees, ensuring ethical sponsorship agreements, suggesting effective library support strategies, transitioning from APC-based models, and planning sustainable practices for launching new journals.

4. What was the most important thing you learned? Please provide an example of how you could apply this in your work. Is there anything you would like to explore further, anything you feel is missing, or anything that was unclear?

[Free text field]

5. How well did this course match your learning needs?

I knew most of this already.
A good balance between familiar content and new insights.
Perfect level for my needs.
Good foundation, but I need more advanced content now.
More than I needed for my role.
No answer

**6. How would you rate the following aspects of the course based on your experience?
Rate each: 1 = Poor / Needs improvement 2 = Adequate 3 = Good / Worked well.**

Clarity of explanations – could you easily understand the material?

Usefulness of examples and case studies – did they help you understand and apply what you've learned?

Course length – was the duration suitable for the content?

Navigation – was it easy to find your way through the course?

Visual design and layout – were it clear and comfortable to follow?

Format – did you appreciate the structure (e.g. conversation, infographic)?

Enjoyment – Was the course pleasant to follow?

7. Do you have any other comments or suggestions? We welcome any thoughts you could have about this course.

[Free text field]

Thank you for your feedback! We appreciate your time and will use your responses to improve this course.